

Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy

Monograph

An inordinate fondness for Silversaga and her patterns: the Clara, Eleonora, and Juliette

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Abstract

Jessica Silversaga is a Swedish pattern designer, photographer, and sewist. She is the owner of Silversaga Patterns, which began as a slow fashion RTW label before transitioning entirely to sewing patterns in 2023. She has some ~200 designs, of which 15 are available for purchase as sewing patterns. Silversaga's patterns have attracted a sizeable community of sewists, mostly on Instagram, who have documented their makes of her patterns. These makes number in the thousands; too much for a single taxonomist to singlehandedly catalog. As such, in this monograph, we focus on breadth instead of depth, by cataloging only a small but reflective sample of makes; that of the Clara (Argenclaridae), Eleonora (Argenteleonoridae), and Juliette (Juliettidae). The diversity and versatility of Silversaga's designs is reflected in the 15 families, 5 orders, and countless more genera and infrageneric taxa dedicated to Silversaga's patterns, scattered polyphyletically throughout the kingdom Abtruncusa.

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saga’s Eleonora pattern from other patterns also named Eleonora.

The LCT-01, developed as a hobby, has its roots in the observations that the well-established system of biological taxonomy was well-suited to naming millions of seemingly diverse and unclassifiable animals, plants, bacteria, and fungi; and that this system could be reused and adapted to something as similarly diverse: fashion. Just as taxonomists have helped humanity learn about the beauty of Earth’s lifeforms (think *Tyrannosaurus rex*), we too hope that our taxonomy work can help people begin to realize how diverse clothing is, and appreciate the craft and effort behind each make; especially from indie designers like Silversaga.

The taxonomy uses the eight major ranks Domain, Kingdom, Phylum, Class, Order, Family, Genus, and Species, akin to biological taxonomy.

The LCT-01 differs from most other systems in its emphasis on grouping by construction (or in biological terms, morphology). Examples of characteristics we classify garments based on include, but are not limited to, necklines, sleeve length, buttons, dress length, straps, ruffles; while those that we set aside are characteristics like the collection a dress was part of (e.g. “Summer/Spring 2022”), the designer, and even the aesthetic of a specific dress (e.g. “cottagecore”). Regardless, “cottagecore” still affects the LCT-01 classification, but indirectly. A cottagecore dress often has puff sleeves, ruffles, lace, floral patterns, and pastel colors; these characteristics that arise from decomposing the meaning of “cottagecore” into its constituent parts are what inform the classification of a specific garment.

However, the LCT-01 is not intended to replace any already-existing systems; but rather, coexist with them. Linnaeus’s decision to name the cat *Felis catus* does not mean that every human is required to refer to their cat as “instances of *Felis catus*”. We aim to be one of the many glasses people can put on to look at the world.

Copyright

We understand the importance of intellectual property rights in the sewing world. We do not reupload or directly embed images or sewing patterns. We find it important to distinguish the *product* from *information about the product* (metadata). We do not distribute the products under any circumstances, but we do freely redistribute *information* about the product. Per the U.S. Copyright Office’s FAQs on the scope of copyright (at <https://www.copyright.gov/help/faq/faq-protect.html>), ideas are not eligible for copyright, but expressions of those ideas are.

How do I protect my idea?

Copyright does not protect ideas, concepts, systems, or methods of doing something. You may express your ideas in writing or drawings and claim copyright in your description, but be aware that copyright will not protect the idea itself as revealed in your written or artistic work.

We have written our own descriptions, our own monographs, and expressed the ideas, and information about the ideas in our own words. If the scientific paper format of the LCT-01’s monographs is disregarded, our documents may essentially be the same as blog posts that describe, criticize, or provide commentary on a product. These posts also often include a significant original component; the blog post may contain photographs of the sewist’s make; while our original component is the aggregation of several of these blog posts and the application of a Linnaean-style taxonomic system to organizing them.

That aside, we license our original content under CC BY 4.0, meaning that anyone, especially sewists, are free to do almost anything they want with our material.

1 Background

We intend for this background section pertaining to Jessica Silversaga to be an introduction to her for the entire taxonomy; in future monographs, we plan to refer back to this section.

1.1 Jessica Silversaga

Jessica Silversaga (<https://silversagapatterns.com>; Instagram: @silversagapatterns; personal Instagram: @jessicasilversaga) is a Swedish photographer, pattern designer, and sewist. She now lives in southern France, and has two cats, Ada (“Friends of TFS - Jessica Silversaga” 2025), and Alice.

In high school, she took journalism & photography; and in 2005, she graduated with a Bachelor of Photography from the Mid Sweden University.

She became interested in sewing after taking a beginner’s sewing class. Most patterns and RTW garments available to her were incompatible with her petite frame and smaller cup size. In her late 20s, Silversaga began taking pattern drafting classes in Stockholm.

In late 2018, she launched the slow fashion RTW label Silversaga (Silversaga 2026b; Silversaga 2023a). Many of the patterns now available through Silversaga Patterns were sold RTW during this period. She designed seven collections on a seasonal schedule; autumn/winter (A/W) 2019, 2021, and 2022; and summer/spring (S/S) 2020, 2021,

2022, and 2023. The dresses were reproduced in small batches. Silversaga herself is inconsistent with where; Silversaga (2026b) makes reference to “a skilled atelier in Estonia” while in Silversaga (2023a) she states that all her clothes were “designed and sewn in Sweden”.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, in September 2023, she discontinued sales of RTW garments and became a pattern-only label (Silversaga 2023b).

Simon, Jessica’s fiancé, joined the company in 2024.

Silversaga’s history is split into two primary periods; the slow fashion period (2018–2023) and pattern period (2023–present).

1.1.1 Online presence

Jessica’s online presence dates to the early 2000s. WHOIS records show that the domain `silversaga.se` was registered on December 9, 2004. The earliest Wayback Machine captures for her website, <https://silversaga.se> date to 2006, when it was used as a portfolio website for her photography. Based on snapshots, which the Archive took at seemingly random non-consistent intervals, throughout the 2010s she kept a blog in both English and Swedish on the website.

It became an e-commerce website c. 2020, two years into the launch of Silversaga, and with the start of the pattern period, the `silversaga.se` domain became a redirect to <https://silversagapatterns.com>. The delay is likely due to Silversaga’s early commercial activities having taken place on Etsy.

Silversaga’s online store now uses software from Shopify, a Canadian e-commerce company. The Shopify instances on both `silversaga.se` and `silversagapatterns.com` are the same. As a result, many holotypes from the RTW period, while “taken down” were never truly deleted, and thus, survive to 2026. Though the Internet Archive was unable to fully cover all of `silversaga.se`’s product pages, the images in question are still accessible through Shopify’s CDN, and can be archived. An example of these retrieved holotypes is *Silversaga 2022.58.7180*, featuring *Argenteleonora candiga natalia* (https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/products/SilversagaSS2022_58.jpg?v=1649342524; see Section 2.9.7.1).

Silversaga also formerly had the Instagram account `@silversaga.se`, however, it is now private. It has 248 posts and a message stating that the account has been moved to `@silversagapatterns`. There may be early posts on `@silversaga.se` that do not exist on the current `@silversagapatterns`. This likely contains early Silversaga history inaccessible to us at the time of this monograph.

1.1.2 Patterns

Jessica’s total pattern repertoire is around ~200, as of January 2026 (Silversaga 2026a).

As of April 2026, only 14 of these patterns are available for purchase through Silversaga Patterns. In alphabetical order, they are the Alma (Almidae), Amelie (Argenmelidae), Celeste (Celestidae), Celine (Celinidae), Chloe (Helarchloidae), Clara (Argenclaridae, Section 2.4), Eleonora (Argenteleonoridae, Section 2.9; Heleonoridae, Section 2.14), Ella (Argenkamellidae and Argentellidae), Elsa (Argenelsidae), Emma (Helargemmidae), Francesca (Francescidae), Juliette (Juliettidae, Section 2.5), Mina (Minastolidae), and Ophelia (Ophelidae).

In this monograph, we cover the Clara, Eleonora, and Juliette.

Some patterns have been discontinued; such as the Cora.

In 2025, the five most popular patterns were the Celine, Chloe, Eleonora, Amelie, and Ella.

These patterns are sold entirely as PDFs with English-language instructions. Patterns are available in sizes EU 34–54 (UK 6–26; US 2–24). Many of these patterns date back to the RTW period, while some, such as the Celeste (April 2026), were new when work began on the monograph.

The Eleonora comes in two primary variants, sold as two separate patterns; a sleeved variant, known simply as the Eleonora; and a sleeveless variant, sold as the Sleeveless Eleonora. We will refer to both as the sleeved and sleeveless Eleonora respectively, for clarity; we use the term Eleonora itself to refer to both patterns collectively.

Jessica tests her patterns in one to three rounds, with a total of anywhere from 40 to 70 testers, ranging from EU sizes 34 to 54 (Silversaga 2026c). Based on these figures, we estimate at least 600–1,050 extant species across the 15 families. For comparison, the LCT-01 had ~300 species across ~70 genera as of the last count conducted in February.

Silversaga’s aesthetic is variously described as “romantic minimalism” (Rainey 2025), “timeless”, and as having “soft romantic silhouettes” (“Friends of TFS - Jessica Silversaga” 2025). Silversaga herself frequently uses the adjective “romantic” on many of her product pages; and the title of the root page of the Silversaga Patterns website reads “Clothes Poetry”, with a white dove emoji.

1.1.2.1 Difficulty

Silversaga uses two different scales, 1-4 and 1-5 to rank the difficulty of her patterns. 1 is easy, while 4 or 5 is difficult.

These are denoted by circles on the title page of each pattern, with a name given to each difficulty in italic text below.

1.1.2.2 Table

We present a table of Silversaga's patterns in Table 1.

Table 1: A table of Silversaga's 15 patterns, with the most pertinent information.

Pattern	Difficulty	Release date	Sizes	Cups	LCT-01 taxa	Species count
Alma	1		EU34-54			
Amelie	2		EU34-54			
Celeste	2	2026-04-01	EU34-54		Celestidae	
Celine	2		EU34-54			
Chloe	1		EU34-54			
Clara	1	2021-04 (RTW); 2023-08-25 (pattern)	EU34-50		Argenclaridae (Sec- tion 2.4)	
Eleonora, sleeved	3		EU34-54		Argenteleonoridae (Sec- tion 2.9)	
Eleonora, sleeveless	3		EU34-50		Heleonoridae (Sec- tion 2.14)	
Ella	3	2025-12-09 (update); 2023 (RTW)	EU34-54			
Elsa	2		EU32-54			
Emma	2		EU34-50			
Francesca	2		EU34-54			
Juliette	3	2023-12-02	EU34-50		Juliettidae (Sec- tion 2.5)	
Mina	?	2023-03-01	EU34-48			
Ophelia	2		EU34-50			

1.1.3 Terminology

We will be referring to Jessica Silversaga by her first name throughout the monograph, to better distinguish her from her company, Silversaga Patterns. She also has the person abbreviation *J.Silversaga* (see Section 1.3).

1.2 Biographies

In this section, we include brief biographies of the persons whose garments we cover in the monograph.

For person abbreviations, see Section 1.3, which will contain Instagram links or otherwise short blurbs when they do not warrant a full section.

Most of them are Silversaga's pattern testers. Pattern testers' names were inferred by reading filenames and browsing Instagram, as elaborated on in Section 1.6.

1.2.1 Annette

Annette Nicoletti (Instagram: @annette.sews) is an American sewist from the greater Boston area. As stated on her Instagram profile, she is 170.18 cm (5 ft 7 in) tall. Bust 78.74 cm (31 in), waist 69.85 cm (27.5 in), hip 91.44 cm (36 in).

Wearer of: 2 spp.; Genus *Heleonora*: *truannettae* (Section 2.14.7.1), *monokhromos* (Section 2.14.7.2)

1.2.2 Bethany Lynne

Bethany Lynne Routamaa (<https://www.bethanylynemakes.com/about/>; Instagram: @bethanylynne_makes) is an American sewist from east Texas. She learned sewing and knitting from her mother and grandmother. Though her earliest interests were in painting, she has since diversified to other creative pursuits such as knitting, crocheting, graphic design, quilting, and most taxonomically relevant, sewing. Her earliest me-made garments date back to 2021.

Bethany has now designed her own patterns; such as the Agnes sweater, Homebody apron, and numerous backpacks, sling bags, and tote bags.

During the early pattern period, Bethany won a copy of five patterns from Silversaga (the entire published collection at the time), which led to the start of her interest in Silversaga. Bethany typically makes garments in EU size 36 (Bethany.L. 2025b).

Her last name, Routamaa, is attested in pattern tester filenames.

Wearer of: *Ac. bethanae* (Section 2.4.1.4), *Ae. bethanae* (Section 2.9.6.1)

1.2.3 Madeleine Salisbury

Madeleine Claire Salisbury (Instagram: @made_by_madeleine.claire) is an American sewist, originally from New York, now living in Prague, Czech Republic. Salisbury herself was discovered as part of yet-to-be-published taxonomic work on other patterns; specifically the Traveller coat by Bella Loves Patterns.

As stated on the description of an Ella dress make (no taxonomic classification yet), as of 2026-04-14, Salisbury had a bust of 91.44 in (36 in), waist of 68.58 cm (27 in), and 101.6 cm (40 in) (Salisbury 2026a).

Salisbury is one of Jessica's pattern testers; she has tested the Eleonora (Salisbury 2026b; Salisbury 2024a), the Juliette (Salisbury 2024b)

Wearer of: 2 spp. *Ae. madeleinae* (Section 2.9.2.2), *Ae. madeleinatra* (Section 2.9.2.3)

1.2.4 Laural Stapleton

Laural Stapleton (<https://www.themakerhaus.com/>; Instagram: @themakerhaus) is an American sewist and the operator of The Maker Haus, a small pattern label with two patterns, the Edie and the Nadine.

She is one of Silversaga's pattern testers.

In the filenames, we consistently observed the spelling *Laural* for *Laural Stapleton*. *Laural* is not a typo; Stapleton herself uses the spelling *Laural*, ruling out the possibility of a typo on Silversaga's end.

Regardless, we have chosen to abbreviate her by her last name, *Stapleton*, as this is less likely to cause confusion as to the spelling of her first name.

Wearer of: *H. lauralia* (Section 2.14.4.2)

1.3 Person abbreviations

We define the following new person abbreviations.

- **Alexis.Wr** — Alexis Wright (Instagram: @mysweet sunshine)
- **Anja.S.** — Anja Scheithauer (Instagram: @pure andsew)
- **Annette.N.** — Annette Nicoletti (Instagram: @annette.sews). United States: Massachusetts, Greater Boston Area.
- **Aria.W.S.** — Aria Wright-Shriver (Instagram: @sewariasew)
- **Ashley.G.** — Ashley General (Instagram: @ashleygeneralhandmade)
- **Beatrice.F.** — Beatrice Fletcher (Instagram: @bea.in.the.making)
- **Bethany.L.** — Bethany Lynne (see Section 1.2.2)

- **E.Grace.J.** — E. Grace Jones (Instagram: [@wzrdreams](#)). United States: [New York or New Jersey]. As of 2026-04-16, 177.8 cm (5 ft 10 in) tall; bust 119.38 cm (47 in) (E. Jones 2023).
- **Eliz.B.** — Elizabeth Baumgart (Instagram: [@thatsewliz](#); also known as Elizabeth Hung). Australia: New South Wales, Sydney. Photographer (Instagram: [@elizabethhung](#)).
- **Elizabeth.M.** — Elizabeth McNally (Instagram: [@seamrippinlizzy](#))
- **Fena.T.** — Fena Tandriarto (Instagram: [@fenamakes](#))
- **Gabrielle.Sc.** — Gabrielle Scollay (Instagram: [@sustainably.gabrielle](#))
- **Garofalo** — Martina Garofalo (Instagram: [@margarlab](#)). Bust 83 cm; waist 66 cm; hip 104 cm (provided on Instagram page). Italy.
- **Hunter-Moon** — Katie Hunter-Moon (Instagram: [@katiehuntermoon](#)). United Kingdom: Wales.
- **Ioana.M.** — Ioana Miron (Instagram: [@sewing_in_my_genes](#)). Bust 86 cm; waist 71 cm; hip 96 cm (provided on Instagram page). 177 cm tall. Canada: Ontario, Toronto.
- **J.Silversaga** — Jessica Silversaga (see Section 1.1)
- **Jessa.J.** — Jessa Jones (Instagram: [@jessamjones](#))
- **Juliana.R.** — Juliana Rucker (Instagram: [@sew.juliana](#)); bust 88.9 cm (35 in); waist 71.1 cm (28 in); hips 96.5 cm (38 in); 162.5 cm (5 ft 4 in) tall (provided on Instagram page).
- **Karen.V.H.** — Karen Van Hoof (Instagram: [@the_fabric_attic](#))
- **Lacy.W.** — Lacy Wilhoit (Instagram: [@beauandc_lover](#))
- **Laura.Dem.** — Laura Demelin (Instagram: [@laura.demelin](#); private account). France.
- **Mackenzie.M.** — Mackenzie Morgan (W/2026 H2)
- **Mai** — Mai Vang
- **Malin.S.** — Malin Stara (Instagram: [@angelinlace](#)). Sweden.
- **Manuela.W.** — Manuela Wilkes (Instagram: [@the.sew.addict](#)); bust 34 in (86.3 cm), waist 27 in (68.5 cm), hips 36 in (91.4 cm), 1.60m tall (provided on Instagram page; height from Wilkes (2023)).
- **Megan.B.** — Megan Bynum (Instagram: [@dinigoos_eandbird](#))
- **Mel.T.** — Mel Tesch (Instagram: [@melt.stitches](#)); bust 81 cm; waist 65 cm; hip 90 cm (provided on Instagram page). Australia: Queensland, Brisbane.
- **Piola** — Piola (Instagram: [@piola.makes](#))
- **Rimfors** — Tuss Rimfors (Instagram: [@tussrimfors](#))
- **Samantha.N.** — Samantha Newbery (Instagram: [@frenchseamsam](#); [@snews](#)). Private accounts.
- **Stapleton** — Laural Stapleton (first name not a typo; Instagram: [@themakerhaus](#); see Section 1.2.4).
- **Stephanie.G.** — Stephanie Garcia (Instagram: [@stef.it.seams](#))
- **Suna.M.** — Suna Mantori (Instagram: [@threadbitcbrighton](#)); bust 89 cm; waist 75 cm; hip 97 cm (provided on Instagram page). United Kingdom: England, East Sussex, Brighton.
- **Tea.S.** — Tea Stamenkovic (LejdiTea; Instagram: [@lejdittea](#))
- **Theresa.N.** — Theresa Neef (Instagram: [@notesonmatter](#)). United States: Louisiana, New Orleans.

1.4 Taxonomic remarks

Silversaga was historically a slow fashion RTW label, as explained in Section 1.1. After the COVID-19 pandemic led to the label transitioning to patterns, the first home-sewn Silversaga garments arose.

The hybrid RTW–home-sewn nature of the taxonomic record of Silversaga garments leads to a taxonomically interesting situation for the LCT-01.

In the simplest of cases, RTW taxonomy typically maps the design, colorway, and wearer to the genus, species, and subspecies respectively; while sewing patterns map the design, option (or view), and individual sewist to the family, genus, and species (Lemuria 2026b).

The most reliable morphological character identifying Silversaga garment taxa of RTW origin is the presence of a label reading “Silversaga”; see Section 1.4.3.

1.4.1 Species counts

In this section, we describe Fermi estimates for the possible count of genera and species encompassing Silversaga’s patterns.

Pattern testers alone likely contribute some 600–1,050 species to the Silversaga repertoire.

1.4.2 Polyphyletic patterns

As with Nina Lee’s Kew dress, extensively taxonomized in prior monographs published in the *Journal*, some of these patterns are classified polyphyletically, due to the dispersion of their morphological diversity across the higher-level taxa of the LCT-01.

In this case, the two patterns classified polyphyletically are the Eleonora and Ella. The sleeved Eleonora falls under the family Argenteleonoridae (Section 2.9), while the sleeveless Eleonora falls under the family Heleonoridae (Section 2.14).

1.4.3 The physical Silversaga label

Invariably, all Silversaga garments from the RTW period worn by third parties feature a label. The label is white, with the word “Silversaga” set in all-caps, with spaced letters, and is positioned on the superiormost medial point of the garment’s dorsal interior surface.

The presence of the label is considered a reliable indicator of the garment’s origin from Jessica herself, and by extension, possible origin from the RTW period. Whether Jessica attaches these labels to her own garments for daily wear or otherwise personal possession is unknown. As such, it may be used to reliably date a garment in a third party’s possession from 2018–2022, and any garment in Jessica’s possession from the early 2000s onward,

1.4.4 Varieties and forms

The LCT-01 makes significant use of infrageneric and sub-specific taxa, especially in these monographs. We use the subgenus, section, and series, variety, and form in their botanical sense. RTW instances of Silversaga taxa use subspecies. We use the zoological convention for subspecies; unlike botany, we do not use the *subsp.* or *ssp.* particule.

The variety corresponds to individual, often irreversible small variations in the dress, such as fabric modification (e.g. *Argenteleonora bethanae*, Section 2.9.6.1; var. *athea* and var. *brunalana*), trimming, or alterations.

The form corresponds to the positioning of the dress on the human body or the status of easily reversible configurations (e.g. button fastening, tied or untied ribbons, or sleeves pulled downward, lateral to the upper arm).

The LCT-01 makes use of the “blessed form” doctrine; for example, a dress such as the Clara can be worn on or off-shoulder. If it were worn off-shoulder, it would be considered part of the class Umerostentida, subclass Alourida; while if it were worn on-shoulder, it would fall in the class Isotrapezia.

Designer intent is that the sleeves are worn on the shoulder, though the product page explicitly acknowledges the off-shoulder configuration (and notes that it is breastfeeding-friendly). As the on-shoulder form is most common, the Argenclaridae are placed within the class Isotrapezia.

1.4.5 Taxonomic history

Our lead author discovered Silversaga through the American sewist Madeleine Salisbury (Instagram: [@made_by_madeleine.claire](https://www.instagram.com/made_by_madeleine.claire)).

During the early taxonomization of Jessica’s patterns, the LCT-01 began using infrageneric taxa; ranks below genus

but above species, such as subgenera and sections, due to the increasing awkwardness of incorporating an increasing amount of characters in the genus name itself.

Originally, we intended for this paper to only cover the Eleonora dress (Argenteleonoridae) and its sleeveless variant (Heleonoridae); but later decided to expand to the other garments within Silversaga’s repertoire.

We later narrowed the scope to focus on breadth rather than depth; in this monograph, we describe a small representative sample of anywhere from 5–20 species from each family, or the entirety of Silversaga’s pattern testing gallery; as our team consists solely of one author, who wanted to prevent potential burnout.

In early May 2026, the author conducted a revision of the Helistola tree, intended to replace its current division into four orders, one for each distinct designer. The analysis, which the author hopes to publish in a separate paper, used a mixture of most parsimonious and most likely tree inferences.

We also further narrowed the scope slightly to accommodate a publication date within May, due to the regrettable time constraints on our author’s part.

1.4.6 Genera abbreviations

We use the following abbreviations for the genera we describe:

- *Ac.* — *Argenclara*
- *Ae.* — *Argenteleonora*
- *H.* — *Heleonora*
- *J.* — *Julietta*
- *T.* — *Trunclara*
- *Ta.* — *Tanaflora*

1.5 Liberty

Liberty (<https://libertylondon.com>) is a British department store on Great Marlborough Street in the West End of London. Liberty sells fashion products and homewares, and most relevant to the monograph, fabrics. One of its collections, the Tana Lawn cotton, represents one of the largest fabric taxa in the fabric taxonomy of the LCT-01, still undeveloped. Some relevant species are described in Section 3.1.

Liberty’s website uses the Ampliance content management system (<https://ampliance.com>), as written in a case study (*Liberty Case Study 2022*), and as inferred from the host `i8.ampliance.net` being used to load images.

`ampliance.net` does not block retrievals using Wget or cURL, however, it blocks the Wayback Machine for unknown reasons. The Wayback Machine returns the error

Figure 1: Entrance of the Liberty department store in London (Hisgett 2010). United Kingdom: England, London, Regent Street, around intersections of Maddox and Noel Street. 51° 30' 49.76" N, 0° 08' 26.28" W (image coordinates).

“Save Page Now could not capture this URL because it was unreachable. If the site is online, it may be blocking access from our service.”. The LCT-01’s standard citation practice of providing a SHA2-256 hash and linking both to the original and to the IA is infeasible as a result of this issue.

Amplience provides date information for images through the `x-amp-published` header; retrieving <https://i8.amplience.net/i/liberty/000544799-R124365006-1> using `curl` with the `--head` option returns the header `x-amp-published: Wed, 05 May 2021 14:46:01 GMT`. However, this date information conflicts with the `DateOriginal` field in the aforementioned image, which claims an original date of 2017-01-24 12:01:26.

Backup copies of holotype images are available on the lead author’s servers. Contact the corresponding author to make a request if the original URL is no longer functional.

1.6 Materials and methods

1.6.1 Equipment and software

The author conducted his research on a computer running Ubuntu 24.04, with the XFCE desktop environment. He used the SHA2-256 algorithms to compute the cryptographic hashes of the photographic specimens he exam-

ined for species descriptions. He used Firefox 139.0.4. His monitor is a 55.8 cm (22 in) wide, 30.48 cm (12 in) tall, 63.5 cm (25 in) diagonal monitor, the NVISION S2515-B 25” IPS with a 100Hz refresh rate. He is not colorblind. He is near sighted and wears glasses.

See Figure 3 for `sha256sum`, `ffmpeg`, and `openssl` hashes.

1.6.2 Specimen locations

Specimens were collected from Silversaga Patterns’ website (<https://silversagapatterns.com>); with a focus on the pattern tester galleries. The Silversaga Patterns website uses Shopify as its underlying platform and image storage; EXIF metadata removal is likely consistent with internal Shopify server-side upload processing code.

The Silversaga Patterns account features numerous Instagram stories where Jessica has compiled large numbers of other makes; this represents the largest, albeit second highest-quality source.

This source is considered lower-quality than the Silversaga Patterns website; as explained in Lemuria (2026a), Meta’s CDN is hostile to reproducibility. Though URLs can be captured by the Internet Archive immediately after generation, the URLs are invariably long, taking up more space in monograph documents.

Silversaga typically names these story groups with the name of the featured pattern followed by a number. However, she has reused multiple pattern-number combinations; there exists two story groups named Clara 8.

Furthermore, Imginn’s interface prevents direct linkage of each individual story to a citable Instagram URL. Thus, we instead used the handles visible within the stories to locate the original Instagram posts containing the species.

1.6.3 Images

As our lead author had no Instagram account at the start of the monograph, he used Imginn, an online service that allows Instagram to be viewed without an account. He eventually created an Instagram account at [@lemuriaph](https://www.instagram.com/lemuriaph) on April 16, 2026, to access numerous public accounts that were unavailable through Imginn.

Images were hashed with the SHA2-256 algorithms, using the `sha256sum` utility on his system. The versions of the `sha256sum` and `openssl` utilities on his system at the time of the paper are given in Figure 3.

The images were of exceptionally high quality; resolutions as high as 4000×2667 were collected. The majority of the images were in JPG format; some images were stored in the HEIC format.

To check EXIF metadata, ExifTool version 12.76 was used. YouTube videos were retrieved using yt-dlp version 2026.03.13.083652; git commit hash 496c0e4319db4359aebd8d3270b681c890cafa28.

We inferred the approximate dates of some pattern releases, with maximum confidence in the year and month, with absolutely none on the day, by retrieving sitemaps from the Silversaga website, which we include in supplementary data.

1.6.4 Annotations

We also provide annotations of certain holotype images to explain their construction and terms we have coined for reference to specific parts of the dress. We note that these terms will almost certainly differ from sewing terms or the terms used by Jessica in the patterns themselves. For copyright purposes, we only provide these annotations standalone; we include a URL for the original image to allow the user to retrieve and stitch the final annotation themselves.

A mostly abridged guide for viewing these annotations with the original images is as follows:

1. Download the annotation SVG file.
2. Open the SVG file and find a URL in the top right corner. Download that URL and save the image to the same folder as the SVG file.
3. Close and reopen the SVG file to see the final form of the annotation with the image in the background.

As an example, we provide an annotation for *Argenclara baumgartia* in Figure 2.

1.6.5 YML and TTL files

In the supplementary data, we include both YML and TTL files. The YML files are already a well-established data format; while the TTL files (which represent triples in Turtle format), are part of the new experimental LCT-01 Holotype Standard (LHS), a new RDF-based ontology for representing LCT-01 data; not just holotypes, but species, and perhaps patterns too. We make no guarantee of the usability of the TTL files, or to possible ontological changes.

Figure 2: A small preview of the raw diagram of *Argenclara baumgartia* (Section 2.4.1.3). For copyright reasons as stated in the body, the reader should overlay the SVG diagram over the original image on their own computer using the instructions provided. The original image can be obtained from the original source; it is not distributed with this monograph or its supplementary data.

```

$ sha256sum --version
sha256sum (GNU coreutils) 9.4
Copyright (C) 2023 Free Software Foundation, Inc.
License GPLv3+: GNU GPL version 3 or later <https://gnu.org/licenses/gpl.html>.
This is free software: you are free to change and redistribute it.
There is NO WARRANTY, to the extent permitted by law.

Written by Ulrich Drepper, Scott Miller, and David Madore.
$ openssl --version
OpenSSL 3.5.0 8 Apr 2025 (Library: OpenSSL 3.5.0 8 Apr 2025)
$ sha256sum /usr/bin/sha256sum /usr/bin/openssl
f293048f656688883ee919eb3f4b12926aaa13362de0eb6e3b5716b915b18b35 /usr/bin/sha256sum
724acbe911513d13f52bae0b8969b20336cd8618fc67898a6bf7847bf1a270ad /usr/bin/openssl
    A hash of the sha256sum and openssl utilities on the lead author's computer.
$ ffmpeg -version
ffmpeg version 6.1.1-3ubuntu5 Copyright (c) 2000-2023 the FFmpeg developers
built with gcc 13 (Ubuntu 13.2.0-23ubuntu3)
configuration: --prefix=/usr --extra-version=3ubuntu5 --toolchain=hardened
--libdir=/usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu --incdir=/usr/include/x86_64-linux-gnu
--arch=amd64 --enable-gpl --disable-stripping --disable-omx --enable-gnutls
--enable-libaom --enable-libass --enable-libbs2b --enable-libcaca
--enable-libcdio --enable-libcodec2 --enable-libdav1d --enable-libflite
--enable-libfontconfig --enable-libfreetype --enable-libfribidi
--enable-libglslang --enable-libgme --enable-libgsm --enable-libharfbuzz
--enable-libmp3lame --enable-libmysofa --enable-libopenjpeg
--enable-libopenmpt --enable-libopus --enable-librubberband
--enable-libshine --enable-libsnappy --enable-libsoxr --enable-libspeex
--enable-libtheora --enable-libtwolame --enable-libvidstab
--enable-libvorbis --enable-libvpx --enable-libwebp --enable-libx265
--enable-libxml2 --enable-libxvid --enable-libzimg --enable-openal
--enable-opencl --enable-opengl --disable-sndio --enable-libvpl
--disable-libmfx --enable-libdc1394 --enable-libdrm --enable-libiec61883
--enable-chromaprint --enable-frei0r --enable-ladspa --enable-libbluray
--enable-libjack --enable-libpulse --enable-librabbitmq --enable-librist
--enable-libsrt --enable-libssh --enable-libsvtav1 --enable-libx264
--enable-libzmq --enable-libzvbi --enable-lv2 --enable-sdl2
--enable-libplacebo --enable-librav1e --enable-pocketsphinx
--enable-librsvg --enable-libjxl --enable-shared
libavutil      58. 29.100 / 58. 29.100
libavcodec     60. 31.102 / 60. 31.102
libavformat    60. 16.100 / 60. 16.100
libavdevice    60.  3.100 / 60.  3.100
libavfilter     9. 12.100 /  9. 12.100
libswscale     7.  5.100 /  7.  5.100
libswresample  4. 12.100 /  4. 12.100
libpostproc   57.  3.100 / 57.  3.100

$ sha256sum $(which ffmpeg)
ed16af623947494a72e284b6eb8ff225f2da22b38b5d5069c2fd4b4ba3384e41 /usr/bin/ffmpeg

```

Figure 3: ffmpeg version and hash on the lead author's computer.

1.7 Trees

We provide several overview trees of the Silversaga taxa.

Figure 4: Overview

Figure 5: Argenteleonoridae

Figure 6: Argenclaridae

2 Descriptions

2.1 Phylum Manubristenta

Manubristenta Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the kingdom Abtruncusa.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, Manubristenta is characterized by the exposure of the skin superficial to the manubrium, the superior (upper) part of the sternum (breastbone), and covered shoulders.

2.2 Class Isotrapezia

Isotrapezia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the phylum Manubristenta.

Diagnosis: Isotrapezia is characterized by a neckline with a shape resembling an isosceles trapezoid (or trapezium); where the neckline is wider superiorly and narrows inferiorly.

Figure 7: An illustration of an isosceles trapezoid (Alexandrov 2007), an idealized geometry of Isotrapezia.

2.3 Order Isargenta

Isargenta Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the class Isotrapezia.

Identification key

- 01 Ventral medial button row: present (02), absent (03)
- 02 See family Juliettidae (Section 2.5). End.
- 03 Number of elastic channels: one (04), two (05)
- 04 See family Almidiae (unpublished). End.
- 05 See family Argenclaridae (Section 2.4). End.

2.4 Family Argenclaridae

Argenclaridae Lemuria, 2026; familia nova

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the order Isargenta.

Diagnosis: Argenclaridae is characterized by an adjustable neckline with elastic channel allowing off/on-shoulder configuration; two elastic channels, one within the inframammary region inferior to the bust (superior elastic channel), and one at the hips, acting as the bodice-skirt seam. The neckline is asymmetric in height across the two sides of the coronal plane.

Its sleeves are gathered at the proximal end and directly connected to the bodice, voluminous across the upper arm, with a cuff-like¹ gather at the elbow, before flaring out and terminating at the medial point between the elbow and wrist.

Its skirt terminates inferior to the knee and features bilateral pockets within the lateral seams.

Phylogenetically, Argenclaridae is characterized by origin from the Clara sewing pattern by Silversaga.

Remarks: The Clara originated during the RTW period. It was her best-selling design during the summer/spring 2021 and summer/spring 2022 collections. Preorders began in April 2021.

Silversaga recruited pattern testers for the Clara from August 3 to 7, 2023. She received ~160 applications, an unknown number of which were accepted. On August 25, 2023, the Clara was released.

Design. Silversaga cites Victorian chemise dresses as the inspiration for the Clara.

Identification key

- 01 Garment has skirt (is dress)? Yes (02), no (03)
- 02 See genus *Argenclara* (Section 2.4.1). End.
- 03 See genus *Trunclara* (Section 2.4.4). End.

Etymology: *Argen-*, Silversaga taxa prefix + *Clara* + *-idae*, family suffix.

Type genus: *Argenclara*

2.4.1 Genus *Argenclara*

Argenclara Lemuria, 2026; gen. nov.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the family Argenclaridae.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara* is the *sensu stricto* genus of the Clara dress. The *Argenclara* are characterized by minimal divergence from the Clara pattern.

¹Cuffs are typically located at the distal end of the sleeve, hence the term “cuff-like” used here.

Identification key

- 01** Fabric between elastic channels? Lace (02), solid fabric (03).
02 See *Argenclara* subg. *Lacashira* (Section 2.4.3). End.
03 Sewn by Katie Hunter-Moon? Yes (04), no (05).
04 See *Argenclara* subg. *Venaluna* (Section 2.4.2). End.
05 Directly under *Argenclara*. End.

Etymology: *Argen-*, Silversaga taxa prefix + *Clara*.

Type species: *Argenclara baumgartia*

Forms: Two forms apply to *Argenclara* spp.: *f. umeros-tenta* (off-shoulder) and *f. isotrapezia* (on-shoulder). *f. isotrapezia* is designated as the blessed form for *Argenclara*.

Distribution: Worldwide, via paid PDF pattern. Significant primary material on the Instagram tag ClaraDressPattern.

2.4.1.1 *Argenclara alexae*

Argenclara alexae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara alexae* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton called “folk” from Merchant and Mills; with a white background and overlapping blue lines in a gingham check-like pattern.

Remarks: See also Alex.B. (2023) for Alex’s instagram post.

The Royal Mail wall-embedded mailbox on the subject’s left proves that the images were taken in the United Kingdom.

Etymology: From *Alex* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. All images were taken outdoors on a sidewalk in daylight conditions, with a red Royal Mail wall-embedded mailbox near the subject. Subject standing underneath vegetation, unknown species in *Fuchsia* Plum. ex L.

Holotype: *Alex 40.6700AA* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject on sidewalk. Arms fully adducted. *Argenclara alexae* wb. Alex.B., 2023. © Alex Begin or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 75e5aeb22ebb1171a6ca28187e26466af48e21d69f611ef781d5e3bf92d8211; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alex_Begin2.jpg?v=1692902847; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414044848/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alex_Begin2.jpg?v=1692902847

Alex 40.6735AA — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject on sidewalk. Arms behind torso, resem-

bling “at ease” position. *Argenclara alexae* wb. Alex.B., 2023. © Alex Begin or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 494d1719bad12d3c7a47bfa3c9ab93e95c5c3a38c36fb42d38c6f76b7ae37a40; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alex_Begin3.jpg?v=1692902839; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414044827/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alex_Begin3.jpg?v=1692902839

Alex 40.6746AA — Photograph. 3024×4032. Angled ventral view. Closer shot compared to first two images. Subject’s arms fully adducted. *Argenclara alexae* wb. Alex.B., 2023. © Alex Begin or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** ae7e1b8fb9964ffdee8a880c9c11589f33bf1c94bcbd000787ec00ac445779d7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alex_Begin.jpg?v=1692902867; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161535/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alex_Begin.jpg?v=1692902867

2.4.1.2 *Argenclara alexisae*

Argenclara alexisae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara alexisae* is characterized by its solid forest green linen fabric.

Remarks: Alexis sewed the dress in a size 38 (88 cm bust), with 3.2 m (3.5 yd; 10.5 ft) of fabric (Wright 2023a).

Etymology: From *Alexis* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Wright 17.4019* — Photograph. 2668×4000. Ventral view. Outdoor lighting, shallow depth of field. Subject looking to right. Hair positioned ventrally, obstructing neckline bilaterally. Medial portion remains visible. Subject’s arms fully adducted. *Argenclara alexisae* wb. Alexis.Wr., 2023. © Alexis Wright or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** f8fb0cbde9ff4dde8b1949f6dd9c0b68870fd3f5f7cca8ce07a1e10fd048b916; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis-Wright.jpg?v=1692900295>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260413155859/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis-Wright.jpg?v=1692900295>

Wright 17.4033 — Photograph. 3335×5000. Right lateral view. Outdoor lighting, shallow depth of field. Hair positioned both ventrally and dorsally. *Argenclara alexisae* wb. Alexis.Wr., 2023. © Alexis Wright or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 29a9ab040a78a6d44c66d7989e9e5aac04b98ddb62948fd672c0ed1fe110f494; **Original:**

<https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis-Wright4.jpg?v=1692900307>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161549/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis-Wright4.jpg?v=1692900307>

Wright 17.4076 — Photograph. 3335×5000. Ventral view. Outdoor lighting, shallow depth of field. Subject looking to right. Hair positioned ventrally, obstructing neckline bilaterally. Medial portion remains visible. Subject's left arm on lateral surface of waist channels. Right arm adducted. *Argenclara alexisae* wb. Alexis.Wr., 2023. © Alexis Wright or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** b7144f02712087587be248f698f232b1809c10f148895e8a2c5b152e5c314823; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis-Wright3.jpg?v=1692900316>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260413155930/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis-Wright3.jpg?v=1692900316>

2.4.1.3 *Argenclara baumgartia*

Argenclara baumgartia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara baumgartia* is characterized by its fabric, with dark blue–black and red floral patterns distributed sparsely across an off-white background.

Remarks: Baumgart sewed the dress in size 36 (system unspecified in original post), though she reduced the circumference of the waist channels to 83.82 cm (33 in) (Baumgart 2023a).

Etymology: *Baumgart* + *-ia*. Name inferred from pattern tester filenames.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Baumgart 95.6714** — Photograph. 2888×3845. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally, obscuring neckline edges bilaterally. Arms fully adducted. Indoor lighting, slightly brighter at subject's right. Subject standing against white background on brown floor. Subject's right foot forward. *Argenclara baumgartia* wb. Eliz.B., unknown. © Elizabeth Baumgart or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 5d05d2e61cd68f822183f12b64e96e245def9f728f63340ac880ae47f84f76ee; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_Baumgart7.jpg?v=1692899766; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413155714/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_Baumgart7.jpg?v=1692899766

Baumgart 95.6811 — Photograph. 3024×4032. EXIF meta-

data stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally. Neckline edges lateral to hair. Arms fully adducted; subject's right foot extended outward, laterally. Indoor lighting, possible light source from left based on shadows. Subject standing against gray background on white tiled floor. *Argenclara baumgartia* wb. Eliz.B., unknown. © Elizabeth Baumgart or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 6b12e5ea7abf8290dcfee8365b121b0dbddfa907da7ee939e80633faa0de176e; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_Baumgart6.jpg?v=1692899786; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413155726/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_Baumgart6.jpg?v=1692899786

Baumgart 95.7035 — Photograph. 2235×2984. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Truncated ventral view. Head out of frame. Subject's hair positioned ventrally, obscuring neckline edges bilaterally. Left arm adducted; right arm on distal gather of sleeve. Indoor lighting from subject's left; light manifests in pattern of bars, likely consistent with window with bars. *Argenclara baumgartia* wb. Eliz.B., unknown. © Elizabeth Baumgart or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** b1a5b429f1d209595c3c1f7d6c912fff43284b9262a4f26ade99a37ed11fb957; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_Baumgart4.jpg?v=1692899737; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413155709/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_Baumgart4.jpg?v=1692899737

2.4.1.4 *Argenclara bethanae*

Argenclara bethanae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara bethanae* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton lawn with a black background and large flowers. The flowers feature six petals, a yellow core, and a green leaf.

Remarks: See also (Bethany.L. 2025b, Clara Dress) for Bethany's blog post, and Bethany.L. (2024b) for Bethany's Instagram post regarding the dress.

Etymology: From

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Bethany 126.4429** — Photograph. 1200×1600. Ventral view. Indoors. Skirt extended outward to the left. Arms fully adducted. Hair positioned dorsally, with slight drape ventrally. Neckline not obscured. *Argenclara bethanae* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-**

256: 51e9246e21e8fa3efb30d04cc5db51847709a620119a9a5bc0baf956ab55daff; **Original:** <https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/clara-dress-front-2.jpg>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260417183436/https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/clara-dress-front-2.jpg>

Bethany 126.4510 — Photograph. 1200×1600. Dorsal view. Indoors. Hair tied dorsally. Arm extended slightly outward to left. Right arm possibly in front. *Argenclara bethanae* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** fe1f9ea9f7c2964811e5ba71fb73ebbe1fb9320a2f1ce101beb99e9a74b4b25f; **Original:** <https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/clara-dress-back.jpg>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260417183433/https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/clara-dress-back.jpg>

Bethany 126.4700 — Photograph. 1200×1601. Ventral view. Indoors. Hair tied dorsally. Subject's left arm adducted. Subject's right arm adducted as if reaching for blinds of window. *Argenclara bethanae* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 6b44e0d23753615633eac1493373899b66456424cd96125f72fc01b3dc5c1a98; **Original:** <https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/clara-dress-front.jpg>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260417183432/https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/clara-dress-front.jpg>

2.4.1.5 *Argenclara caitlinae*

Argenclara caitlinae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara caitlinae* is characterized by its fabric, a navy linen from B&M Fabrics, that is likely black or navy blue; unknown due to lighting conditions.

Remarks: See also Caitlin.D. (2023) for Caitlin's Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Caitlin* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Caitlin 40.1873AC** — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject looking slightly downward. Hair positioned ventrally, terminating just short of neckline edges. Subject interacting with distal edge of left sleeve using right hand. Outdoor conditions. Sun behind photographer as inferred from shadows. *Argenclara caitlinae* wb. Caitlin.D., 2023. © Caitlin.D. or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Photograph locality:** United Kingdom: England, West Yorkshire, Leeds. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-**

256: e11ef025717f86be06b983ced9cd3973cb6a754d5d10b8b421a98310118a3d71; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/CaitlinDPatternTest-09.jpg?v=1692902128>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260414040234/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/CaitlinDPatternTest-09.jpg?v=1692902128>

Caitlin 40.1877AC — Photograph. 3024×4032. Dorsal view. Subject looking back at camera. Hair positioned dorsally. Subject's arms fully adducted. Outdoor conditions. Sun behind photographer as inferred from shadows. *Argenclara caitlinae* wb. Caitlin.D., 2023. © Caitlin.D. or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 58664cf39631ffec4557d3646358111f645d06833a32468bc2f8444a2a3ddf83; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/CaitlinDPatternTest-16.jpg?v=1692902119>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161543/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/CaitlinDPatternTest-16.jpg?v=1692902119>

Caitlin 40.1879AC — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject looking slightly upward to her right. Hair positioned dorsally, small strands ventrally, slightly obscuring neckline edges. Subject's left arm slightly behind skirt. Right arm adducted. Outdoor conditions. Sun behind photographer as inferred from shadows. *Argenclara caitlinae* wb. Caitlin.D., 2023. © Caitlin.D. or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 96e588d9a11367104b28ca3dc0fab741c394c9305fb1da53442a31c254fac98f; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/CaitlinDPatternTest-11.jpg?v=1692902110>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260414040227/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/CaitlinDPatternTest-11.jpg?v=1692902110>

2.4.1.6 *Argenclara cosmia*

Argenclara cosmia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara cosmia* is characterized by its fabric, a double printed gauze with a brown background and small clusters of black dot and teardrop shapes.

Remarks: See also Tortajada (2023) for Marta's Instagram post.

Synonyms:

- *Argenclara tortajada* Lemuria, 2026. Junior synonym. Based on Marta's last name, inferred from pattern tester filenames. We decided to rename the species epithet to *cosmia* based on Marta's Instagram handle during the compilation of the monograph.

Etymology: From Marta's Instagram handle, *cosmia*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Tortajada 39.8104* — Photograph. 3456×4608. Ventral view, outdoors. Subject looking to her right. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring left neckline area. *Argenclara cosmia* wb. Marta.T., 2023. © Marta Tortajada or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Photograph locality:** Spain: Valencia, Jardins del Real² **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 73acf0e0447ca2e1893b2ee45c301a30d0712a4e43fa379b51a5e7ec5eddaa4e; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Marta_Tortajada9.jpg?v=1692901969; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161538/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Marta_Tortajada9.jpg?v=1692901969

Tortajada 39.8175 — Photograph. 3150×4200. Angled dorsal view, outdoors. Sun possibly in top-left of image, as inferred from significantly higher exposure. Subject looking back towards camera. Hair positioned both ventrally and dorsally. *Argenclara cosmia* wb. Marta.T., 2023. © Marta Tortajada or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Photograph locality:** Same as *Tortajada 39.8104*. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 42ebddb381f033932335097c72611151b57f1d9c17668a99d6ea8621a05ebd2c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Marta_Tortajada7.jpg?v=1692901934; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161546/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Marta_Tortajada7.jpg?v=1692901934

Tortajada 39.8560 — Photograph. 3456×4608. Ventral view, outdoors. Light source, most likely the sun, from subject's right (top left of photograph). Subject facing slightly downward to her right. Hair positioned dorsally with significant drape over left shoulder, partially obscuring neckline. *Nerium oleander* L. in background. *Argenclara cosmia* wb. Marta.T., 2023. © Marta Tortajada or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Photograph locality:** Same as *Tortajada 39.8104*. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** d4fd197e4b33f8243928496e467456a8daf234ed79ba965c844e903f589a8dc7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Marta_Tortajada4.jpg?v=1692901891; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414035806/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Marta_Tortajada4.jpg?v=1692901891

2.4.1.7 *Argenclara evae*

Argenclara evae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

²OpenStreetMap spelling. Instagram post uses the spelling *Jardines del Real / Jardines de Viveros*.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara evae* is characterized by its fabric, a solid blue background with sparsely distributed red flowers; likely roses.

Remarks: See Eva (2024) and Eva (2026a) for Kate Eva's Instagram posts on *Ac. evae*.

Etymology: From *Eva* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken within Eva's sewing room, in indoors conditions. An artificial light is present in the room, often emitting yellowish light. *Eva 2024.51321AE* was taken by Eva using a phone and mirror. The 2026 photographs were taken using a tripod (Eva 2026b).

Holotype: *Eva 2024.51321AE* — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. Indoor lighting; yellow light from overhead lamp. Window to subject's left, slight shadow cast by legs. Subject in mirror, holding phone; phone slightly obscures left shoulder. Hair mostly positioned dorsally, with slight ventral presence on left shoulder. *Argenclara evae* wb. Eva, 2024. © Kate Eva, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Eva (2024); **SHA2-256:** 3dfbce82a5bb8e4fd1cad3b48718d637adef86cda8330db5d5426ddaa7e7a355; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260415164826/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/658439210_18092747069157318_2777814582593702200_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpegr_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=100&ig_cache_key=MzM2ODM5NDA4ODU2MDkyNDUyMg%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDM5ODUyMg%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=MWhqLyrOfNEQ7kNvWvHkG1mD&_nc_oc=AdqWy75IPEYjGMYo1PyMszZWUMG4dZU3ipxM40Bpcl_aWSTt-r0zik9UpmQyv_4rtC8&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&se=-1&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=714neZitmBxwtgr_hgOGKQ&_nc_ss=7a32e&oh=00_Af0dBv7eX7Ku2citXh8S676bFNllmVCTahrh0WFSxENyAQ&oe=69E59276

Eva 2026.520.39442 — Photograph. 1440×1920. Ventral view. Subject's arms extended out. Skirt flaring outward significantly in manner resembling twirl. Legs crossing. *Argenclara evae* wb. Eva, 2026. © Kate Eva, 2026, all rights reserved. **Page:** Eva (2026a); **SHA2-256:** 67896cf2ec98ac0b521346fddf5f29c5f5de39cd3860fcd525d591b5834d076b; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504200743/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/683780806_18581398309024297_5372316129147739442_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=105&ig_cache_key=Mzg4NzU3NTYzMjcXNjUzOTYwOQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDM5ODUyMg%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=1WTNjXNme0EQ7kNvWvHi6sjz&_nc_oc=AdoBCxA7Eh0UNoPWFhsWlnNEYMUO6gO9M_uT-DNY-5dGpCOET5RRBnOhw0eavvz

Wb6A&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=EAEYYrmSwYJpLzy8N2Pk7w&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af50N5RjMjFdfmaajo2Jjf5hZg-PMWY7Gj75q45mGHMLw&oe=69FED344

Eva 2026.520.56290 — Photograph. 1440×1920. Ventral view. Subject's head leaning slightly to right. Arms fully adducted. Slight frame truncation at skirt hem. *Argenclara evae* wb. Eva, 2026. © Kate Eva, 2026, all rights reserved. **Page:** Eva (2026a); **SHA2-256:** 02eaedc0a5f88a339570332a41b7ab81245278a1410dfb31fc5449c02902d494; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504200744/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/687760142_18581398318024297_1958349817387356290_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=Mzg4NzU3NTY0MDQxNzI4NTc3Nw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI4MTkyMC5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=vH3F4uPhFCgQ7kNvWGG5cvw&_nc_oc=AdoLQaThYR3cY5ooeewwD_qJkgCqzhWUJjN29XAYNl3TSsUl8m8o2QsoqcbLh7Nv9l4&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=EAEYYrmSwYJpLzy8N2Pk7w&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af4UigA-6le8rn7sgHZkiQObHR-VQbu7ci4s6udwRHv7fw&oe=69FEC8C1

Eva 2026.520.71156 — Photograph. 1440×1920. Dorsal view. Subject facing right. Arms fully adducted. Shadow from sunlight roughly 270° to subject. *Argenclara evae* wb. Eva, 2026. © Kate Eva, 2026, all rights reserved. **Page:** Eva (2026a); **SHA2-256:** f17b6e90ef15f9feafd384ed3ed2f0d3d79140fe9d7ba266c683f068093d4e4; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504200748/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/671161059_18581398333024297_8958263499940971156_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpeg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=102&ig_cache_key=Mzg4NzU3NTY1NDg4NzY1MTg3NQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI4MTkyMC5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=3vvNpk9U5YoQ7kNvwGKR11k&_nc_oc=AdotaAdXCpwT2h9w_189c5uVODLzki2U-Dv3NcLc0zqrnns20Yz7anle2UYU1h334Gk&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&se=-1&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=EAEYYrmSwYJpLzy8N2Pk7w&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5L1a7tqVOsANWc8SwR8hQuCwAnrDN9n1B9QyMvcSOomQ&oe=69FEE4D8

2.4.1.8 *Argenclara fena*

Argenclara fena Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara fena* is characterized by its fabric, a cyan linen bought secondhand from FabMo, a fabric retailer based in Sunnyvale, California.

Remarks: All images of *Ac. fena* depict Fena wearing the dress off-shoulder. The blessed form for *Argenclara*

has the sleeves worn on-shoulder. As such, *Argenclara fena* is not considered to be within the subclass Alourida Lemuria, 2026; unpublished. Fena sewed the dress in a size 40. See also Fena.T. (2023) for Fena's Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Fena* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix. Pronounced /fe.'nei/, in line with the endonymic pronunciation of "Fena", /'fɛ.nə/ (or as described on her Instagram profile, "like feta".)

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were likely taken outdoors, in a semi-shaded environment. Directional shadows are visible around Fena in all three images to some extent.

Holotype: *Fena 105.6711AF* — Photograph. 2786×3715. Angled ventral view. Subject against wall, arms slightly crossed. Hair positioned dorsally. *Argenclara fena* f. *umst.* wb. Fena.T., 2023. © Fena Tandriarto or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 9c2722262cf0970f1187acf40e72e80c381d0c5a2c03d7e85996a1a574c275ed; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Fena_tandriarto.jpg?v=1692902195; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/2/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Fena_tandriarto.jpg

Fena 105.6734AF — Photograph. 2969×3959. Ventral view. Subject's arms on hair. Hair positioned dorsally. Narrow depth of field; lantern in background blurry. *Argenclara fena* f. *umst.* wb. Fena.T., 2023. © Fena Tandriarto or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** d91d7bdef693f9123f021b1b970fe856f7bd0e88db91966092026ea62bf295c9; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Fena_tandriarto6.jpg?v=1692902220; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161539/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Fena_tandriarto6.jpg?v=1692902220

Fena 105.6737AF — Photograph. 2937×3915. Angled ventral view. Subject's left foot forward. Arms mostly adducted. Hair positioned ventrally. *Argenclara fena* f. *umst.* wb. Fena.T., 2023. © Fena Tandriarto or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 052b2c2ca848a660f9279638d9141d675f1c0f834b504a07bdcfe87b8828b49d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Fena_tandriarto3.jpg?v=1692902283; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161525/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Fena_tandriarto3.jpg?v=1692902283

2.4.1.9 *Argenclara gratia*

Argenclara gratia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara gratia* is characterized by its fabric, a solid light sky blue rayon–linen blend.

Remarks: We infer the location of the photographs as either the state of New York or New Jersey, based on the One World Trade Center in the far background of the image, located by looking at the wearer’s right shoulder from her perspective, then looking left, and viewing the faint skyline.

See also Grace’s Instagram post at E. Jones (2023).

Etymology: From Latin *gratia* (“kindness, favor, esteem”), the word from which English *grace* originated.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Grace 15.44320* — Photograph. 2316×3088. Ventral view. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Subject facing camera, sunglasses on. Hair positioned ventrally, slightly obscuring left shoulder. Both hands inside pockets. Outdoor lighting, roof of building. Sky consistent with golden hour. *Argenclara gratia* wb. E.Grace.J., 2023. © E. Grace Jones or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 06623a2b019f575ed54def935c1c7f84c8d3460d59269d1618d0debd3975db65; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/E_Grace_Jones3.jpg?v=1692901801; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414035453/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/E_Grace_Jones3.jpg?v=1692901801

Grace 15.44710 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Ventral view. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Subject facing camera, sunglasses on. Hair positioned ventrally, slightly obscuring left shoulder. Both hands inside pockets. Outdoor lighting, roof of building. Sky consistent with golden hour. *Argenclara gratia* wb. E.Grace.J., 2023. © E. Grace Jones or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** ff79b27452986e26c7c8b7d4d71fdd8597d0709199400717f4b8894413d9f1c7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/E_Grace_Jones11.jpg?v=1692901817; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414035514/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/E_Grace_Jones11.jpg?v=1692901817

Grace 15.44737 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Dorsal view. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Subject looking to her left, sunglasses on. Hair positioned dorsally. Both hands inside pockets. Outdoor lighting, roof of building. Sky consistent with golden hour. *Argenclara gratia* wb. E.Grace.J., 2023. © E. Grace Jones or unknown photographer, all

rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 827b1082921f58d7b05b24dc954f3fb0d9a5b42a87a9fd166f77863059e4b012; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/E_Grace_Jones4.jpg?v=1692901809; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414035452/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/E_Grace_Jones4.jpg?v=1692901809

2.4.1.10 *Argenclara hetheringtonia*

Argenclara hetheringtonia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara hetheringtonia* is characterized by its blue, very slightly transparent fabric, with three distinct building designs, a tree, and other flora.

Figure 8: Natural range of *Ficus macrophylla* Desf. ex Pers. in eastern Australia. The range includes Sydney and Brisbane, the two primary candidates for Hetherington’s location. Map by Casliber (2018); range according to Dixon (2001). *Ficus macrophylla* has been cultivated outside of its range, which reduces our confidence in our inference of Australia as Hetherington’s location.

Remarks: We infer that Emily Hetherington is Australian, based on the tree in the background of all three photographs being consistent with *Ficus macrophylla* Desf. ex Pers. This was confirmed when we later discovered Hetherington’s Instagram profile, where she self-reports Queensland as her location. Hetherington additionally posted her make to Instagram (Hetherington 2023). Silversaga gallery preferred for reproducibility.

Etymology: From *Hetherington* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Hetherington 240.4350* — Photograph. EXIF

metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. 2250×3000 Ventral view. Outdoor lighting conditions, daytime. Subject standing in forest, under tree. Left arm adducted. Right hand placed slightly inferior to inferior elastic channel on lateral surface. Right foot forward. Entire dress in frame. *Argenclara hetheringtonia* wb. E.Heth., 2023. © Emily Hetherington or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Photograph locality:** Australia: Queensland. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 43087f0d8acdc4b6a0ad60e46a9880be13e619d46ecfe99c752be3ec03f95c05; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Emily-Hetherington6.jpg?v=1692903153>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260414045126/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Emily-Hetherington6.jpg?v=1692903153>

Hetherington 240.4717 — Photograph. 2250×3000 EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Dorsal view. Outdoor lighting conditions, daytime. Subject standing in forest. *Argenclara hetheringtonia* wb. E.Heth., 2023. © Emily Hetherington or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 096ee14282ece7e61f33e23efc7cd4ad1d33241ae9e90bb845ee49ce7ca0d774; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Emily-Hetherington4.jpg?v=1692903178>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161545/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Emily-Hetherington4.jpg?v=1692903178>

Hetherington 240.5670 — Photograph. 2250×3000 EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Ventral view. Outdoor lighting conditions, daytime. Subject standing in forest. *Argenclara hetheringtonia* wb. E.Heth., 2023. © Emily Hetherington or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** b7dc17222f0e049c44a8ac18854ce419d9d3ec7c423ff6970b51cb46e5a21036; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Emily-Hetherington9.jpg?v=1692903165>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260414045117/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Emily-Hetherington9.jpg?v=1692903165>

2.4.1.11 *Argenclara jessae*

Argenclara jessae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara jessae* is characterized by its solid brown fabric.

Remarks: See also J. Jones (2023) for Jones's Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Jessa* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: Jones 28.1741 — Photograph. 2316×3088 Ventral view. Semi-outdoors environment; subject under roof, on patio. Subject's arms adducted and in bilateral pockets. Hair positioned dorsally. Bilateral earrings. Neckline not obscured. *Argenclara jessae* wb. Jessa.J., 2023. © Jessa Jones or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 4a5a1a52a6d65719e0643ddcc9c16b09e613f6ef63bd26f783fcb7523421ea8d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones5.jpg?v=1692900432; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161532/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones5.jpg?v=1692900432

Jones 28.1835 — Photograph. 2967×3956 Ventral view. Semi-outdoors environment; subject under roof, on patio. Other houses in background. Subject's arms adducted and in bilateral pockets. Hair positioned dorsally. Bilateral earrings. Neckline not obscured. *Argenclara jessae* wb. Jessa.J., 2023. © Jessa Jones or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 4fb548d548ba2a2da09871e7f8777913fafc45a9e3f8a627f5d7265ec2e750ef; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones2.jpg?v=1692900418; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161556/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones2.jpg?v=1692900418

Jones 28.1837 — Photograph. 2316×3088 Ventral view. Semi-outdoors environment; subject under roof, on patio. Subject's left arm on patio railing. Right arm not visible. Sleeves worn lateral to upper arm, as off-shoulder. *Argenclara jessae* f. *umst.* wb. Jessa.J., 2023. © Jessa Jones or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 56e72cc47563229110332b014fc9404a14a3ef29d1d47cdf10354b550177dde5; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones4.jpg?v=1692900426; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413160055/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones4.jpg?v=1692900426

2.4.1.12 *Argenclara mai*

Argenclara mai Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara mai* is characterized by its fabric, a light mocha background with clusters of white flowers.

Remarks: We infer the year as 2023 based on the other rounds of pattern testing conducted by Silversaga.

The photographs appear to have been taken at a two-story residential structure, with *Mai* in the shadow of another building behind the photographer. The ground has significant overexposure.

Etymology: From *Mai* Vang's first name, *Mai*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Vang 25.4050* — Photograph. 2209×3031. Ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. Slight motion blur on left arm. Right arm fully adducted. *Argenclara mai* wb. Mai, 2023. © Mai Vang or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 44b249a15c5640ab762cba2c929ec502e61174c94d0397696a1315dae02948c4; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mai_Vang3.jpg?v=1692901558; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161528/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mai_Vang3.jpg?v=169290155

Vang 25.4085 — Photograph. 1967×2622. Ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. Subject's arms fully adducted. *Argenclara mai* wb. Mai, 2023. © Mai Vang or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 836057f9419577ddb9e1991e9e166067f59757e1ffadd033922f6d81228521a7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mai_Vang2.jpg?v=1692901378; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413160700/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mai_Vang2.jpg?v=169290137

2.4.1.13 *Argenclara malinae*

Argenclara malinae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara malinae* is characterized by its fabric, a quilt cotton from Selfmade.com; featuring white flowers on a red background.

Remarks: Malin's Instagram post documenting the make is available at Stara (2023).

Etymology: From *Malin* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Stara 10.19448* — Photograph. 2000×3008. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting. *Argenclara malinae* f. *umst.* wb. Malin.S., 2023. © Malin Stara or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** a4fdf3d5536e9a4b6095495adb3a5dbbd53151a258f307af84076cb669acacc2; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Malin_Stara2.jpg?v=1692899533; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161551/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Malin_Stara.jpg?v=1692899512

Stara 10.19571 — Photograph. 2000×3008. *Argenclara malinae* wb. Malin.S., 2023. © Malin Stara or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 683db976955ab01c92c32a6d6f9f5ae7cfb3bd539c3de91dd15b09ee43fd87b4; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Malin_Stara3.jpg?v=1692899523; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413154853/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Malin_Stara3.jpg?v=1692899523

Stara 10.19780 — Photograph. 2000×3008. *Argenclara malinae* wb. Malin.S., 2023. © Malin Stara or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 00ea6fbd28dc593ecb14d05eeee1c9c99a27f2b3bdc28c5027c409cf3fefde5c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Malin_Stara.jpg?v=1692899512; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413154851/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Malin_Stara.jpg?v=1692899512

2.4.1.14 *Argenclara morgania*

Argenclara morgania Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara morgania* is characterized by its fabric, a light turquoise floral pattern on a white background.

Description:

Remarks: We had great difficulty attempting to identify the wearer of *Argenclara morgania*. Numerous people named Mackenzie Morgan exist; and Silversaga's Instagram posts featuring Morgan did not include a tag for Morgan's Instagram account, if it even exists.

Etymology: From *Morgan* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Morgan 13.57610* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting. Subject on wooden walkway with forest in background. No confident correspondence to botanical taxa. *Argenclara morgania* wb. Mackenzie.M., unknown. © Mackenzie Morgan or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** e0ec8f3ea200032ac9876d2add05b755ab2e270d9403e9c864cdf1a370b7255e; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan2.jpg?v=1692899387; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413154134/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan2.jpg?v=1692899387

Morgan 13.57633 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting. Subject in darker lighting compared to background. Subject looking to her right, slightly downward. Hair positioned dorsally with slight drape on right side, laterally, obscuring right edge of neckline and shoulder. Small strands of hair ventral. Subject walking on wooden deck with forest in background.

Argenclara morgania f. *umst.* wb. Mackenzie.M., unknown. © Mackenzie Morgan or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 35b3dead3e28d030388c6b98c68ad887ceec48a694d31b8c303f5bbce88a8462; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan4.jpg?v=1692899416; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413154325/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan4.jpg?v=1692899416

Morgan 13.57635 — Photograph. 2670×4032. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting. Subject looking to her right, slightly downward. Hair positioned dorsally. Subject standing behind large wooden door. Significant overexposure in top-right of image. *Argenclara morgania* wb. Mackenzie.M., unknown. © Mackenzie Morgan or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 41f388c08711c703345b4dc1985d2d2442db8e24078d48557fc89240dc1a2f17; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan.jpg?v=1692899399; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161547/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan.jpg?v=1692899399

Morgan 13.58900 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting. Subject looking to her right, roughly level. Hair positioned ventrally, tied and draped over left shoulder, slightly obscuring small portion of neckline. Subject on floor of building, between two pillars. Photographer not visible in reflection of doors. *Argenclara morgania* wb. Mackenzie.M., unknown. © Mackenzie Morgan or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 055b991913d5e646615a42f4fb7f6f54cf5cae30a55d54e1f168ebe24c54e874; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan7.jpg?v=1692899408; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413154331/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mackenzie_Morgan7.jpg?v=1692899408

2.4.1.15 *Argenclara teschia*

Argenclara teschia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara teschia* is characterized by its fabric, a white-slight gray/teal gingham pattern.

Etymology: From *Tesch* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Tesch 50.6700** — Photograph. 2464×3280. Ventral view. Subject's arms extended. Hair positioned entirely dorsally, likely tied. Neckline not obscured. In-

door lighting conditions. White wall in background; subject near corner. Unknown potted plant in background; no known correspondence to botanical taxa. *Argenclara teschia* wb. Mel.T., 2023. © Mel Tesch or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** fa16c0ff27e6d724e68ee3dbd256f6f4a58ec619d0f6bcae428ff1041bee9baa; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mel_Tesch9.jpg?v=1692900615; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413160342/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mel_Tesch9.jpg?v=1692900615

Tesch 50.6751 — Photograph. 2464×3280. Ventral view. Subject's arms adducted. Right leg extended laterally. Hair positioned entirely dorsally, likely tied. Neckline not obscured. Indoor lighting conditions. White wall in background; subject near corner. Unknown potted plant in background; no known correspondence to botanical taxa. *Argenclara teschia* wb. Mel.T., 2023. © Mel Tesch or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 29dcdcfefe145527f57e15d271c5191265044f02cf6240f864fe3ecb7dc3db8; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mel_Tesch3.jpg?v=1692900601; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413160343/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mel_Tesch3.jpg?v=1692900601

Tesch 50.6790 — Photograph. 2464×3280. Ventral view, slightly angled. Subject's arms mostly adducted. Hair positioned entirely dorsally, likely tied. Neckline not obscured. Indoor lighting conditions. White wall in background; subject near corner. Unknown potted plant in background; no known correspondence to botanical taxa. *Argenclara teschia* wb. Mel.T., 2023. © Mel Tesch or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 4b8768b4ad2ec6fd9a36f039e2b2bd9b1c4af1899c130990ea8ca515cb94c309; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mel_Tesch4.jpg?v=1692900608; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161557/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Mel_Tesch4.jpg?v=1692900608

2.4.1.16 *Argenclara theresae*

Argenclara theresae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara theresae* is characterized by its fabric, solid black, 100% cotton shirting from JoAnn Fabrics. It was cut in a size 36 based on Theresa's bust measurement. It lacks pockets. The sleeve was lengthened by 1 in (2.54 cm).

Remarks: See also Theresa.N. (2023) for Theresa's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Theresa* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Theresa* 23.2818AT — Photograph. 3294×4118 Ventral view. Indoors. Window to subject's right, fully open, daytime conditions. Hair positioned dorsally, likely tied. Neckline not obscured. Subject's head slanted very slightly right. Arms fully adducted. *Argenclara theresae* wb. Theresa.N., 2023. © Theresa Neef or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 78d1a33a0b23d4314740fc039d87737ed1857f0e658e8d097a9c9ba42893fdd3; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Theresa_Neef5.jpg?v=1692902728; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414043552/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Theresa_Neef5.jpg?v=1692902728

Theresa 23.3092AT — Photograph. 2410×3012 Ventral view. Indoors. Window to subject's right, fully open, daytime conditions. Hair positioned dorsally, likely tied. Neckline not obscured. Hands placed on wall. Zoomed out view. *Argenclara theresae* wb. Theresa.N., 2023. © Theresa Neef or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 28ec362d9a28844d2df2d72fcf0c702b8da2370286109b928bd4d4239642b319; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Theresa_Neef6.jpg?v=1692902719; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414043523/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Theresa_Neef6.jpg?v=1692902719

Theresa 23.3091AT — Photograph. 2733×3416 Truncated angled ventral view. Indoors. Window to subject's right, fully open, daytime conditions. Hair positioned dorsally, likely tied. Neckline not obscured. Arms placed on lateral portions of ventral surface, inferior to inferior waist channel. *Argenclara theresae* wb. Theresa.N., 2023. © Theresa Neef or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 05634dfb5036b41fa05ddf16bea8ab12915adfc7b0dc3d02de3641af459009d7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Theresa_Neef.jpg?v=1692902739; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414043538/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Theresa_Neef.jpg?v=1692902739

2.4.1.17 *Argenclara wilhoitia*

Argenclara wilhoitia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara wilhoitia* is characterized by its plain pink fabric.

Etymology: From *Wilhoit* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Wilhoit* 34.1870 — Photograph. 1500×1518 EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Angled ventral view. Subject facing to her left, as if walking. Hair positioned ventrally, draped to subject's right, obscuring right neckline edge. Left hand position unknown. Right hand on hair. Outdoors. Mid-day. Grass field surrounded by trees. Botanical identification impossible due to plants being out of focus. *Argenclara wilhoitia* wb. Lacy.W., unknown. © Lacy Wilhoit or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 3c9df8f8fe22fa80202e14b52d74ea6da2f784b342db0785d7077783a0fad483; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lacy_Wilhoit9.jpg?v=1692902602; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161536/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lacy_Wilhoit9.jpg?v=1692902602

Wilhoit 34.1957 — Photograph. 1512×2016 EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Truncated ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. Both hands placed on lateral surfaces inferior to inferior elastic channel. Outdoors. Mid-day. Grass field surrounded by trees. Botanical identification impossible due to plants being out of focus. *Argenclara wilhoitia* wb. Lacy.W., unknown. © Lacy Wilhoit or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** b6eb6e4e302b59b3ffd06d38a0c29f94c771eabe60fba54b40a5c85a761107f9; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lacy_Wilhoit.jpg?v=1692902593; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414045606/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lacy_Wilhoit.jpg?v=1692902593

Wilhoit 34.3771 — Photograph. 1424×1594 EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Truncated dorsal view. Hair positioned ventrally, likely tied; neckline fully visible. Subject's arms adducted. Outdoors. Mid-day. Grass field surrounded by trees. Botanical identification impossible due to plants being out of focus. *Argenclara wilhoitia* wb. Lacy.W., unknown. © Lacy Wilhoit or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 3f12a5b413540f5622d6c0b96c491d0b271bcd24ccaf349bd6d2bb469521d371; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lacy_Wilhoit1.jpg?v=1692902608; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260414045612/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lacy_Wilhoit1.jpg?v=1692902608

2.4.2 *Argenclara* subg. *Venaluna*

Argenclara subgenus *Venaluna* Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara* subg. *Venaluna* is phylogenetically characterized by having been sewn by Katie Hunter-

Moon.

Etymology: Portmanteau of Latin *venatrix* (“hunter”) + *luna* (“moon”).

Remarks: We choose *Argenclara lunatris* as the type species due to its non-toile state.

Type species: *Argenclara lunatris*

2.4.2.1 *Argenclara lunatris*

Argenclara lunatris Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara lunatris* is characterized by its fabric, light pink flowers and green leaves on a black background.

Remarks:

Etymology: From *lunatrix* + Latin *bis* (“twice”), as it is Hunter-Moon’s second make.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Hunter-Moon 25.17665* — Photograph. 1184×1776. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Ventral view. Subject looking to her left. Light source from her left; indoor white lighting. Motion blur from left hand holding bouquet of flowers. *Argenclara lunatris* wb. Hunter-Moon, unknown. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** a471730cb1e901428ce5707f3dba2dad285622f5a89ac073b9d341b37534c57c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon5.jpg?v=1692901633; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413161010/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon5.jpg?v=1692901633

Hunter-Moon 25.17803 — Photograph. 1184×1776. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Subject looking to her right. Light source from her left; indoor white lighting. Slight motion blur. Left hand in pocket; right hand holding flower. Window behind white curtain. *Argenclara lunatris* wb. Hunter-Moon, unknown. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 29d6079a9afa851f21e905d87dac3b8992706c8eef6309b697b38a02baac7515; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon3.jpg?v=1692901618; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161529/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon3.jpg?v=1692901618

Hunter-Moon 25.17921 — Photograph. 1184×1776. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Ventral view. Subject looking to her right.

Light source from her left; indoor white lighting. Less motion blur. Left hand on lateral side of waist. Right hand holding bouquet of yellow flowers. *Argenclara lunatris* wb. Hunter-Moon, unknown. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** f14e1e300c1c0018d781c7f43b744bd0a19be81526ae21d82624277728cfa17c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon4.jpg?v=1692901626; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161550/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon4.jpg?v=1692901626

2.4.2.2 *Argenclara lunatrix*

Argenclara lunatrix Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara lunatrix* is characterized by its solid white fabric, slightly transparent.

Remarks: *Argenclara lunatrix* was likely sewn as a toile (muslin). The same or similar images were published on Instagram (Hunter-Moon 2023). The holotypes available through the Silversaga website are preferred for reproducibility and higher quality.

Etymology: Portmanteau of Latin *luna* (“moon”) + *venatrix*, feminine form of *venator* (“hunter”).

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Hunter-Moon 23.4877* — Photograph. 2926×4389. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Ventral view. Subject standing on coast. Outdoors lighting conditions, possibly dawn or dusk from color of sky, consistent with golden hour. Hair positioned ventrally, slightly draped on subject’s right shoulder. United Kingdom, Wales. *Argenclara lunatrix* wb. Hunter-Moon, 2023. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 6c8f53d040ffb38e67e3e790b0fd2d4e09468d6770f25bffa1bf75906908c039; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon6.jpg?v=1692899662; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161530/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon6.jpg?v=1692899662

Hunter-Moon 23.4901 — Photograph. 2926×4389. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Dorsal view. Subject standing on coast. Outdoors lighting conditions, possibly dawn or dusk based on color of sky, consistent with golden hour. Subject walking amongst rocks. Wind blowing dress and hair to subject’s left. United Kingdom, Wales. *Argenclara lunatrix* wb. Hunter-Moon, 2023. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights

reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** c51095fc15911c1706298a2922f7b9fe028ea729d49864b33158dd473716b78d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon7.jpg?v=1692899670; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161528/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon7.jpg?v=1692899670

Hunter-Moon 23.5361 — Photograph. 2926×4389. EXIF metadata stripped, consistent with Shopify image processing. Dorsal view. Subject standing on coast. Outdoors lighting conditions, possibly dawn or dusk based on color of sky, consistent with golden hour. Subject walking amongst rocks, facing in the direction of the water. United Kingdom, Wales. *Argenclara lunatrix* wb. Hunter-Moon, 2023. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 14345281caae7a41cd86d0abe77c71ff04b8727b00fe6f089e8558a293a3f8ef; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon13.jpg?v=1692899685; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260413155350/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Katie_Hunter-Moon13.jpg?v=1692899685

2.4.3 *Argenclara* subg. *Lacashira*

Argenclara* subgenus *Lacashira Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara* subg. *Lacashira* is characterized by the presence of lace in the insert between the superior and interior waist channels.

Etymology: From *Laca*, pseudo-Latin form of *lace* + *shira*, pseudo-Latin form of *shirr*.

Type species: *Argenclara mantorae*

2.4.3.1 *Argenclara mantorae*

Argenclara mantorae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenclara mantorae* is characterized by its fabric, a viscose–tencel blend from MeetMILK fabric, with a subtle gingham check pattern, and by the usage of lace fabric as a trim at the distal edges of the sleeve, as the primary fabric between the waist channels, and as another trim at the inferior end of the skirt.

Description:

Remarks: See also Mantori (2023a) for Suna’s Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Mantori* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. White curtain in background. Light source from subject’s left.

Holotype: *Mantori 19.3097* — Photograph. 2667×4000. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally. Most strands terminating on subject’s left side, with small single strand on right side. Neckline shoulder edges not obscured. Subject’s left arm placed on skirt, on lateral surface just inferior to inferior elastic channel. Right arm extended out of frame. Neckline stretched to roughly scapula level, with ~10–25% of shoulder area exposed. *Argenclara mantorae* wb. Suna.M., 2023. © Suna Mantori or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 6e25bd7c36ed209cca5fe6f73be80c74ffa2b1485ff97e1a3b69ef78c83ee2b; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna-Mantori6.jpg?v=1692899267>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161553/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna-Mantori6.jpg?v=1692899267>

Mantori 19.1761 — Photograph. 2771×4000. Dorsal view. Hair positioned ventrally, with small strands draping dorsally, neckline not significantly obscured. Subject’s left arm placed on superior portion of skirt. Right arm extends out of frame. Neckline stretched to roughly scapula level, with ~10–25% of shoulder area exposed. *Argenclara mantorae* wb. Suna.M., 2023. © Suna Mantori or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** df7a021014cdf4cbe8e2d3e8c4405c62a2252120d2b87561441a556f9bc5ac2a; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna-Mantori5.jpg?v=1692899286>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318161541/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna-Mantori5.jpg?v=1692899286>

Mantori 19.1823 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally, draping laterally, neckline not significantly obscured. Subject’s left arm placed on skirt, on lateral surface just inferior to inferior elastic channel. Neckline stretched to roughly scapula level, with ~10–25% of shoulder area exposed. *Argenclara mantorae* wb. Suna.M., 2023. © Suna Mantori or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** a58e3f4d81d66735aa8c1a25e8aceb19d45547ef4a1245b71209b66f6228c2ef; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna-Mantori.jpg?v=1692899248>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260413153422/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna-Mantori.jpg?v=1692899248>

2.4.4 Genus *Trunclara*

Trunclara Lemuria, 2026; gen. nov.

Diagnosis: *Trunclara* is distinguished from *Argenclara* by the lack of a skirt.

Juliette (Silversaga 2023c). She closed applications on November 14, 2023. On December 2, 2023, the Juliette was released.

The belt, with its ventral medial tie, is often draped over the ventral medial button row in many holotype images, which can prevent accurate counts of the number of buttons.

Design. Jessica cites the peasant dress as inspiration for the Juliette.

Making. Silversaga recommends a lightweight structured fabric, including but not limited to cotton, linen, and some blends. Silversaga designed the dress to be cut from 130 cm (51 in) wide fabric. Estimated fabric use, low estimates: 4.45 m (57,850 cm²) at EU34, 5.65 m at EU50 (73,450 cm²).

Etymology: *Juliette* + *-idae*, family suffix.

Type genus: *Julietta* Lemuria, 2026; gen. nov.

2.5.1 Genus *Julietta*

Julietta Lemuria, 2026; gen. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta* is the *sensu stricto* genus of Juliettidae. *Julietta* is characterized by origin from the Juliette pattern with minimal divergence.

Etymology: *Juliette* + *-a* to Latinize it.

Type species: *Julietta alexisae*

2.5.1.1 *Julietta alexisae*

Julietta alexisae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta alexisae* is characterized by its fabric, a solid black lycelle from Blackbird Fabrics. 3.6 m (4 yd) used. Size EU38. Black buttons, unknown reflective material. Four thread holes within central inset. Button hole alignment in plus shape relative to vertical direction. Buttons on wearer's right.

Remarks: See also Wright (2023b) for Wright's Instagram post.

The positioning of the ventral medial tie obscured significant portions of the ventral medial button row.

Etymology: From *Alexis* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Alexis* 2023.178.86867 — Photograph. 2668×4000. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting conditions. Vegetation in background. No direct sunlight on subject. Hair positioned ventrally, lateral to chin, bilaterally, obscuring significant portion of neckline. Subject's left arm placed on left lateral surface

of ventral medial belt. Right arm adducted. First button obscured by hair. Buttons 2–6 visible. Buttons inferior to 6th button obscured by ventral medial tie. Inferiormost four buttons of ventral medial button row unfastened. *Julietta alexisae* wb. Alexis.Wr., 2023. © Alexis Wright or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 7bf0708c7b0609e81f51ab5af1e952ee4613adc57465b693263a45b8de58b13c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis_Wright4.jpg?v=1701386867; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171516/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis_Wright4.jpg?v=1701386867

Alexis 2023.178.86880 — Photograph. 2668×4000. Left lateral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting conditions. Vegetation in background. No direct sunlight on subject. Hair draped lateral to head, bilaterally. Ventral neckline obscured by angle. Dorsal neckline obscured by hair. Subject's left arm presumably positioned ventrally. Right arm entirely invisible. No buttons visible. *Julietta alexisae* wb. Alexis.Wr., 2023. © Alexis Wright or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** db4ef0faac8c38de61a87151e3edd3db071be9ad62d3efca1af67d8d232f927; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis_Wright5.jpg?v=1701386880; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171521/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis_Wright5.jpg?v=1701386880

Alexis 2023.178.39088 — Photograph. 2668×4000. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting conditions. Vegetation in background. No direct sunlight on subject. Hair draped lateral to head, bilaterally. Lateral portions of neckline obscured. Left arm extended outward, holding skirt. Right arm mostly adducted. Ventral medial button row on bodice entirely visible. Inferior portions of ventral medial button row unfastened; portions of subject's right lower leg visible. *Julietta alexisae* wb. Alexis.Wr., 2023. © Alexis Wright or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 54a91d9be59850d9439dad9e9ff2d94e0ef71731440477fec8855184185229bf; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis_Wright14.jpg?v=1701439088; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171434/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alexis_Wright14.jpg?v=1701439088

Alexis 2023.178.IG159 — Instagram post. COUmN01v8hB. Wright (2023b). Eight photographs, numbered 01–08 from left to right.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.01 — Photograph. Identical in content to *Alexis* 2023.178.86867. Dispreferred due to image quality and reproducibility issues.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.02 — Photograph.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.03 — Photograph.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.04 — Photograph.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.05 — Photograph.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.06 — Photograph.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.07 — Photograph.

Alexis 2023.178.IG159.08 — Photograph.

2.5.1.2 *Julietta annettae*

Julietta annettae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta annettae* is characterized by its fabric, a Robert Kaufman hunter green plaid (tartan) fabric (SB-13110D17-29; *SB-13110D17-29 HUNTER from Sevenberry: Classic Plaid Twill (2026)*) from Gather Here (stylized gather_here). Size EU36 (“updated” according to Annette.N. (2023b)). Ventral medial button row. Circular buttons, black and slight stone gray color. Two thread holes, thread line horizontal.

Remarks: See also Annette.N. (2023b) for Annette’s Instagram post, and Annette.N. (2023a) for an Instagram reel.

With regards to the placement of the buttons, the semi-unfastened state was likely only exhibited during a single photoshoot. All three photographs are from the same photoshoot.

Etymology: From *Annette* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: ***Annette 2023.15.6104*** — Photograph. 2736×3648. Ventral view. Outdoors, daytime lighting conditions. White brick wall in background on top of concrete wall base. Leaves on ground. Hair tied dorsally, no obscuration of neckline (as inferred from visible tie on other images.) Subject’s left arm extended outwards holding skirt. Right arm presumably adducted. *Julietta annettae* wb. Annette.N., 2023. © Annette Nicoletti or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Annette.N. (2023b); **SHA2-256:** 23f3a7a90853215376dd8468c9e8fdcfb8a274b5c3cb0b7d02fcd6ee5b87842b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/annette_nicoletti_-_annette.sews_04.jpg?v=1701387007; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171444/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/annette_nicoletti_-_annette.sews_04.jpg?v=1701387007

Annette 2023.15.6709 — Photograph. 2736×3648. Outdoors, daytime lighting conditions. White brick wall in background on top of concrete wall base. Leaves on ground. Hair tied dorsally (visible dorsal tie, same fabric

as *Julietta annettae*; unclassified), no obscuration of neckline. Second and third buttons partially unfastened. Second button ~15% receded into buttonhole, 50% receded into buttonhole. Fourth buttons obscured by ventral medial tie. Subject’s arms fully adducted. *Julietta annettae* wb. Annette.N., 2023. © Annette Nicoletti or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Annette.N. (2023b); **SHA2-256:** d57a3026ea65eab0ddde3cefd6772f293dc7740794cda331d0ee5f30a6e285f9; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/annette_nicoletti_-_annette.sews_06.jpg?v=1701387040; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171529/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/annette_nicoletti_-_annette.sews_06.jpg?v=1701387040

Annette 2023.15.6834 — Photograph. 2736×3648. Outdoors, daytime lighting conditions. White brick wall in background on top of concrete wall base. Leaves on ground. Hair tied dorsally (visible dorsal tie, same fabric as *Julietta annettae*; unclassified), no obscuration of neckline. Subject’s left arm extended, holding skirt out. Right arm adducted, also holding skirt. *Julietta annettae* wb. Annette.N., 2023. © Annette Nicoletti or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Annette.N. (2023b); **SHA2-256:** 7dec17a4ae90b852f3fe9244b3e6bcebe3ce865d3489568c31edf701c97cfc25; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/annette_nicoletti_-_annette.sews_07.jpg?v=1701387048; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171531/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/annette_nicoletti_-_annette.sews_07.jpg?v=1701387048

2.5.1.3 *Julietta ariae*

Julietta ariae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta ariae* is characterized by its fabric, a slub linen rayon blend from JoAnn, dyed twice in “woodland” from Rit dye; the resulting color is light forest green. It deviates from the pattern with a ventral medial row of only 12 buttons, and sleeves 1 in (2.54 cm) shorter. Yellow buttons, unknown reflective material; four thread holes.

Remarks: Aria only sewed 12 buttons due to either her energy levels or button supply having depleted. She remarks that the dress, despite its lower button count, has not significantly spread apart such as to constitute a wardrobe malfunction; and that she may decide to retain the button count of 12. See Aria.W.S. (2023) for Aria’s original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Aria* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. All photographs appear to

have been taken in outdoor lighting conditions, with no apparent direction of sunlight. Taken in the backyard of a house. Unknown plant in background, closest possible match to *Corylus avellana* L. (hazel, common hazel, European hazel). The subject's hair is positioned ventrally; it bilaterally drapes over the bodice, obscuring the ventral medial button row. First, second, third, and fourth buttons unfastened; buttons from fifth button onward fastened.

Holotype: *Aria* 2023.190.371 — Photograph. 3072×4080. Ventral view. Subject facing to her right. Arms bilaterally placed on lateral surfaces of belt. *Julietta ariae* wb. Aria.W.S., 2023. © Aria Wright-Shriver or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** b3a390776b67fcad7b0393afc15b8ec9f5a0bea7b2988941527d79440a955841; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/PXL_20231128_183137499.MP_2.jpg?v=1701443004; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171518/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/PXL_20231128_183137499.MP_2.jpg?v=1701443004

Aria 2023.190.390 — Photograph. 3072×4080. Ventral view. Subject's arms extended outward. *Julietta ariae* wb. Aria.W.S., 2023. © Aria Wright-Shriver or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** fa8a2ccfef0a1fcb25617a412facca624dc369abc0bf6a4b58d84c4d75c3c8ee; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/PXL_20231128_183113426.MP_1_2.jpg?v=1701442982; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171450/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/PXL_20231128_183113426.MP_1_2.jpg?v=1701442982

Aria 2023.190.464 — Photograph. 3072×4080. Ventral view. Subject facing to her right. Arms bilaterally placed on lateral surfaces of belt. *Julietta ariae* wb. Aria.W.S., 2023. © Aria Wright-Shriver or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 5e43a1273d5c3b6891b6c1775f3faee83e67db18f3d4640e2c57a521c640e330; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/PXL_20231128_183131504.MP_3.jpg?v=1701443020; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171502/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/PXL_20231128_183131504.MP_3.jpg?v=1701443020

2.5.1.4 *Julietta baumgartia*

Julietta baumgartia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta baumgartia* is characterized by its fabric, a navy blue cotton broadcloth of unknown origin; the presence of triangles at the inferior edge of the skirt; while its ventral medial button row features white buttons made of an unknown reflective material, with two

thread holes. The thread lines of the buttons are highly variable.

Remarks: Baumgart remarks that the inferior edge triangles were accidental; she had forgotten to attach the skirt pieces before cutting. She remarked how similar situations often occur in vintage garments. See (Baumgart 2023b) for Baumgart's Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Baumgart* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. Just as with *Ac. baumgartia*, *J. baumgartia* was taken in the same room, as can be inferred from the floor visible in *Baumgart* 2023.10485.176. A window is to her right in 176 and 338, through which the sun shines intensely, causing underexposure on the left side of the dress due to dynamic range adjustments. 662 is a tighter crop, though the shadow to her left still leads to underexposure. The pixels within 176 are significantly grainier than the other two.

Holotype: *Baumgart* 2023.10485.176 — Photograph. 2457×3276. Ventral view. Subject facing to her right. Arms extending skirt outward bilaterally. *Julietta baumgartia* wb. Eliz.B., 2023. © Elizabeth Baumgart or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 207c0cfa360576362fe8232d81f9cb0a ae2f1fa96231846f971d2b07e0b6ad4f; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Thatsewliz_juliette_2.jpg?v=1701443357; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171435/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Thatsewliz_juliette_2.jpg?v=1701443357

Baumgart 2023.10485.338 — Photograph. 2454×3272. Ventral view. Subject facing to her right. Arms extending skirt outward bilaterally; right arm significantly further out. Ventral medial tie drapes diagonally, allowing view of the skirt portion of the ventral medial button row. Button material reflecting sunlight. *Julietta baumgartia* wb. Eliz.B., 2023. © Elizabeth Baumgart or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 03d56f9f6cf7b736ceccd54c72a2 94c766c52f29c976901e99a08b0a36078337; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Thatsewliz_juliette_3.jpg?v=1701443374; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171537/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Thatsewliz_juliette_3.jpg?v=1701443374

Baumgart 2023.10485.662 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view. Subject facing to her right. Arms bilaterally placed on lateral surfaces inferior to belt. Belt tied and draping diagonally, leaving ventral medial button row unobscured. *Julietta baumgartia* wb. Eliz.B., 2023.

© Elizabeth Baumgart or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 3d8d498f08d53f2b7da895b2d3b35626be39236e327407a5ea3f6fdb782d6fe8; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Thatsewliz_juliette_7.jpg?v=1701443394; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171437/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Thatsewliz_juliette_7.jpg?v=1701443394

2.5.1.5 *Julietta julianae*

Julietta julianae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta julianae* is characterized by its fabric, an orange–yellow gold fabric with a pattern of two parallel vertical white lines running 90° in a diagonal grid; and its ventral medial button row, consisting of buttons on the wearer’s right. Buttons circular, two thread holes, primarily horizontal thread line. Possible white thread. Reflectivity unknown. Subtle black–brown–gray marks, faint, across button surface.

Remarks: Rucker remarked that the color of the dress varies by lighting conditions; stating that it ranges between “yellow gold” and “orange”. From the lead author’s monitor configuration and visual system (as detailed in Section 1.6.1), *J. julianae* appears to have an orange fabric.

Etymology: From *Juliana* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. All four photographs appear to have been taken indoors, with a curtain to Rucker’s left.

Holotype: *Juliana 2023.501.4871* — Photograph. 2316×3088. Slightly truncated ventral view; hemline not visible. Subject facing to her left. Left arm adducted; right arm extends outward with hand placed on right lateral surface. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring right eye and lateral edges of neckline. Inferiormost button visible; one of subject’s legs extended outward and exposed, inferior to inferiormost button. *Julietta julianae* wb. Juliana.R., 2023. © Juliana Rucker or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Juliana.R. (2023); **SHA2-256:** 2507e6feb4683cfb225e56638859eb71fff9d701ac7a8908e2274c9b2493699a; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker3.jpg?v=1701387296; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171509/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker3.jpg?v=1701387296

Juliana 2023.501.4880 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Truncated ventral view. Subject facing to her left. Left sleeve fully visible. Right sleeve truncated from im-

age. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring lateral edges of neckline. *Julietta julianae* wb. Juliana.R., 2023. © Juliana Rucker or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Juliana.R. (2023); **SHA2-256:** 58dd7e05316d46c6219cfcb678572c26a1f19384d9b4ef52ec77da13d9e939fb; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker4.jpg?v=1701387289; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171451/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker4.jpg?v=1701387289

Juliana 2023.501.4930 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Dorsal view. Subject facing to her left. Arms positioned ventrally. Hair positioned dorsally, obscuring dorsal portion of neckline. *Julietta julianae* wb. Juliana.R., 2023 © Juliana Rucker or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Juliana.R. (2023); **SHA2-256:** 630f728ba214b482c2a7536501038165d1c1e8ddf5089a157814bc3eb94324be; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker2.jpg?v=1701387305; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171522/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker2.jpg?v=1701387305

Juliana 2023.501.4937 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Lateral view. Right sleeve extends out towards camera; right arm placed between lateral and dorsal surface of dress, somewhat inferior to belt. *Julietta julianae* wb. Juliana.R., 2023. © Juliana Rucker or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Juliana.R. (2023); **SHA2-256:** 90041e59149cfd9bb57792f2e0aac1a851c507b00aa0048cdf4037220a95a21; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker.jpg?v=1701387312; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171532/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Juliana_Rucker.jpg?v=1701387312

2.5.1.6 *Julietta mantorae*

Julietta mantorae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta mantorae* is characterized by its fabric, a black broderie anglaise, with small portions of lace in a repeating pattern; consisting of flower-like structures and small lines, near which a triangular pattern of three holes is situated repeatedly; and its ventral medial button row, located on the right. Circular buttons, two thread holes, likely black thread, thread line mostly horizontal.

Synonyms: *Julietta sunae* Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.; (in earlier versions)

Remarks: See Mantori (2023b) for Suna’s original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Mantori* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken outdoors in daytime, possibly in a backyard. Significant foliage near the subject. No apparent source of light. Suna's Instagram post images appear to show the dress in a false navy-blue-like color, possibly due to application of filters. As usual, the images from Silversaga's pattern tester gallery are preferred for reproducibility.

Holotype: *Mantori 2023.531.1321* — Photograph. 2667×4000. Ventral view. Subject facing camera. Subject's left arm extended outward holding skirt; slight motion blur. Right arm fully adducted. *Julietta mantorae* wb. Suna.M., 2023. © Suna Mantori or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 98330235abd42fdd5ebb2f6c823b21fac2d5b2cfa7637bb9e00862be2c64e020;

Original: https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna_Mantori4_c22c175f-b871-4743-be69-735db4c411e7.jpg?v=1701388530; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171512/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna_Mantori4_c22c175f-b871-4743-be69-735db4c411e7.jpg?v=1701388530

Mantori 2023.531.1495 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Truncated ventral view. Subject facing slightly to right. Left arm positioned ventrally medially over skirt. Right arm fully adducted. *Julietta mantorae* wb. Suna.M., 2023. © Suna Mantori or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 562585e06be5343e4b9d12d0b2b569851c9e034801b858a17c0d9570c2c10b52; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna_Mantori5_b7b61902-5692-45e4-9587-f9b50fbfdfbf.jpg?v=1701388668; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171442/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna_Mantori5_b7b61902-5692-45e4-9587-f9b50fbfdfbf.jpg?v=1701388668

Mantori 2023.531.2356 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Dorsal view. Subject facing slightly to left. Both arms mostly adducted. Slight motion blur in inferior regions of skirt. *Julietta mantorae* wb. Suna.M., © Suna Mantori or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 058f2754f5aeebf4293e95fdf15ffa4bc105accec1259e286f5d68a60111bc0be; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna_Mantori2_8e307661-3e4d-4459-8853-8e5e64956c65.jpg?v=1701388688; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171453/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Suna_Mantori2_8e307661-3e4d-4459-8853-8e5e64956c65.jpg?v=1701388688

2.5.1.7 *Julietta manuelae*

Julietta manuelae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta manuelae* is characterized by its fabric, a black linen viscose mix bought from JoAnn Fabrics.

Description:

Remarks: See Wilkes (2023) for Manuela's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Manuela* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. All three photographs were taken in an indoor environment. The subject was facing a white door with three-column windows; of which five rows are visible in the photographs. Manuela's hair terminates around the level of her chin and did not obscure the neckline in all photographs.

Holotype: *Manuela 2023.150.4290* — Photograph. 2574×3772. Ventral view. Subject facing towards door to her right. Subject's left arm on right lateral surface of dress. Left arm adducted. *Julietta manuelae* wb. Manuela.W., 2023. © Manuela Wilkes or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 13124b7b8b8b68bac1bb1dd0e55ead47cae52e3d3670ed6da5318616b2402f27; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes5.jpg?v=1701439688; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171454/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes5.jpg?v=1701439688

Manuela 2023.150.6738 — Photograph. 2456×3057. Truncated ventral view. Subject facing towards door to her left. Subject's left arm extended outwards holding skirt. Subject's right arm also holding skirt, though it is more adducted than the left arm. *Julietta manuelae* wb. Manuela.W., 2023. © Manuela Wilkes or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 23e564dc30e656bfe788102338d8059a61ccffdf65b9372f4b8c17b1242f950b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes2.jpg?v=1701439738; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171447/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes2.jpg?v=1701439738

Manuela 2023.150.5167 — Photograph. 2762×3683. Slightly truncated dorsal view. Inferior portions of skirt invisible; superior surface of subject's head out of frame. Subject's left arm occluded by torso. Subject's right arm on hair. *Julietta manuelae* wb. Manuela.W., 2023. © Manuela Wilkes or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 0c20c1f785c73cb591a04b6c437401769bcdb3b820a56e2f583d8e64a4cea6bd; **Original:**

https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes7.jpg?v=1701439758; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171519/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes7.jpg?v=1701439758

2.5.1.8 *Julietta oliwiae*

Julietta oliwiae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta oliwiae* is characterized by its fabric, a dark stone gray solid fabric, and its significantly narrower ventral waist belt. Its ventral medial button row consists of 18 buttons on the left. Circular buttons, black, unknown reflective material. Two thread holes. Horizontal threadline.

Remarks: 1150, the holotype, shows that the belt may have been tied dorsally. Jarosz did not post about the Juliette dress on her Instagram.

Etymology: From *Oliwia* (Polish-language spelling of *Olivia*, not a typo) + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken indoors, with sunlight appearing to originate behind the camera, shining on Jarosz, possibly consistent with the location of a window. The photographs are consistently 3024×4032.

Holotype: *Oliwia* 2023.76.1150 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Angled ventral view. Subject facing to right relative to camera. Arms fully adducted. *Julietta oliwiae* wb. Oliwia.J., 2023© Oliwia Jarosz or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 6cdc5a9feb6210fbfb5d4fc92084cd875df54d163140d19a183d02883168f217; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Oliwia_Jarosz4.jpg?v=1701443238; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171504/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Oliwia_Jarosz4.jpg?v=1701443238

Oliwia 2023.76.1190 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject's arms on head. *Julietta oliwiae* wb. Oliwia.J., 2023© Oliwia Jarosz or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** a5ddbe7b18fdc11945328a4ac17e8aa9c5df6f7d76e61fe887b2b1c6e94e63db; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Oliwia_Jarosz3.jpg?v=1701443217; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171528/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Oliwia_Jarosz3.jpg?v=1701443217

Oliwia 2023.76.1415 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject's arms fully adducted. *Julietta oliwiae* wb. Oliwia.J., 2023© Oliwia Jarosz or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et

al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 46a2561e68111316d057e196de07df1a840f8bf583e4fdb1142fefaf1f2cc62ab; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Oliwia_Jarosz.jpg?v=1701443201; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171526/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Oliwia_Jarosz.jpg?v=1701443201

2.5.1.9 *Julietta plettia*

Julietta plettia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta plettia* is characterized by its fabric, a floral fabric consisting of yellow, light red (not pink), and gray flowers on a white background, and a ventral medial button row on the left. Placket narrow; button holes not visible. Buttons circular, unknown white reflective material; two thread holes, thread line mostly horizontal.

Remarks: Silversaga did not tag Plett in her post about the Juliette.

Etymology: From *Plett* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The dress was photographed indoors, in a room with white walls and a wooden floor, and a white curtain to the subject's left, in daylight conditions. The photographs are blurry and prevent a clear view of the fabric.

Holotype: *Plett* 2023.15.9309 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Ventral view. Subject's arms fully adducted. Hair positioned dorsally with slight drape on shoulders. Minor occlusion of neckline. *Julietta plettia* wb. Isabel.P., 2023. © Isabel Plett or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 4845e0ef272a026b75de68123afa57df91ccec07671040d712176e250f635401; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Isabel_Plett6.jpg?v=1701389104; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171446/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Isabel_Plett6.jpg?v=1701389104

Plett 2023.15.9781 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Ventral view. Subject's arms extended slightly outward, holding out skirt. Subject facing slightly to her right. *Julietta plettia* wb. Isabel.P., 2023. © Isabel Plett or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 139038fa1f37b062b9f3b8cc3607446d5ee31e8be69965cbfa6fef0f1a73ce96; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Isabel_Plett5.jpg?v=1701389126; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171534/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Isabel_Plett5.jpg?v=1701389126

Plett 2023.15.4029 — Photograph. 3635×5452. Lateral view. Subject's left arm adducted. Right arm occluded by body. Blurry and unfocused on subject. *Julietta plettia* wb. Isabel.P., 2023. © Isabel Plett or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** a9a00ae912bf01b88327cc85c35c9554ceb49cda4ab558dadcf749b33811103f; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Isabel_Plett7.jpg?v=1701389146; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171441/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Isabel_Plett7.jpg?v=1701389146

2.5.1.10 *Julietta plihalia*

Julietta plihalia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta plihalia* is characterized by its fabric, a Tana Lawn fabric from Liberty, with a black-and-white floral pattern print (*incertae sedis* in the unranked taxon Tana; see Section 3.1). Its ventral medial button row consists of black circular buttons with two thread holes, of variable threadline orientation across the row. Dress made in size 36. Hem shortened 3 in (7.62 mm).

Remarks: See Rucker (2023) for Plihal's original Instagram post. The pattern of the fabric makes observation of the dress's pleats and features difficult.

Etymology: From *Plihal* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in daylight, against a white wall with the subject standing on grass. Shadow patterns on the wall are consistent with vegetation, possibly trees.

Holotype: *Plihal 2023.5607.118* — Photograph. 2475×4032. Ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally, obscuring lateral edges of neckline. Subject's left arm adducted in pockets, right arm similarly adducted. Subject facing forward, slightly leaning downwards to her right. *Julietta plihalia* wb. Paige.P., 2023. © Paige Plihal or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 3a986a6d0319be5b260059a5231006a75268eeb14965079fd1458b235326cc05; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Paige_Plihal.jpg?v=1701443097; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171540/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Paige_Plihal.jpg?v=1701443097

Plihal 2023.5607.196 — Photograph. 2534×3783. Ventral view, zoomed out. Significant portions of subject's face occluded by hair. *Julietta plihalia* wb. Paige.P., 2023. © Paige Plihal or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-**

256: c995b3511b1d17ceaf36f6dcbd43a3fe0c4a83cc182825feb7faf1edfd6eddfa; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Paige_Plihal3.jpg?v=1701443123; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171459/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Paige_Plihal3.jpg?v=1701443123

2.5.1.11 *Julietta samanthae*

Julietta samanthae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta samanthae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material, depicting multiple types of flowers against a white background, with consistent spacing between each flower; and consistently sized flowers in arbitrary rotations. Its ventral medial button row is made of an unknown material; most possibly a light copper-like reflective material or fabric-covered, and is located on the left of the dress.

Remarks: Newbery's Instagram accounts are private. Her last name was inferred from filenames.

Etymology: From *Samantha* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs may have been taken in mild fog. Narrow depth of field centered on subject. The neckline of *J. samanthae* is low enough such that the upper portion of a tattooed moon is visible, which may be useful for wearer identification for other holotypes. In both photographs, Newbery has her hair worn ventrally; lateral to her head, bilaterally

Holotype: *Newbery 2023.158.3048* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject's arms extended outward slightly, holding skirt. *Julietta samanthae* wb. Sam.Ne., 2023. © Samantha Newbery or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 74dd5bd51df906fd4c314b8405e152116091354741419b6664adfecd4258476d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Samantha_Newbery2.jpg?v=1701440663; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171513/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Samantha_Newbery2.jpg?v=1701440663

Newbery 2023.158.3663 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view, tighter crop. Subject facing slightly downwards. Subject's arms extended outward slightly, holding skirt. *Julietta samanthae* wb. Sam.Ne., 2023. © Samantha Newbery or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 43d0d5dd643c989ac6d974ecd5310376118677b9da9144715984871a571c7577; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Samantha_

Newbery3.jpg?v=1701440688; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171437/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Samantha_Newbery3.jpg?v=1701440688

2.5.1.12 *Julietta stephaniae*

Julietta stephaniae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta stephaniae* is characterized by its fabric, a navy blue–black cotton voile, and a ventral medial button row of 18 buttons, narrow, on the left. Four thread holes, primarily at rotated 45° angle.

Remarks: See Goh (2023) for Goh’s Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Stephanie* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in a bright space with white walls and a tree in the background. Apparent light source from the subject’s left (relative to subject’s position in 530).

Holotype: *Goh 2023.589102.108* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view, slightly truncated. Subject sitting on wooden bench. Left arm placed on knee. Right arm on bench. *Julietta stephaniae* wb. Stephanie.G., 2023. © Stephanie Goh or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 0b00b1051994112b8e42bd804337100da59dbadcbf13ce71d88dbfa7b6ef73f8; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh5.jpg?v=1701441048; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171457/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh5.jpg?v=1701441048

Goh 2023.589102.433 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Close-up ventral view, truncated. Significantly higher exposure; wall in background overexposed. Large portions of ventral medial button row visible, with minor occlusion from ventral medial tie. *Julietta stephaniae* wb. Stephanie.G., 2023. © Stephanie Goh or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 650dbae2a78aedfe2bed699671d0e288f2726960f0d31d28acb3e25efd5466c7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh8.jpg?v=1701441183; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171500/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh8.jpg?v=1701441183

Goh 2023.589102.530 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject facing left, slightly upward. Left leg extended to subject’s left. Left arm mostly adducted. Right arm on hair. *Julietta stephaniae* wb. Stephanie.G., 2023. © Stephanie Goh or unknown photographer, 2023, all

rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 5919c9a0e7662229a742f13bd85b0ce5c86ff57f8632345331da9fdaf87e9220; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh3.jpg?v=1701441031; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171448/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh3.jpg?v=1701441031

Goh 2023.589102.887 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Dorsal view. Subject’s arms raised upward. Skirt draping, slightly transparent. *Julietta stephaniae* wb. Stephanie.G., 2023. © Stephanie Goh or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 10f1daaf2bb402cb9dd6f77e1e5c8f2a9f35cc8e5b9646a6284b79924df09e1b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh2.jpg?v=1701441013; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171515/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Goh2.jpg?v=1701441013

2.5.1.13 *Julietta thea*

Julietta thea Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta thea* is characterized by its fabric, a solid slightly light teal cotton poplin, and its ventral medial row of buttons, with circular patterned buttons, mostly white with slight streaks of gray. Two thread holes, thread line mostly horizontal.

Remarks: See Tea.S. (2023) for Tea’s original post.

Etymology: From New Latin *thea* (“tea”).

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken outdoors, in an urban environment, with vegetation in the background.

We infer that 609 and 818 were taken in rapid succession, based on the movement of a bus and car in the left portion of the image, and in the distant right of the image, a faint image of a man in gray having “skipped” forward.

Holotype: *Tea 2023.150.141* — Photograph. 2651×3314. Ventral view. Subject’s arms adducted, legs together, mostly straight posture. Hair mostly dorsal, draping ventrally and obscuring right lateral edge of neckline. *Julietta thea* wb. Tea.S., 2023. © Tea Stamenkovic or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 3d1e73380610be14ecfd8a3afb87b9295015edad8e2ae109f6c6b0d958276de; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic.jpg?v=1701443458; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171439/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/>

[0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic6.jpg?v=1701443458](https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic6.jpg?v=1701443458)

Tea 2023.150.609 — Photograph. 2458×3072. Lateral and dorsal view. Subject's left arm holding onto skirt, right arm occluded by body; hair positioned dorsally. *Julietta thea* wb. Tea.S., 2023. © Tea Stamenkovic or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** b822819bdc6355348088fa840aa97fa47e9fed498ad035e0fc8fa45041b09d2f; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic7.jpg?v=1701443473; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171455/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic7.jpg?v=1701443473

Tea 2023.150.818 — Photograph. 2458×3072. Dorsal view. Hair positioned dorsally, slight occlusion of neckline from hair. Subject's arms mostly adducted, holding onto skirt. *Julietta thea* wb. Tea.S., 2023. © Tea Stamenkovic or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 114304fda84848aa2a8872e41512f0a871c67bd80eb25eafffa85d0391d3113b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic8.jpg?v=1701443488; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171456/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic8.jpg?v=1701443488

2.5.1.14 *Julietta venaluna*

Julietta venaluna Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Julietta venaluna* is characterized by its solid white fabric, unknown material. Small white circular buttons with a mostly diagonal threadline, made of unknown reflective material. Buttons on unknown side.

Remarks: Hunter-Moon did not make an Instagram post about the dress.

Etymology: From Latin *venatrix* (feminine) or *venator* (masculine), both meaning “hunter”, and *luna* (“moon”).

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in a forest, most likely within Wales.

Holotype: **Hunter-Moon 2023.115.401** — Photograph. 3456×5184. Ventral view. Subject against tree, sunlight patterns consistent with vegetation in front. Left arm positioned dorsally, right arm raised against tree, hair positioned mostly dorsally with few strands over left edge of neckline; relatively little occlusion of neckline. *Julietta venaluna* wb. Hunter-Moon, 2023. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, 2023, all

rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 275f9ada9e7bb0115e4af67ed28b9ef5c90396a7f844d30612e8daf893084719; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/image00002.jpg?v=1701440213>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171524/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/image00002.jpg?v=1701440213>

Hunter-Moon 2023.115.688 — Photograph. 2176×3264. Grayscale image. Ventral view. Slightly truncated at inferior portions of skirt. Subject's right hand placed on tree; left hand extended outwards. Shadow line medially running across subject, around the medial portion of left bust. *Julietta venaluna* wb. Hunter-Moon, 2023. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 066eef1269f4a585eadf08541db08fa24e44a1016682fd138cdd3b31f3aef109; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/image00006.jpg?v=1701440231>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171538/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/image00006.jpg?v=1701440231>

Hunter-Moon 2023.115.923 — Photograph. 1184×1776. Lateral view. Subject looking up, left hand placed on tree. Right arm extended forward, no significant lateral distance. *Julietta venaluna* wb. Hunter-Moon, 2023. © Katie Hunter-Moon or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2026); **SHA2-256:** 963291e6f1b231025a1315ff99ed79e2333436f4978f0133ffb9407846406f03; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/image00010.jpg?v=1701440252>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171525/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/image00010.jpg?v=1701440252>

2.6 Subphylum Quaracomorpha

Quaracomorpha Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the phylum Manubristenta.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, Quaracomorpha is characterized by a square neckline.

2.7 Class Kampylilimosida

Kampylilimosida Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the subphylum Quaracomorpha.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, Kampylilimosida is characterized by a square neckline with curved edges.

Etymology: From Greek *καμπύλη* (*kampýli*, ‘curve’) + *λαιμός* (*laimós*, ‘neck’); lit. “curved neck”.

2.8 Order Sueciargenta

Sueciargenta Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the class *Kampylilaimosida*.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, Sueciargenta is characterized by descent from a Silversaga pattern, and phenetically, by a square neckline with curved edges.

Etymology: From Latin *Suecia* (“Sweden”) + *argenta*, feminine form of *argentum* (“silver”).

2.9 Family Argenteleonoridae

Argenteleonoridae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

2.9.1 Genus *Argenteleonora*

Argenteleonora Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Description: Curved square neckline, elastic at neck edge. Fabric gathered superior to the neck edge, and at distal end of sleeves. Raglan sleeves, rather voluminous. Two ventral medial ties, one originating at neckline, another roughly at the transpyloric plane. At waist, invariably, one elasticated channel at bodice–skirt seam. By itself, sect. *Unilastica* (Section 2.9.5); with option of additional channel directly inferior to bust (sect. *Duolastica*, Section 2.9.6). Both options under subg. *Elastica*, Section 2.9.4. Cinched bodice with shirring also available (subg. *Shira*, Section 2.9.2). Skirt terminates inferior to knee, at medial point between ankle and knee, roughly at mid-calf region, described by Silversaga as midi-length. Skirt flares outward, four panels, with hidden pockets. Seam slightly 1–2 cm superior to hemline.

Identification key

- 01 Shirring present on inferior portion of bodice? Yes (02), no (03)
- 02 *Argenteleonora* subg. *Shira*. Intended to resemble the Døen Ischia dress (Donischidae, unpublished)? Yes (09), no (08)
- 03 *Argenteleonora* subg. *Elastica*. Number of elastic channels: one (04), two (05)
- 04 One elastic channel: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Unilastica* (Section 2.9.5). End.
- 05 Two elastic channels. Number of elastic channels with ties: one (06), two (07).
- 06 One of two elastic channels has tie: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Duolastica* (Section 2.9.6). End.
- 07 Both elastic channels have ties: *Argenteleonora* subsect. *Duonoda* (Section 2.9.7). End.
- 08 Directly under *Argenteleonora* subg. *Shira* (Section 2.9.2). End.
- 09 *Argenteleonora* sect. *Plesichia* (Section 2.9.3). End.

Alternate key (view-based): These provide alternative entry points into the key when classifying based on the three views provided by Silversaga.

100 View of Eleonora dress used: A (101), B (102), C (103)

101 View A: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Unilastica* (04).

102 View B: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Duolastica* (06)

103 View C: *Argenteleonora* subg. *Shira* (02)

Remarks: *Argenteleonora* is the *sensu stricto* genus of the family Argenteleonoridae, covering specimens with the least amount of deviation from the pattern. Silversaga cites the “classic” chemise dress³ as the inspiration for the Eleonora (Silversaga et al. 2024b).

The sleeved Eleonora dress predates the sewing pattern period; numerous instances of the dress exist that have morphology consistent with RTW, most notably a Silversaga label on the superior medial point of the dress’s dorsal interior. This label is by far the most reliable indicator of the RTW period.

The *Argenteleonora* are divided into three views by Silversaga: views A, B, and C. Refer to couplet 100 of identification key.

2.9.2 *Argenteleonora* subg. *Shira*

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Argenteleonora*.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* subg. *Shira* is distinguished from subg. *Elastica* by its shirring at the inferior portion of the bodice.

2.9.2.1 *Argenteleonora katieae*

Argenteleonora katieae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora katieae* is characterized by its fabric, a red printed fabric featuring non-circular flowers with petals that fan out in a limited arc; typically a half-circle.

Etymology: From *Katie* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Weyhardt 2024.1475.50* — Photograph. 3293×4940. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora katieae* wb. Katie.W., 2024. © Katie Weyhardt or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 0bfba0c217a2227ed40a63ab2d15e773566912e89eb4a021c22c221f77242780; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweyhardt5.jpg?v=1713459266>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095229/https://>

³Most likely a reference to a general category of dress, rather than a specific brand.

[//cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweychardt5.jpg?v=1713459266](https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweychardt5.jpg?v=1713459266)

Weychardt 2024.1475.77 — Photograph. 3169×4754. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora katieae* wb. Katie.W., 2024. © Katie Weychardt or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 786c8b743594b37ce2b287442923ff74700b6277053780c1c19d9069cbdf0b0; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweychardt7.jpg?v=1713459417>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095229/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweychardt7.jpg?v=1713459417>

Weychardt 2024.1475.24 — Photograph. 2997×4495. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora katieae* wb. Katie.W., 2024. © Katie Weychardt or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** ce67b0bedfe5c2edbf8b115be59266802b1dcf47b2a9db30e3473a89bd5421d0; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweychardt2.jpg?v=1713459324>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095700/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/katieweychardt2.jpg?v=1713459324>

2.9.2.2 *Argenteleonora madeleinae*

Argenteleonora madeleinae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora madeleinae* is characterized by its fabric, a vintage cotton from Lyrical Fabrics, with a white background and bouquets of red and blue flowers at random rotations.

Etymology: From *Madeleine* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Madeleine 2024.340.10805** — Photograph. 1440×1792. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinae* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2026b); **SHA2-256:** 102ed9549bd2214ed4a404706986998751cd0be593b387488db611a1f578219b; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193545/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655297862_18074848364403927_5586146526558589089_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=SB6is5KpMFQQ7kNvwEOvPOu&nc_oc=AdoBuSZ2IqqCf-Ku3EYaAJGO0yvTZispmqIOD7mUWH4uv5SE47PrGIZ9HEdJnXGGhDM&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=npdk7WSPAvKq5rH_Irjngg&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5bp8Qhdy1sibF60jizLL_3V3CkOZSLwaTrMfbSZ3ZgsA&oe=6A1BDD9B

Madeleine 2024.340.11387 — Photograph. 1440×1792. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinae* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2026b); **SHA2-256:** a3d325313898ec193351ac55c573fd2299f9a8b11df26b74ee1474ecf4f026b1; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193547/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/656210069_18120316297615569_2707750280588918186_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=tCIvAdm10OQQ7kNvwF0Hcq5&nc_oc=Ado85zqNOuoE_WupLenD5t1JlqzrS1Pkx-B5gNAXR_xdjfobA4qJNealMs8WQbMnWM&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=npdk7WSPAvKq5rH_Irjngg&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5e4LZ7BIVe69ra3Gg-XcaeOheL4rn61KRGoA_xrSj4J_A&oe=6A1BD2F4

Madeleine 2024.340.11609 — Photograph. 1440×1792. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinae* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2026b); **SHA2-256:** c9936ca24532035704f78bfdbe2bd99ca5e19224fa801768ae86fd901f5219e5; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193549/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/654946466_18094930667018742_8701739205467374612_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=yJp259spVMMQ7kNvwFg3rPl&nc_oc=AdpYioIc0_EZog3LddefhNE_IZ5kYIRnEW1ye1i6uOjJy9oazlcHqaYrby3KjePOYo&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=npdk7WSPAvKq5rH_Irjngg&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7lyf6Hknr61wtVAu_AW5zHvt6Krx3CANmfmx_XS8GKA&oe=6A1BBCFE

Madeleine 2024.340.17309 — Photograph. 1440×1792. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinae* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2026b); **SHA2-256:** 54af3d73519629f19e109743abd839169ccc9ea89dbee3d214ce628e8026368c; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193629/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/670297470_18519786919074146_5121532298317872402_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=e92hKdzTGf0Q7kNvwHuUZud&nc_oc=Adp1B9sio72WpDndyPXUSCfN7YUvXb1b7NZ5tTCIGk57V82FkiKR1ltbp41K3D6qAro&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=npdk7WSPAvKq5rH_Irjngg&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5vIsEiAVMnm9T5UGHyj6ytOPsCLEQHs70PG3Y3yYv6ZQ&oe=6A1BCF87

Madeleine 2024.340.19087 — Photograph. 1440×1792. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinae* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2026b); **SHA2-256:** 01ac3f29ff63a033e5018906e4c36861fda08f18

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2.9.2.3 *Argenteleonora madeleinatra*

Argenteleonora madeleinatra Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* is characterized by its fabric, a black cotton/viscose blend from Atelier Brunette.

Remarks: See Salisbury (2024a) for Salisbury's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *madeleinae* + *atra*, feminine form of Latin *āter* ("dull black").

Specimens examined

Photography conditions: Daylight; slightly cloudy. Several windmills in background. Location; Denmark; Copenhagen; unknown site.

Holotype: *Madeleine 2024.584.11008* — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. Subject standing on rocks by coast. Hair positioned laterally; very little interference with features of dress. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 2136b0efef7f30f89f85b34f9d7aeeb507add13b856b4897b9e76a60523e6408; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526192656/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655131046_17975847101844227_7927563813538374471_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=LDwe25aRNT4Q7kNvwEpLh2l&nc_oc=AdrSjflueCnnanRIEomGYug2XWqV4ZQ42WxCxSoEus_XHGpB7NvgXE67UJdYXUBz5k&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7dUDPF41cUc-qaooHp391Gvhtu0ijHUUyA0qz69ffaw&oe=6A1BDF4D

Madeleine 2024.584.11409 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. Subject standing on rocks. Left arm in pocket. Right arm on hair. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** c425a192725129bd3bd2f29388a767ce20558614f5a09161f8fcc3f5d085ae78; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526192657/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/656016281_18007827203697266_3058946831574996496_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=DFiY0agl0qIQ7kNvwHsCwGr&nc_oc=AdqduO_-wgVVHuoIHlUaev7ADwsmQtMwVz0HTX1jxHmf3y1CL-3rKR3GKi0Uuhnmarw&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7_qHNCrI3TLYH4rDa0IuY_tbGO0WjLbNXL4I9DKP0p7g&oe=6A1BCD68

Madeleine 2024.584.12336 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** a9a524c531d53780c1dc81ef569c8980bebb13c294e2f4f494043b0bac4eb54c; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526192659/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655881292_18057140708458073_7851745391782612121_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=vGk_RgPSWR0Q7kNvwFDg040&nc_oc=Adr20haTlxxHnLwduxKTI9VAVj24g42jNlnfri2vi5rwonBX6PRXCkOLTjOHnwnM-g&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7NDSO-39WYFV2akh_ZIA0Yin_p456p_slljGZbVQnjDw&oe=6A1BBE99

Madeleine 2024.584.13904 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** f51638f6e94976f5fc8f82eb7c53aaddd76aed764a57fc3acc7c920a06acc59; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526192702/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655192086_18074701919628146_8976797930973624292_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=Pujt8IQzwZEQ7kNvwFQftYb&nc_oc=Adp-GwK_SsrO3vSW662jO4zsWSWOXHovUbQSNfRRNzfl7Ocl7KmAABR-9cwxSki9q1I&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af4lFYZOo400-jGaPWA0WZVRcYcga6ECUUD81pu4umPig&oe=6A1BB8B9

Madeleine 2024.584.15198 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** f65ff0da5080a97d0916bad37d0fdc6d74759ac1d5d8d10c08398206b7ec7059; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193115/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/652735517_18021789767814853_121972676830051859_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=Cs44nv8aGpMQ7kNvwFrYZKF&nc_oc=Adr_1PLfK8nSV8a8_J9oExEpF7indEunvu

Madeleine 2024.584.15198 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** f65ff0da5080a97d0916bad37d0fdc6d74759ac1d5d8d10c08398206b7ec7059; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193115/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/652735517_18021789767814853_121972676830051859_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_ohc=Cs44nv8aGpMQ7kNvwFrYZKF&nc_oc=Adr_1PLfK8nSV8a8_J9oExEpF7indEunvu

CQcPPY53VSiUuQi66ZRY8fLmmFxbw3LPg&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5w-XR89PSWFHbJqbhudFW5YDupBgSeENUpjNe7Tj5zbQ&oe=6A1BAECF

Madeleine 2024.584.15729 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** fcc3d704b7c072a408d5d43f637f52c028d340a99a8b733e8f51175cd17763e2; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193118/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/656402224_18079350941100306_6091283585468025148_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_ohc=aiQIAzhT3IwQ7kNvWg7N207&_nc_oc=Adoi9BFjWREjBib6huhCK5Hq_BEEmCGHIg6vMvyp0t7uQHLG6a3xkeFO0C8ZBawGJu4I&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5Fp5JWOMBiqCmNSC31h0gOmiqUgnjR8S1keLhV5ncYHw&oe=6A1BD0D3

Madeleine 2024.584.16305 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 350972a22da39bfaf47a2e6718ef4eaa1c9fd2ed1ca4a6df887d4e43af5396ff; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193120/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/654093368_18075708101390524_262297275285563156_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_ohc=LGhA7RHFXg0Q7kNvwGUTA2&_nc_oc=AdqpP1A_Sa7MpSFTiid4xgACJoso_Ernk9lwJoavufabrq8CVQFJiRwbuDTPW9L3sGE&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6X5WhoIJIDzfnhaXv0IxaTV2cDrS0z5OHcB8Be74icA&oe=6A1BC9DF

Madeleine 2024.584.18040 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 53623c3bb4d70a047f215ce3881fcb46ab7bba728255397216d58020e8917164; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193211/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/657350942_18096506081283922_8137311498468398982_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_ohc=Uv2Iru5nNLAQ7kNvwGg7y8y&_nc_oc=AdqnTs_MiT6ciT9Jyr4IxvrjJBsOJmaFITei3q7_i5kvLUWm8YiMXmFofAsfzeTxGPg&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af75qTW0LyJKNa9fQzP1AEFQyB6JwFj1kAd8y_gA_qKoxw&oe=6A1BD1C7

Madeleine 2024.584.35706 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora madeleinatra* wb. Madeleine.S., 2024. © Madeleine Salisbury or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Salisbury (2024a); **SHA2-256:** cceb59af70f96002a5918a744503d1131d50f4c70f230493c30171c811519e0d; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260526193225/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/659145406_18316370815254148_560844554667036928_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_ohc=jPgByOpy4qwQ7kNvwFb7RUC&_nc_oc=AdqNi9qB0xzVD6nsKsxc1Tz8u4df-F4uQwGQCrMQ0Qohx7QcHRDHNaPdm2Sjv2OlM8&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=8V4cwcXUj0jcsKkQ-DF9ZA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6UTRP8b98vUcCA4rHTu3-19nf-pWfX_TwBohJECnrbKg&oe=6A1BAAA6

2.9.2.4 *Argenteleonora manuelae*

Argenteleonora manuelae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora manuelae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with a powder-blue background and near-photorealistic depictions of white and yellow flowers at random orientations.

Etymology: From *Manuela* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Wilkes 2024.884.25708** — Photograph. 2302×3286. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora manuelae* wb. Manuela.W., 2024. © Manuela Wilkes or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 91842f300604cc8aa397142199dc242aa0871de7bac3b8eee4bb7642fa8a55f6; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes6.jpg?v=1713456129; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095229/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes6.jpg?v=1713456129

Wilkes 2024.884.25510 — Photograph. 2658×3284. Lateral view. *Argenteleonora manuelae* wb. Manuela.W., 2024. © Manuela Wilkes or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 47e034139a0f7081317ba751d41bc86dcd0f85ce5fa80e625573db2e5b1755f2; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes5_copy.jpg?v=1713456314; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095229/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes5_copy.jpg?v=1713456314

Wilkes 2024.884.24809 — Photograph. 2646×3405. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora manuelae* wb. Manuela.W., 2024. © Manuela Wilkes or unknown photographer, all

rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 0813f65efda075c2240d94b965026ac7d059064425d24b1edda42fb166dc94fa; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes3.jpg?v=1713456102; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095229/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Manuela_Wilkes3.jpg?v=1713456102

2.9.2.5 *Argenteleonora rubra*

Argenteleonora rubra Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora rubra* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown solid red material.

Etymology: From *rubra*, feminine form of *ruber* (“red”), as McClintock has multiple *Argenteleonora* spp.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *McClintock 2024.574.400* — Photograph. 1638×2048. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora rubra* wb. Yoanna.M., 2024. © Yoanna McClintock or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 6ca2b9c3f1dd22e0dee5b5602dc1de16cf19317b8891fe688345e97a9722ec1d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock4.jpg?v=1713456020; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095231/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock4.jpg?v=1713456020

McClintock 2024.574.300 — Photograph. 1638×2048. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora rubra* wb. Yoanna.M., 2024. © Yoanna McClintock or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 579ba8e94854646f83dbc36b3a54b77482112cd135c344f2fb490e31d565e994; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock3.jpg?v=1713455994; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095707/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock3.jpg?v=1713455994

2.9.2.6 *Argenteleonora thea*

Argenteleonora thea Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora thea* is characterized by its fabric, a solid teal, and unknown material, with a diagonal grid of embossed dots that rise above the exterior side of the fabric.

Etymology: From New Latin *thea* (“tea”), from Tea Stamenkovic’s name.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Stamenkovic 2024.114.7338* — Photograph. 1619×2024. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora thea* wb. Tea.S., 2024. © Tea Stamenkovic or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** bac1f572f0976bf7a9dca31490ae6a53c314c00b89de14346285629a471c082; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic_7338.jpg?v=1713470586; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095712/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic_7338.jpg?v=1713470586

Stamenkovic 2024.114.7296 — Photograph. 1619×2024. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora thea* wb. Tea.S., 2024. © Tea Stamenkovic or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 9760fed9432849260cddbcbad4567bcd618b59214ddc94634fb8c8cf0493078dc; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic_7296.jpg?v=1713470641; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095800/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic_7296.jpg?v=1713470641

Stamenkovic 2024.114.7265 — Photograph. 1619×2024. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora thea* wb. Tea.S., 2024. © Tea Stamenkovic or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 3aa739d085d5e1365191b9a1a8bc97ea8866a1fcf0254654ae407c8a69bdab36; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic_7265.jpg?v=1713470661; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095806/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tea_Stamenkovic_7265.jpg?v=1713470661

2.9.2.7 *Argenteleonora veneta*

Argenteleonora veneta Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora veneta* is characterized by its fabric, a solid blue unknown material.

Etymology: From *veneta*, feminine form of Latin *venetus* (“sea-blue”, “blue”), as McClintock has multiple *Argenteleonora* spp.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *McClintock 2024.573.130* — Photograph. 1638×2048. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora veneta* wb. Yoanna.M., 2024. © Yoanna McClintock or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 06a3450e290adc9ce2ffa350908b514da93271c406343a74b82e6b76836a1665; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock13.jpg?v=1713455899; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095019/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock13.jpg?v=1713455899

[//cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock13.jpg?v=1713455899](https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock13.jpg?v=1713455899)

McClintock 2024.573.700 — Photograph. 1638×2048. Ventral view. *Argenteleonora veneta* wb. Yoanna.M., 2024. © Yoanna McClintock or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 165914ab08fe48cad1585fb699f459f86f0032c2ff02052e0f7c044847b0a311; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock7.jpg?v=1713455929; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095124/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock7.jpg?v=1713455929

2.9.3 *Argenteleonora* sect. *Plesichia*

Argenteleonora* section *Plesichia Lemuria, 2026; section nova

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Plesichia* is characterized by similarity to the Ischia dress from Dôen (stylized in all-caps).

Remarks: There exist significant similarities between the Argenteleonoridae, the Milalilianidae (Liliana dress, MilaOnni), and the Donischidae (Ischia dress, Dôen, ready-to-wear). The three dresses most likely obtained their similarity through convergent evolution or the trends at the time the designs were first created. No evidence of direct copyright infringement exists; and in accordance with the presumption of innocence, we operate as though no such activity has taken place.

2.9.4 *Argenteleonora* subg. *Elastica*

Argenteleonora* subgenus *Elastica Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Argenteleonora*.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* subg. *Elastica* is distinguished from subg. *Shira* by its lack of shirring at the inferior portion of the bodice.

Identification key: Start at couplet 3 of *Argenteleonora* key.

2.9.5 *Argenteleonora* sect. *Unilastica*

Argenteleonora* section *Unilastica Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Argenteleonora* subg. *Elastica*.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Unilastica* is characterized by two elastic channels inferior to the bust, and phylogenetically, origin from View A of the Eleonora dress.

2.9.6 *Argenteleonora* sect. *Duolastica*

Argenteleonora* section *Duolastica Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Argenteleonora* subg. *Elastica*.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* sect. *Duolastica* is characterized by two elastic channels inferior to the bust, and phylogenetically, origin from View B of the Eleonora dress.

2.9.6.1 *Argenteleonora* *bethanae*

Argenteleonora* *bethanae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* *bethanae* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton dimity lawn from Lyrical Fabrics, dyed off-white with tea.

Remarks: Bethany made the dress in size EU 38 (US 8, UK 10). She cut two skirt panels at the full width of the fabric (55 in; ~139.7 cm), as opposed to the four panels specified by the pattern (Bethany.L. 2025b, Eleonora Dress).

Tea fabric. In April 2024, Bethany dyed *Argenteleonora* *bethanae* in tea to diminish its fabric's bright white color to a slight off-white brown. (Bethany.L. 2025a).

Bethany used 114 packets of English Breakfast black tea from Benner Tea Co, placed in a pot with 3.8 liters of water. Black tea most likely from leaves of *Camellia sinensis* (L.) Kuntze. Tea bags were gradually added to the boiling water, which was steeped for 15 minutes with occasional stirring. A strainer was then used to remove the tea bags. The tea was strained through scrap fabric into a large bowl. Bethany recommends a loosely woven fabric such as cheesecloth for straining, and the use of a stainless steel bowl to prevent tea stains. (Bethany.L. 2025a).

Argenteleonora *bethanae* was submerged in a sink with 15 liters of hot water, mixed with five cups (est. 1182.941 ml) of white vinegar, a roughly 15:1 hot water–vinegar ratio (Bethany.L. 2025a), which diverged from the 1:4 ratio recommended by Koshimizu (2018).

The tea was then poured into a plastic tub, then diluted with three pots (est. 12 liters; fill height unknown) of water. *Argenteleonora* *bethanae* was then submerged in the tea. It was pushed deeper into the water to remove air bubbles and swirled continuously for 15 minutes to ensure even dispersion of the tea dye across the dress. The dress was then held over a sink and rinsed with cool water until the water ran clear. (Bethany.L. 2025a).

In Koshimizu (2018), which Bethany cites, the fabric was soaked in a 1:2 ratio of cold water–vinegar and then rinsed. However, Bethany skipped this step due to insufficient vinegar. The dress was then squeezed and placed on a plastic hanger to dry. The dress was then placed in

a gentle wash cycle with a mild detergent and dried in a dryer (Bethany.L. 2025a).

Bethany wrote her own blog post detailing the process (Bethany.L. 2025a), and cited a blog post from the *Woodlark Blog* (Koshimizu 2018). See also her Instagram post at Bethany.L. (2024a).

The change in color of the fabric is perhaps the first example of anagenesis in the LCT-01.

Varieties:

- *Argenteleonorora bethanae* var. *brunathea* — type variety. From Medieval Latin *bruna* (“brown”) + New Latin *thea* (“tea”).
- †*Argenteleonorora bethanae* var. *athea* — pre-dyed variant. From Greek *a-* (“no”) + New Latin *thea* (“tea”). Rendered extinct by anagenesis into var. *brunathea* as documented in Bethany.L. (2025a).

Etymology: From *Bethany* + *-ae*, Latin feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Bethany 108.5716* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Daytime lighting. Subject standing indoors, window to her right. Partially in shadow. Subject’s arms fully adducted, with her right foot stretched out. Hair positioned ventrally. *Argenteleonorora bethanae* var. *athea* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** a1aef642f44c5bfb6f8c00a6911e7a32e5df31252e71fd7a4330e4edf90ddf2; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Bethany_Routamaa.jpg?v=1713471765; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095302/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Bethany_Routamaa.jpg?v=1713471765

Bethany 108.1798 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Dorsal view. Daytime lighting. Subject standing indoors, same room as *Bethany 108.5716*, shadow slightly larger. Hair tied and positioned dorsally, running laterally across right scapula. Subject’s right arm adducted. EXIF metadata stripped. *Argenteleonorora bethanae* var. *athea* wb. Bethany.L., 2025. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 06ea6f6c2a8b08aebdc8475aa43da82767211842ac11b0162b3bba8b9ccc204f; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Bethany_Routamaa2.jpg?v=1713471798; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095308/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Bethany_Routamaa2.jpg?v=1713471798

Bethany 108.1763 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Ventral view, white wall. Apparent light source from subject’s

right. Truncated view; subject’s head not shown. EXIF metadata stripped. *Argenteleonorora bethanae* var. *athea* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024b); **SHA2-256:** 9d5ed53970c97a161cdcc7835b1ed80b62a6aac2ae4723c22f9d84e92caaf77; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Bethany_Routamaa4.jpg?v=1713471720; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095300/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Bethany_Routamaa4.jpg?v=1713471720

Bethany 108.1902 — Photograph. 1200×1600. Ventral view, outdoor lighting. Subject’s arms fully adducted. Truncated view; area of head superior to lips not shown. EXIF metadata stripped. Last-Modified header 2024-04-19. “Encoded with Blend=1 downsampling” Filename floral-dress-after-dyeing-with-tea.jpg. EXIF metadata stripped. *Argenteleonorora bethanae* var. *brunathea* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. **Page:** Bethany.L. (2025a) **SHA2-256:** 4ae10225373623f7c9235d127f345a7395b5a5fd16c0cd5f56e967e49a34fa43 **Original:** <https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/floral-dress-after-dyeing-with-tea.jpg>; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260409051700/https://www.bethanylynnemakes.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/floral-dress-after-dyeing-with-tea.jpg>

2.9.6.2 *Argenteleonorora patriciae*

Argenteleonorora patriciae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonorora patriciae* is characterized by its black rayon crepe fabric, an Indian block print in black, cream, gold taupe, and Irish green. Bodice lengthened by 2 in (5.08 cm) and neckline raised by 1 in (2.54 cm).

Etymology: From *Patricia* + *-ae*, Latin feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Rainey 17.15090* — Photograph. 3024×4032 *Argenteleonorora patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** f9429b926183edb3f89a87181d688a9dd72912cb301f55a22303ccd364e49ce5; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEi1dHKRkxf8cgUtT2Yvqy3nJ_drE48a6FTmAmS9YHGYq5jERJ1o4EOMar29q8ibmHuyVICN_ZxXDbYrZEC4lmGpK0KbsJi6XzP-F_sIH2K-pPzam5PmLKh88OgyW59mFtLN5ugHjKYnz8srx7Wsq8MtY5PII9PfiYc_yFqfBWWOMvEbmp1KO3y9r5R478U3/s0/Picture%201.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070218/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEi1dHKRkxf8cgUtT2Yvqy3nJ_drE48a6FTmAmS9YHGYq5jERJ1o4EOMar29q8ibmHuyVICN_ZxXDbYrZEC4lmGpK0KbsJi6XzP-F_sIH2K-pPzam5PmLKh88OgyW59mFtLN5ugHjKYnz8srx7Wsq8MtY5PII9PfiYc_yFqfBWWOMvEbmp1KO3y9r5R478U3/s0/Picture%201.jpg=s0?imgmax=0

Yq5jERJ1o4EOMar29q8ibmHuyVICN_ZxXDbYrZEC4lmGpK0KbsJi6XzP-F_sIH2K-pPzam5PmLKh88OgyW59mFTLN5ugHjKYnz8srX7Wsq8MtY5PII9PfiYc_yFqfBWWOMvEbmP1KO3y9r5R478U3/s0/Picture%201.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.21134 — Photograph. 3024×4032 *Argenteleonorina patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** 9c0eba94ee320e8d77cf71881bdd08958d0eb60263d861a11adb2edb7fac7f9e; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiJgyEfoyu0LV2ynuIzvePtJ8E_O8686movABhyphenhyphenY3E7gsy59uYiPzEIHfJekIU9TpoRXZaPfxrv12CU-10iNqyn5fWfM5odbtDMY3Bdb9j1u8uWafBS_vjdd0yXHLipqarYtTysw9rxsbLDNOaC1ZcSrD9Jam7QyPi5AU1gr0QlhPrB4mtQ-F1-mWLBd/s0/Picture%202.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070227/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiJgyEfoyu0LV2ynuIzvePtJ8E_O8686movABhyphenhyphenY3E7gsy59uYiPzEIHfJekIU9TpoRXZaPfxrv12CU-10iNqyn5fWfM5odbtDMY3Bdb9j1u8uWafBS_vjdd0yXHLipqarYtTysw9rxsbLDNOaC1ZcSrD9Jam7QyPi5AU1gr0QlhPrB4mtQ-F1-mWLBd/s0/Picture%202.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.21167 — Photograph. 3024×4032 *Argenteleonorina patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** ff5dda3d4bee5c846664cdf790278d490b2b4b63e84e3d0a1da1c53ae92f939a; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgl7xEShXAH_esazviAjnH5Q3x6yc4aGuHpMD05GaDYQ4cuoI4RYPhIl6F5HVAhQky82YuOeOMcukTjjN1wvdmB_Qhbg16I5vEY_SYjFI7uW3B0AHojxjwoQnsEOMxtxEz10jW76UrDwf8r6rQV5ZCFN0A4QSSRPW5yG2umxcdDix9WRRDvIrSOvsrMHboL/s0/Picture%204.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070230/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgl7xEShXAH_esazviAjnH5Q3x6yc4aGuHpMD05GaDYQ4cuoI4RYPhIl6F5HVAhQky82YuOeOMcukTjjN1wvdmB_Qhbg16I5vEY_SYjFI7uW3B0AHojxjwoQnsEOMxtxEz10jW76UrDwf8r6rQV5ZCFN0A4QSSRPW5yG2umxcdDix9WRRDvIrSOvsrMHboL/s0/Picture%204.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.21190 — Photograph. 3024×4032 *Argenteleonorina patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** 6412a063856f56bf77d12e9f312a7da7a3185815534a8a800f95f80b44ff5595; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiHuYQ9l6wRwPWS9hn5-4ucLrU6KeqZhyphenhyphenC31nl03HMF0uvN_6PzjWsjqPuPHrjX00tpmrePsOSvlpAUTrNkVQ47m1gt-MofkepTqFGk_1WkYLNrg2p_C_Ufs0DBtx3iNETiG8jkWjzjG-shlWpIN6t_fuQvwBi0TANf3J1R3ynphEQc9n6EdbRdb9dhNw/s0/Picture%205.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

05.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070158/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiHuYQ9l6wRwPWS9hn5-4ucLrU6KeqZhyphenhyphenC31nl03HMF0uvN_6PzjWsjqPuPHrjX00tpmrePsOSvlpAUTrNkVQ47m1gt-MofkepTqFGk_1WkYLNrg2p_C_Ufs0DBtx3iNETiG8jkWjzjG-shlWpIN6t_fuQvwBi0TANf3J1R3ynphEQc9n6EdbRdb9dhNw/s0/Picture%205.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.25400 — Photograph. 3024×4032 *Argenteleonorina patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** 2e8f2d6c921bc8eb5bcfb3f670c4351100460134350ae5566b56214f6fb431d8; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgXOx7LbOzdD139kTiyH6x0TyAd3dwaaxeGcqit5NGaTbaEe6q_m0Ew473VVvMGVE9mlJdfhCCqyY2rY4r-juqkRasD3ZBCH6PYjObI5eXAI8egaR-sf_jgtfq1615VYTApMjRwRkiUrmaZ-LPIC5BhIV89M97jGGj1ZbQPXr33dp99by_KIunzBEQyq-t/s0/Picture%206.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070147/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgXOx7LbOzdD139kTiyH6x0TyAd3dwaaxeGcqit5NGaTbaEe6q_m0Ew473VVvMGVE9mlJdfhCCqyY2rY4r-juqkRasD3ZBCH6PYjObI5eXAI8egaR-sf_jgtfq1615VYTApMjRwRkiUrmaZ-LPIC5BhIV89M97jGGj1ZbQPXr33dp99by_KIunzBEQyq-t/s0/Picture%206.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.25463 — Photograph. 3024×4032. *Argenteleonorina patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** e1d5f12b877d7337a0e92fba7bef1970900556968f6e330ebdec98766bc733ec; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgtOVXtLRLIKfMqa5U0nwZ8SOPzKqj7IXUZ6jtIXSmksHBhZxqUxeQWz0C7GRReVb0T1DhFv8Zl9c1PmpvaHkqc55gl3b3I0367mME_cIIGv-nGTWq8LFHwtsH3SBynIBlMy-0ii-Pz5C-L50cUbwHqeYlWAvxi6gxkQEMos0ROdTM-VG7NVmfM4_N1rxKwe/s0/Picture%207.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070122/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgtOVXtLRLIKfMqa5U0nwZ8SOPzKqj7IXUZ6jtIXSmksHBhZxqUxeQWz0C7GRReVb0T1DhFv8Zl9c1PmpvaHkqc55gl3b3I0367mME_cIIGv-nGTWq8LFHwtsH3SBynIBlMy-0ii-Pz5C-L50cUbwHqeYlWAvxi6gxkQEMos0ROdTM-VG7NVmfM4_N1rxKwe/s0/Picture%207.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.27101 — Photograph. 3024×4032. *Argenteleonorina patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** f89399a53bc32584ab42fdf85b47753c5cdfb121b9b87822be1bdf055a1a327e; **Original:** <https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEibdvEZ6RwnNIEfxHqtzxaY6yRXXiQ8fv6104aCXFv515C14eZv-PmUEHcj0eIwMBy8Q>

m45wUG9PuBQz4iFJEFraBhdTFa3eLULi8GKV-Nd7-XPTqrbhgHoncEkrLiSpuks7IvDxOAxhVUCFpudbopuU5qn05i3QPivgHuVmL_WjZtfHe0e8Z3GJlX1QXQm/s0/Picture%2013.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409070048/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEibdvEZ6RwnNIEfxHqtzxaY6yRXXiQ8fv6104aCXFv515Cl4eZv-PmUEHcj0eIWmBy8Qm45wUG9PuBQz4iFJEFraBhdTFa3eLULi8GKV-Nd7-XPTqrbhgHoncEkrLiSpuks7IvDxOAxhVUCFpudbopuU5qn05i3QPivgHuVmL_WjZtfHe0e8Z3GJlX1QXQm/s0/Picture%2013.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.27161 — Photograph. 3024×4032. *Argenteleonora patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** da641328888bb56232c686852c6657e5c63bbc39306cb389a63e0ae5c6f02cf3; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgOADu0sRh_zt8JzZ3U9FiM0VZWDNpDOT9rqGlv-PUV8EuNmLjgnmets4eZfllKD-H1naUZogJ1kOpfafs8mgUSS0sVZSRB2qilfG0roru6qpvxmtz6Q25QB9pzYxi_6mKkNillius3YYk5mABTT_0ANuHG3EtV0x56cScYK0cTnrKAHpqbDqQVQaUPRQOLY/s0/Picture%2015.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgOADu0sRh_zt8JzZ3U9FiM0VZWDNpDOT9rqGlv-PUV8EuNmLjgnmets4eZfllKD-H1naUZogJ1kOpfafs8mgUSS0sVZSRB2qilfG0roru6qpvxmtz6Q25QB9pzYxi_6mKkNillius3YYk5mABTT_0ANuHG3EtV0x56cScYK0cTnrKAHpqbDqQVQaUPRQOLY/s0/Picture%2015.jpg%3Ds0?imgmax=0;

Rainey 17.30145 — Photograph. 3024×4032. *Argenteleonora patriciae* wb. Patricia.R., 2024. © Patricia Rainey or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Rainey (2025); **SHA2-256:** d2eb52cfcecd175041e4bd9ee8d7a7af53ea2ba7fcf53deb9f731fb1d179a5b8; **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgD28QTOkpyC2aCMkxtSbm2Mg1GqVFZntCFZFRQ3N2S6xZVjDjWjIhd2XP_ifCFRbnSpIoJeoSvHrOLcIrdruInUDQiCpMzTQ5skfupdCQAumI4DiuLnWGM0khMoV__mCSioPsv0ugleV9bk4l_BGfvDTH-nMvY2w5_SST0F3cyLyfjZeugMTrzza8mkye/s0/Picture%2016.jpg=s0?imgmax=0; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260409065957/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgD28QTOkpyC2aCMkxtSbm2Mg1GqVFZntCFZFRQ3N2S6xZVjDjWjIhd2XP_ifCFRbnSpIoJeoSvHrOLcIrdruInUDQiCpMzTQ5skfupdCQAumI4DiuLnWGM0khMoV__mCSioPsv0ugleV9bk4l_BGfvDTH-nMvY2w5_SST0F3cyLyfjZeugMTrzza8mkye/s0/Picture%2016.jpg=s0?imgmax=0;

2.9.7 *Argenteleonora* subsect. *Duonoda*

Argenteleonora subsection *Duonoda* Lemuria, 2026; subsectio nova

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora* subsect. *Duonoda* is characterized by the presence of two ventral medial ties on both elastic channels.

Etymology: From *duo* (“two”) + *noda*, pseudo-Latin feminine form of *nodus* (“knot”), altered as *nodus* is grammatically masculine, while *Argenteleonora* is grammatically feminine.

2.9.7.1 *Argenteleonora candida*

Argenteleonora candida Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Argenteleonora candida* is characterized by its white color, and a Silversaga label on the superior medial point of its dorsal interior surface.

Remarks: The placement of *Argenteleonora candida* is certain within *Argenteleonora*, while infrageneric placement is uncertain. *A. candida* is one of the ready-to-wear species of *Argenteleonora*. As such, there exist two phylogenetic origins for an *Argenteleonora* species: either sewn at home from the pattern, or sewn by the Estonian atelier.

Etymology: From Latin *candida*, feminine form of *candidus* (“white, shining white”), from the dress’s solid white color.

Synonyms: In older documents, *Ae. candiga* Lemuria, 2026; due to misremembered terms.

Subspecies:

- *Ae. c. jessicae* Lemuria, 2026; subsp. nov.
- *Ae. c. natalia* Lemuria, 2026; subsp. nov.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Silversaga 2022.58.7180*⁴ — Photograph. 2592×3888. Indoor lighting conditions, white background. Likely studio conditions. Subject facing to the right (from camera perspective). Hair positioned both ventrally and dorsally, terminating inferior to inferior elastic channel. Left hand in front. Right hand on dorsal surface inferior to inferior elastic channel. *Argenteleonora candida natalia* wb. Natalia, 2022. © Jessica Silversaga, 2022, all rights reserved **Page:** **SHA2-256:** 4600a3561a53fc6c79bf64911f943efd588921ec255c9b07b3128ed2405a2ab2; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/products/SilversagaSS2022_58.jpg?v=1649342524; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260416202701/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/products/SilversagaSS2022_58.jpg?v=1649342524;

2.10 Phylum Scapunatoria

Scapunatoria Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

⁴7180 is a randomly-generated number for this holotype.

We refine the description first provided in Lemuria (2026a).

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the kingdom Abtruncusa.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, Scapunatoria is characterized by the exposure of at least one shoulder.

2.11 Subphylum Scapamanica

Scapamanica Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the phylum Scapunatoria.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, Scapamanica is characterized by the presence of at least one strap worn superior to the scapula. It is distinguished from Umerostentida by the absence of shoulder sleeves.

2.12 Class Helistola

Helistola Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

We refine the description first provided in Lemuria (2026a).

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the subphylum Scapamanica.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, Helistola is characterized by the presence of bilateral shoulder straps, the exposure of both shoulders, and the lack of sleeves lateral to the arm.

Etymology: From Ancient Greek ἥλιος (*hēlios*, “sun”) + Latin *stola* (“clothing; long dress; stole”).

2.13 Clade Heltruettia

Heltruettia Lemuria, 2026; cladus novus

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the class Helistola.

Description: No closure. Bilateral single straps, not crossing. Lack of ventral medial button row. Gathers/ruffles on bodice and straps. Straight hem, no slits, narrow straps, likely adjustable through neckline elastic channels. Ventral ribbons on neckline and bodice-skirt seam at waist. Square neckline with slightly curved corners. Lack of darts on bodice.

Phylogenetically and cladistically, Heltruettia is the clade that contains both Heleonoridae and Truettidae (unpublished).

Remarks: There exists the potential that the Heltruettia may soon grow to encompass dresses designed in line with the cottagecore aesthetic. However, the LCT-01 uses physical morphology as its primary criteria, as opposed to the intended aesthetic and subculture of a garment.

2.14 Family Heleonoridae

Heleonoridae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the superfamily Heltruettoidea.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Heleonora* is characterized by origin from the Sleeveless Eleonora dress pattern by Jessica Silversaga, and phenetically, by resemblance to the Argenteleonoridae and a lack of sleeves; and from Truettidae by the presence of waist shirring, invariably absent within Truettidae, and one elastic channel as opposed to the invariable 2. Many Heleonoridae spp. often share similarities to the Truett.

Etymology: Portmanteau of *Helistola* and *Eleonora*.

Type genus: *Heleonora*

2.14.1 Genus Heleonora

Heleonora Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in the family Heleonoridae.

Remarks: *Heleonora* was the first taxon in the LCT-01 to use infrageneric ranks. It uses the same high-level infrageneric structure as *Argenteleonora* (Section 2.9.1).

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Heleonora* is the *sensu stricto* genus of the Heleonoridae, characterized by origin from the Sleeveless Eleonora dress pattern by Jessica Silversaga, and phenetically, by resemblance to the Argenteleonoridae and a lack of sleeves; without significant divergence from the pattern.

Etymology: Portmanteau of *Helistola* + *Eleonora*.

Distribution: Worldwide. Significant primary material on the Instagram tags SleevelessEleonoraDressPattern, and through typos, SleevelessEleanorDressPattern (note the A instead of O). EleonoraDressPattern also contains specimens from both *Heleonora* and *Argenteleonora*.

Type species: *Heleonora beatricae*

2.14.2 Heleonora subg. Shira

Heleonora subgenus Shira Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Phenetically, *Heleonora* subg. *Shira* is characterized by either three or more elastic channels or shirring on the interelastic fabric.

Etymology: *Shira* is a pseudo-Latin form of English *shirr*.

Type species: *Heleonora beatricae*

2.14.2.1 *Heleonora anjae*

Heleonora anjae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora anjae* is characterized by its cotton fabric, with a floral handblock print, consisting of blue and pink flowers on a white background, with blue ferns in a curled shape.

Remarks: See Anja.S. (2024) for Anja's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Anja* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken outdoors in a natural environment, with a consistently shallow depth of field rendering the background out of focus.

Holotype: *Anja 930.1871* — Photograph. 1080×1620. Ventral view. Subject's head tilted slightly to right. Subject's left arm extended outward out of frame. Right arm holding wooden fence pole. *Heleonora anjae* wb. Anja.S., 2024. © Anja Scheithauer or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** cfbf249735dc7e95b6bd4f5d1f5acc753b7852bf74e1504450285878030da71; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Anja_Scheithauer2.jpg?v=1720291725; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171058/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Anja_Scheithauer2.jpg?v=1720291725

Anja 930.1724 — Photograph. 1080×1620. Ventral view. Subject facing to her left. Left arm fully adducted. Right arm not visible. Daisies (*Bellis perennis* L.) visible near subject. *Heleonora anjae* wb. Anja.S., 2024. © Anja Scheithauer or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 52c1bce172348d12f1559de86ed9662dc3e003135e7ef588ce07fa370dabdb33; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Anja_Scheithauer8.jpg?v=1720291724; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171236/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Anja_Scheithauer8.jpg?v=1720291724

2.14.2.2 *Heleonora beatricae*

Heleonora beatricae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora beatricae* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton duvet cover, with a floral print consisting of floral shapes in white against a light blue background. Size 42 C-E cup; bodice 3 cm longer.

Remarks: See Beatrice.F. (2024) for Beatrice's original Instagram post. A diagram of *H. beatricae* is available in SVG

form, which is used to establish terminology for *Heleonora*-specific anatomy. See `Beatrice_210.1651.annot.svg`.

Etymology: From *Beatrice* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in bright sunny conditions outdoors, with the sun casting a shadow at roughly ~200° azimuth (see Section 4.2 for background information).

Based on self-disclosed location in post: Sweden: Småland, Jönköping County, Bottnaryd. No GPS coordinates known.

Holotype: *Beatrice 210.1631* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral zoomed-out view. Subject facing forward. Both arms in bilateral pockets. *Heleonora beatricae* wb. Beatrice.F., 2024. © Beatrice Fletcher or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 52713bac98440233620dc64800dc05459ddb6af333952c459f0a83ba84310402; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Beatrice_Fletcher3.heic?v=1720291673; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100107/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Beatrice_Fletcher3.heic?v=1720291673

Beatrice 210.1651 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Closer ventral view. Subject facing forward, slightly leaning to left. Both arms in bilateral pockets. *Heleonora beatricae* wb. Beatrice.F., 2024. © Beatrice Fletcher or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 883570d98927a3cbf540d6c29bbc307062ab73da1041794ad9d2321f889884; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Beatrice_Fletcher4.heic?v=1720291673; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100108/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Beatrice_Fletcher4.heic?v=1720291673

2.14.2.3 *Heleonora blantonina*

Heleonora blantonina Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora blantonina* is characterized by its fabric, a solid light pink seersucker, with a subtle horizontal pattern consisting of plain flat areas with slight shirring/gathering in-between, purchased from Hobby Lobby at US\$3/yd.

Etymology: From *Blanton* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken by Blanton's niece, Hannah Dennis (Hannah.Den.), in a variety of conditions, all outdoors. There exist five distinct

environments, Env1 to Env5. Blanton's hair is short, terminating around the level of the chin; and thus, the neckline is almost never occluded by the hair. **Env1.** Walkway with concrete and brick flooring. Shallow depth of field with buildings and water tower in background. **Env2.** Brick wall with dense vegetation. Shallow depth of field. **Env3.** Brick wall with two black windows/doors barely visible at edge of frame. **Env4.** Grass surface near walkway with copper-colored building and black doors in background. **Env5.** Possibly a marina. Boats and apartment complexes in background; very possibly Florida. Blanton has not explicitly disclosed her state or country in her Instagram post.

We also note that the similarity in the design of the railing in environments 1 and 5 suggest that the photographs were taken within the same general area (in a cluster of 1km at most.). No geographic EXIF metadata, consistent with Instagram EXIF purging.

Holotype: *Blanton 2024.433.46636* — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. Environment 1. Subject's left arm adducted. Right arm extending leftward onto skirt, holding portion of it. *Heleonora blantonina* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis,2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** f770f5492d480c7d45058df43b2708da5a2cf6a6042c54822df3ed8fb7c5044b; **IA:** [https://web.archive.org/web/20260504215831/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/651079589_17981392790988173_7238665911249046636_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=107&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTE5Mjg2MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D&nc_ohc=ha9KCR3_9EgQ7kNvwEtDemU&nc_oc=AdoWmI9tJswPhirlyU9TufT60TigQoIFoULYzL7zxmheJ55Qt9L0d3k6kME2KnyD-s&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmqo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5Z_7Y1UoFcPlCdVFSVtFoKRJvddjBcWvUyOu1LSMwCw&oe=69FEEC4B](https://web.archive.org/web/20260504215831/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/651079589_17981392790988173_7238665911249046636_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=107&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTE5Mjg2MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D&nc_ohc=ha9KCR3_9EgQ7kNvwEtDemU&nc_oc=AdoWmI9tJswPhirlyU9TufT60TigQoIFoULYzL7zxmheJ55Qt9L0d3k6kME2KnyD-s&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmqo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5Z_7Y1UoFcPlCdVFSVtFoKRJvddjBcWvUyOu1LSMwCw&oe=69FEEC4B)

Blanton 2024.433.32667 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Right lateral view. Environment 2. Subject facing downward. Left arm holding onto skirt. Right arm occluded by body. *Heleonora blantonina* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis,2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** 19249b85bc1c3c794de9af3e5a8bf056b8999f3c00451a4dae792b4a5052e3aa; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220022/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655610868_18092356916330508_8540628614448032667_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=105&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTE3NTg2MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D&nc_ohc=gjGr4zFG6MwQ7kNvwGmgv2x&nc_oc=AdpW4otU7R13pIGxys-qYPJ2LD3JR2W6xfauaT0nxzXnHMXH4zo5R1DejhJ0RFVOW4&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmqo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6FJ3ftKjzjDHL3D-deUTPYHMQ8q2C8HvtlK0DqVftu1w&oe=69FEF438

Blanton 2024.433.69846 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Right lateral view. Environment 2. Subject facing slightly to left, forward. *Heleonora blantonina* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis,2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** 80b796757ffad05266e9ec52f184d7807c8444cd c9550656c5930feec6231ea3; **IA:** [https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220023/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/669550353_18215544754320906_110498988008769846_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTEyOTU0MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D&nc_ohc=U9jxoMCgLy4Q7kNvwH3SVso&nc_oc=AdphDlV4XPQuC4Bx3QAfTvcvPTWvFsbk2dfdrduDGKXj1_jY7xtLOPZFzRyNz3V5qQ&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmqo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6F3Zhh-PbW6-qh1DtTVb-PHFxiL0bFLEEMW0PDX3Wvzg&oe=69FEF8A1](https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220023/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/669550353_18215544754320906_110498988008769846_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTEyOTU0MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D&nc_ohc=U9jxoMCgLy4Q7kNvwH3SVso&nc_oc=AdphDlV4XPQuC4Bx3QAfTvcvPTWvFsbk2dfdrduDGKXj1_jY7xtLOPZFzRyNz3V5qQ&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmqo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6F3Zhh-PbW6-qh1DtTVb-PHFxiL0bFLEEMW0PDX3Wvzg&oe=69FEF8A1)

Blanton 2024.433.79988 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Dorsal view. Environment 1. Left arm extending outward, holding skirt. Right arm mostly adducted with slight extension outward. *Heleonora blantonina* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis,2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** 2f3ed759eec6563837a1e8be85b972c951497d647d3322076c4bb86ed8030b24; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220025/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655012307_18058731620698021_6573847349408379988_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=100&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTI5OTQ0Nw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0OTU0OTU0MmV%3D%3D&nc_ohc=S_OYs6mEgkUQ7kNvwGkKT4G&nc_oc=AdoBUOHdlixJ1oW_J2QsLgBlL-dlmjvKgjw3tCjVDw96AbdzAOcQL8mkdHmb3aYBNk&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmqo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6HBJKtOiCECjCd_o60dCoietjznPTRUhzjJit2C_MA&oe=69FEF060

Blanton 2024.433.14853 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. Environment 4. Left arm over face. Right arm mostly adducted. *Heleonora blantonina* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis,2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B.

(2024); **SHA2-256:** 7169cff2a6f2a4997a65fd4f011c2f25aadf978b6b13ae71c9f18e22e3f7c5e9; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220416/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/651431201_17980991465975936_7830797461430914853_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=105&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0MTg1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=utQtLwWEUXgQ7kNvwFEQAgI&nc_oc=AdrVeNcixjMCIfjKZw053Sdw0eBd3pCyiCb0bx78lAQXVh5vEoC5P5T2Mh88FG09VL0&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmQo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7yWnjILW8jT p4mOQwpCllu0b6Uj9D7rOhfL4Qcpg-8lQ&oe=69FECC29

Blanton 2024.433.40968 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Left lateral view. Environment 5. Left arm extending backward: upper arm backward, lower arm then extends forward. Right arm on railing. *Heleonora blanton* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** ab17c868d1745b098c8f8a7e1536368823ccdadb795288bcab939fca91347442; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220429/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/662341312_18368242204201797_502939237225740968_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2NzAxNzk5NTE1OA%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0MTg1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=XqXqIfjXssQQ7kNvwGTJxbV&nc_oc=AdryY5ZWS8eR7HkQg8PDxSCu67289rGhv1Wc_u9TjLPNPFbWydCuxXTVntJy9W-s848&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmQo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af6lyR-HDmhGHTlk4h9dqaxoMsPu0ja_Kh-Ejy7_wdTs9g&oe=69FECB23

Blanton 2024.433.76407 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Close dorsal view. Environment 4. Shallow depth of field. Closer camera position provides higher-resolution view of fabric. Arms mostly adducted. *Heleonora blanton* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** be15f997ae3729fc48631167b965e0e5bdf165c348f28a5b7a5357a857c67384; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220341/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/656733159_18138350659508029_7864903067687476407_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=103&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1MDg1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0MTg1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=JU7PfjUYvZsQ7kNvwGZGURw&nc_oc=Adrc_ylcPX4KY4vXkAXhp0v7rUeCtu8Qbqu-

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Blanton 2024.433.19582 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Angled ventral view. Environment 1. Subject's arms on railing. *Heleonora blanton* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** 7eed96a4e041b61a3560c884743a7c15cd5edf4c bfb35479d58ed9058d994cd; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220310/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/655019723_18011563436683653_2454417883585919582_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=102&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1MDg1Nzc2Nw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0MTg1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=D4tasegLiIQ7kNvwFBxh4L&nc_oc=Adr7r77CaVxtTmfIUWxtlRwjxK2RsoREY2PFh4OV-wuzCV6sftA8DyeV3TLbjPllidi&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmQo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7KRkVydYgyljg_GnWoouRR5ebUwwfGHX2qVwfoj-mAmw&oe=69FEE989

Blanton 2024.433.51080 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Angled ventral view. Environment 3. Subject's left arm adducted. Subject's right arm holding skirt out forward. *Heleonora blanton* wb. Becky.L.B., 2024. © Becky Lynch Blanton and her niece, Hannah Dennis, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Becky.L.B. (2024); **SHA2-256:** 2bbd364559c001a26fc235c774244e295578a7627aaa1a137839b4fd7f430c15; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260504220241/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/657348192_18221685520314287_2072022463349951080_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=MzQyNzE4NzQ2Njk1OTIzODcxNA%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjE0NDI0MTg1MDc0MTM4NQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=q57H12qthQIQ7kNvwHDKmZ2&nc_oc=AdrR3rmezJyiosm5anW0M_y8er4rFdOT6ORWZI-FIF6Bw_n4mIMcDa1DC6RXkC6r4XI&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=oKmQo24hjHVhxILzRYJCsQ&nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af7Aon3KzM0aYsR9NZo7kZJnK1j_FsbAYW1iLWr33KI9gQ&oe=69FEFD5B

2.14.2.4 *Heleonora gabriellae*

Heleonora gabriellae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora gabriellae* is characterized by its fabric, a floral pattern with light blue flowers against a white background, described by Scollay as “thrifed bedsheets”

from Salvos Stores, an Australian chain of thrift stores (known as opportunity shops or op shops in Australia).

Remarks: For Scollay's original Instagram posts, see Scollay (2026a), a gallery of photographs; Scollay (2026b), a reel where she tries on *H. gabriellae*; and Scollay (2026c), a reel where she sews *H. gabriellae*.

Etymology: From *Gabrielle* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. Outdoors, daylight conditions.

Holotype: *Gabrielle 394.2071* — Photograph. 2667×4000. Ventral view. Hair draped ventrally, occluding left strap. Left arm adducted. Right arm holding bouquet of flowers. Subject against the light. *Heleonora gabriellae* wb. Gabrielle.Sc., 2024. © Gabrielle Scollay or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** e208a4ee05f95f2fe58059b3e655d2195fcf9208d8a9309d99168da0076b6bf4; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Gabrielle_Scollay_jpg.jpg?v=1720381421; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100730/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Gabrielle_Scollay_jpg.jpg?v=1720381421

Gabrielle 394.2049 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Angled ventral view. Focused on area around bust. *Heleonora gabriellae* wb. Gabrielle.Sc., 2024. © Gabrielle Scollay or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 25a03be39971e41e8e91912d46c3801ffffb795520926c2484fdb235129e346b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Gabrielle_Scollay2.jpg?v=1720381421; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100732/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Gabrielle_Scollay2.jpg?v=1720381421

2.14.2.5 *Heleonora garciae*

Heleonora garciae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora garciae* is characterized by

Description:

Remarks:

Etymology: From

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Garcia 290.1709* — Photograph. 2736×3648. Ventral view. Subject in possible urban environment, and in shade of vegetation based on tree-like shadow

patterns. Wind blowing to the subject's right. Hair positioned dorsally; with slight ventral spillover, obscuring left shoulder. *Heleonora garciae* wb. Stephanie.G., 2024. © Stephanie Garcia or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 27781e0ed94d748ef0239503aa1fe6af0a2724ca7d67be1eb4e5b44f76897d54; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Garcia20.jpg?v=1720291718; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100028/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Garcia20.jpg?v=1720291718

Garcia 290.1711 — Photograph. 2992×2992. Dress hanging against window. Blue flare to left of bodice, possible sun or overexposure. Instance of *Felis catus* Linnaeus, 1758 (cat) behind dress. *Heleonora garciae*. © Stephanie Garcia or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 14ef77a944aa73506b213d6d4d01056bfc8c5d1543a935f48430e09ac2d5b12e; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Garcia22.jpg?v=1720291719; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100930/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Garcia22.jpg?v=1720291719

Garcia 290.1736 — Photograph. 3000×4000. Ventral view. Subject in forest. Significant sunlight shining on subject, especially on right bust and skirt area. Subject wearing hat with morphological similarities to sombreros (no LCT-01 classification). Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring left strap. Skirt truncated out of frame. *Heleonora garciae* wb. Stephanie.G., . © Stephanie Garcia or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 2bb4734ba0390956aaae8eb5e29bf937e6292dfe3d5267018758284fd9896a23; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Garcia6.jpg?v=1720291718; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095909/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Stephanie_Garcia6.jpg?v=1720291718

2.14.2.6 *Heleonora ioanae*

Heleonora ioanae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora ioanae* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton voile from Fabricland Canada, consisting of blue floral patterns against a white background.

Remarks: See Ioana.M. (2024) for Ioana's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Ioana* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken

indoors, with multiple open windows bringing sunlight in. In the images, Ioana stands in a patch of direct sunlight.

Holotype: *Ioana 119.1048* — Photograph. 2947×3684. Ventral view. Subject's body tilted. Subject facing downward. Left arm extended out, right arm also extended out, grabbing skirt. Motion blur at hem of skirt. *Heleonora ioanae* wb. Ioana.M., 2024. © Ioana Miron or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 713958f9151fc3c00e7d41d68a03edf325fdeaf2da0209ed4e6810738368e2dc; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ioana_Miron2.jpg?v=1720291682; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260503013948/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ioana_Miron2.jpg?v=1720291682

Ioana 119.1057 — Photograph. 2801×3502. Ventral view. Subject's body mostly straight. Subject facing downward. Both arms on dorsal surface of head. *Heleonora ioanae* wb. Ioana.M., 2024. © Ioana Miron or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 3da5e78b8563bbe3a41410e498241465e37ffe88a9e36bd46c51f7e82a4aa528; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ioana_Miron3.jpg?v=1720291682; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100223/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ioana_Miron3.jpg?v=1720291682

2.14.2.7 *Heleonora jessae*

Heleonora jessae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora jessae* is characterized by its fabric, a plaid/tartan-like fabric consisting of thick blue lines, and thinner green, red, and orange lines against a white background.

Description:

Remarks: We were not able to locate Jessa's Instagram post for the dress within the four Sleeveless Eleonora Instagram posts.

Etymology: From *Jessa* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in daytime conditions in a backyard. Jessa has tattoos covering significant portions of her arms and legs, which may help in correlating her to any possible Instagram posts. The most distinctive feature is an envelope sealed with a red heart positioned medially along the right arm, possibly at the antecubital fossa⁵ Jessa's hair was mostly

⁵Better known to non-medical personnel as the general area from which blood is often drawn.

positioned ventrally and bilaterally, though her inferior-most strands on her right were medial to the right strap, reducing occlusion.

Holotype: *Jessa 157.1490* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject's arms extended outward grabbing skirt. *Heleonora jessae* wb. Jessa.J., 2024. © Jessa Jones or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 833067180a4227f0ee1acb09558c2daf507b65819925bf058c8b52da085d098f; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones2_650693fb-5b7a-46e7-8c63-ec487bb29e02.jpg?v=1720291686; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100606/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones2_650693fb-5b7a-46e7-8c63-ec487bb29e02.jpg?v=1720291686

Jessa 157.12676 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Dorsal view. Subject's arms extended outward; legs positioned and rotated as if photograph was taken during a twirl. *Heleonora jessae* wb. Jessa.J., 2024. © Jessa Jones or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** b448220751bdb1e5f639cd6cb6f2920d31fc23ab77b6e1f8b3a71980b0ff80b6; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones6.jpg?v=1720291687; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100607/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jessa_Jones6.jpg?v=1720291687

2.14.2.8 *Heleonora karecandida*

Heleonora karecandida Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora karecandida* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material from a solid white bedsheet.

Description:

Remarks: *H. karecandida* is one of Karen's two *Heleonora* spp; the other being *H. vanhoofae*. See Van Hoof (2024a) for Karen's original Instagram post. *H. karecandida* was not featured on Silversaga's testing gallery.

Etymology: Blend of *Karen* + Latin *candida*, feminine form of *candidus* ("shining white").

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in a field, in daylight conditions, with a shallow depth of field.

Holotype: *Karen 210.1439.92994* — Photograph. 1440×1800. Ventral view. Subject facing downwards. Hair positioned ventrally; significant occlusion of left strap, relatively less occlusion on right strap. Both arms adducted. *Heleonora karecandida* wb. Karen

V.H., 2024. © Karen Van Hoof or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Van Hoof (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 402137d616bfa8235873967b018b6b0bd418f952fa315dc56b3f4564bd120b77; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260508201712/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/653773839_18106517113869276_178601654437592994_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=102&ig_cache_key=MzQwNzQ2Njk5MTE2Mzg3MDIzNQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6IknBUk9VU0VMX0lURU0ueHBpZHMUMTQ0MC5zZHIucmVndWxhcl9waG90by5DMYj9&_nc_ohc=yYaxGaSkqwQ7kNvWFA4uLp&_nc_oc=AdoNGmmBOv_j9K_h07NP4lrXYJl7Tt73t5_BX7lWPS14kGchcz6PXc-bl8SUYqHJnNE&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=WegrsvC_if3z_IepqHbGvA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5VnKc87FW1G5A3gH7j68KKNsZxZqZYiVUJAmE227y5lQ&oe=6A0406BA

Karen 210.1439.71897 — Photograph. 1440×1800. Dorsal view. Subject facing forward. Hair positioned dorsally; significant occlusion of neckline. Left arm in front of her; right arm mostly adducted, holding onto skirt. *Heleonora karecandida* wb. Karen V.H., 2024. © Karen Van Hoof or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Van Hoof (2024a); **SHA2-256:** 2abf26f5823535da2f4519152bbd8740a81f738369c13c0a336880e868af18fd; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260508201709/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/653700412_18028061573796598_427100016846671897_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=MzQwNzQ2Njk5MTI2NDYwMTc2Mw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6IknBUk9VU0VMX0lURU0ueHBpZHMUMTQ0MC5zZHIucmVndWxhcl9waG90by5DMYj9&_nc_ohc=wDkAo3TpN30Q7kNvWFGHSPR&_nc_oc=AdrV9euKvDgVZxFQUE2DkiNKOBfSI0Lv kpyTTnbachVKKbWFnvj5Wa74MFdg-eLUoe8&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=WegrsvC_if3z_IepqHbGvA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5YSGAwi-cZJELYzqafiBPJMzlcZunGjNwHX1KQqDixpA&oe=6A043129

Karen 210.1439.43997 — Photograph. 1440×1796. Truncated ventral view. Hair positioned slightly dorsally; relatively little occlusion of left strap as it runs along coronal plane towards shoulder. Arms clasp together; and converge ventromedially. *Heleonora karecandida* wb. Karen V.H., 2024. © Karen Van Hoof or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Van Hoof (2024a); **SHA2-256:** cbdda809b9c834fb2213f1645bcf11635dbbafa1f51aaed5422825765cba5b0f; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260508201716/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/656334026_18080120132093671_4012967633139543997_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=109&ig_cache_key=MzQwNzQ2Njk5MDk3OTMzNTczOQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6IknBUk9VU0VMX0lURU0ueHBpZHMUMTQ0MC5zZHIucmVndWxhcl9waG90by5DMYj9&_nc_ohc=x0IY0DnvuakQ7kNvWgGuBDV&_nc_oc=Adq15Ri3a970nRYDdPYTpNf4FfOT1E5YoRQZakGBcbq2_MCSg74tq-NqBNbxgVqQA4&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=WegrsvC_if3z_IepqHbGvA&_nc_ss=7a22e&oh=00_Af5KmTnRXlJ4U6lWOWEQaIxcd7Hle4cQtDRTXtR6LmOAqw&oe=6A0409C2

Huber 2024.40553.197 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view. Entire head in frame; inferior portions of skirt out of frame. Hair positioned ventrally, occluding left strap significantly, and right strap to lesser extent. *Heleonora larissae* wb. Larissa.H., 2024. © Larissa Huber or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 3ae998174f4d83c9794d2d3dfefeb0832833b14006768a6df9dfa5f0a3ee012526; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Larissa_Huber3.jpg?v=1720291691; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/2/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Larissa_Huber3.jpg?v=1720291691

2.14.2.9 *Heleonora larissae*

Heleonora larissae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora larissae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with a white background, featuring a blue monochrome depiction of a medieval rural area, vaguely reminiscent of England. Several humans (*Homo sapiens* Linnaeus, 1758) are seen interacting with unknown animals (Animalia spp.).

Etymology: From *Larissa* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions: The saturation of the blue pattern on Larissa's dress differs between both photographs.

Holotype: **Huber 2024.40553.197** — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view. Entire head in frame; inferior portions of skirt out of frame. Hair positioned ventrally, occluding left strap significantly, and right strap to lesser extent. *Heleonora larissae* wb. Larissa.H., 2024. © Larissa Huber or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 3ae998174f4d83c9794d2d3dfefeb0832833b14006768a6df9dfa5f0a3ee012526; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Larissa_Huber3.jpg?v=1720291691; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/2/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Larissa_Huber3.jpg?v=1720291691

Huber 2024.40553.445 — Photograph. 2134×2988. Truncated ventral view. Head out of frame; inferior portions of skirt out of frame. Hair positioned ventrally, occluding left strap significantly, and right strap to lesser extent. *Heleonora larissae* wb. Larissa.H., 2024. © Larissa Huber or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 3fb789a3164bb160db11ad18cee837b86da4de2e30211b41df4f4a184f4948d4; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Larissa_Huber.jpg?v=1720291689; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/2/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Larissa_Huber.jpg?v=1720291689

2.14.2.10 *Heleonora martinae*

Heleonora martinae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora martinae* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton voile in a solid teal color, and a tiered skirt with two distinct skirt areas separated by a seam located roughly superior to the knee.

Remarks: See Garofalo (2024) for Garofalo's Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Martina* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Martina 1057.326* — Photograph. 2592×4608. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally; left strap significantly occluded, hair on right medial such that right strap is not occluded. Subject's left arms on head, right arm extending out and grabbing portion of inferior layer of skirt. *Heleonora martinae* wb. Garofalo, 2024. © Martina Garofalo or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** a9afef4253cd511a34a90e08a9ed98beff31740fdf76aad8f1296cd847cfd3cf; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Martina_Garofalo_6.jpg?v=1720291695; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260503020857/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Martina_Garofalo_6.jpg?v=1720291695

Martina 1057.118 — Photograph. 2592×4608. Angled lateral view. Subject facing camera. Skirt flaring outward in twirl-like motion. Left arm on skirt and hands located along skirt seam. *Heleonora martinae* wb. Garofalo, 2024. © Martina Garofalo or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** fc7e7d791bee0d634e75a87d8078d2164542039f5014c7ce1977f4f2c76f3cd3; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Martina_Garofalo_1.jpg?v=1720291695; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100404/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Martina_Garofalo_1.jpg?v=1720291695

2.14.2.11 *Heleonora meganae*

Heleonora meganae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora meganae* is characterized by its fabric, a linen consisting of two prints: a plaid (tartan)-like pattern on the bodice; with a vertical rectangle square plaid-like pattern on the skirt.

Etymology: From *Megan* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Megan 171.4071* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject facing downward. Hair worn laterally, and slightly ventrally; noobscuration of neckline. Shallow depth of field. Subject's arms mostly adducted. *Heleonora meganae* wb. Megan.B., 2024. © Megan Bynum or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 8d57cce69d2db026e6a7a21a939d497b11896aaaed99ce8935aba1e5cc0d3b6b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Megan_Bynum.jpg?v=1720291697; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100428/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Megan_Bynum.jpg?v=1720291697

Megan 171.4098 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject facing downward. Similar pose to *Megan 171.4071*. Shallow depth of field. Very minor out-of-frame truncation of skirt hemline on right. Subject's left arm extended outward, holding skirt. Right arm adducted. *Heleonora meganae* wb. Megan.B., 2024. © Megan Bynum or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** c2ead0e6bb186daf48fc5e90df12a701c0f32069b7f6b74211094652796f38c7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Megan_Bynum2.jpg?v=1720291697; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100829/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Megan_Bynum2.jpg?v=1720291697

2.14.2.12 *Heleonora nellia*

Heleonora nellia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora nellia* is characterized by its fabric, consisting of a pattern of randomly rotated bouquets of blue flowers spaced out in a rough diagonal square grid, and by the presence of several gathered pieces of fabric constituting a trim located inferior to the skirt hemline.

Description:

Remarks: See Colne (2024) for Nelly's original Instagram post. Silversaga did not include Nelly in her four Instagram post compilation of *Heleonora* spp.; we located the post by checking the `SleevelessEleonoraDressPattern` tag on Instagram.

Etymology: From *Nelly* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken outdoors in a grass field, with a shallow depth of field. The subject wears a hair tie made of the same fabric in both photographs; this is considered a separate taxon.

Holotype: *Nelly 233.9071* — Photograph. 3000×4000. Ventral view. Subject facing to her left. Hair worn bilaterally,

causing slight occlusion of right strap. Left strap fully visible. Subject's arms mostly adducted. *Heleonora nellia* wb. Nelly.C., 2024. © Nelly Colne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** d2b3950c36319184ea909bf88d3eb59e7b2947c2dd8b41fc23a4d37851671f12; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Nelly_Colne11.jpg?v=1720292012; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100615/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Nelly_Colne11.jpg?v=1720292012

Nelly 233.9085 — Photograph. 2627×3524. Ventral view. Hair worn bilaterally. Major occlusion of left strap, slight occlusion of right strap due to hair strands. Subject looking slightly upward to her right. Arms mostly adducted, deliberately holding out skirt. *Heleonora nellia* wb. Nelly.C., 2024. © Nelly Colne or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** dd9d50d4944641371e7220e049d796a90901c293bfd8dc2f23763e9db9d5c37; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Nelly_Colne5_a27a2593-3a57-4991-8819-696e1fa73532.jpg?v=1720292984; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100725/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Nelly_Colne5_a27a2593-3a57-4991-8819-696e1fa73532.jpg?v=1720292984

2.14.2.13 *Heleonora rimforsia*

Heleonora rimforsia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora rimforsia* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton from Italy, with a white background and a pattern of green flowers and two parallel silver lines, all running horizontally.

Remarks: Rimfors was part of the third testing group for the sleeveless Eleonora. See Rimfors (2024) for Rimfors's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Rimfors* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken outdoors in daylight. Vegetation highly saturated. Rimfors's hair was tied dorsally, using a hair clip positioned parietally; the straps were not obscured.

Holotype: *Rimfors 15.1660* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Left arm fully adducted. Right arm reaching backward, in posture resembling at ease. *Heleonora rimforsia* wb. Rimfors, 2024. © Tuss Rimfors or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 383343b7930238147ad2ca06e3e59dee8993a8b7bdec559fb567671ba3167ebf; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tuss_Rimfors.heic?v=1720291720; **IA:**

https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100536/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tuss_Rimfors.heic?v=1720291720

Rimfors 15.1710 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view focused on bodice. Subject's arms in at ease position. *Heleonora rimforsia* wb. Rimfors, 2024. © Tuss Rimfors or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 1bd85dd6679d51c2409bb562bb83f96212eaef3d496e66044a0ba7da89f8f1dd; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tuss_Rimfors7.heic?v=1720291721; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100511/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Tuss_Rimfors7.heic?v=1720291721

2.14.2.14 *Heleonora shreyae*

Heleonora shreyae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora shreyae* is characterized by its fabric, a voile from Mood Designer Fabrics, consisting of large flowers on a dark background, with a mostly dark color palette. Six shirring lines; three of them additional ones placed by Shreya 0.5cm inferior to original shir lines. Skirt flared outward to slightly higher degree than pattern.

Remarks: See Shreya and Juno (2024) for Shreya's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Shreya* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in daylight on a grass field with a stone wall in the background.

Holotype: *Shreya 59.5165* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view, slightly angled. Arms fully adducted. Shallow depth of field. *Heleonora shreyae* wb. Shreya, 2024. © Shreya or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 9fcf9592f703998480b966a3217d4eb2bfe8c49f8da04ac7d7488f893a632b0d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shreya_Eleonora_2.jpg?v=1720291714; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100217/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shreya_Eleonora_2.jpg?v=1720291714

Shreya 59.5166 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Full-body, zoomed out. Subject tilting slightly to left. Hair positioned dorsally; no occlusion of straps ventrally. Small portion of hair draped along coronal plane and landing on left strap. *Heleonora shreyae* wb. Shreya, 2024. © Shreya or unknown photographer, 2024, all

rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** d1eea0276e361b393c523ae9fade4d905983e9c9657ef9e3ca3270acd4164da2; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shreya_Eleonora_3.jpg?v=1720291714; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100230/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shreya_Eleonora_3.jpg?v=1720291714

2.14.2.15 *Heleonora vanhoofae*

Heleonora vanhoofae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora vanhoofae* is characterized by its fabric, a bedsheet made of an unknown material, with a solid light pink color.

Remarks: See Van Hoof (2024b) for Karen's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Van Hoof* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. Both photographs have differing conditions and are described separately. **Locality of both photographs.** Belgium: Flemish Community: Flemish Region: Flemish Brabant: Vilvoorde; 50.56°N, 4.25°E ± 1.1 km (inferred from Instagram posts); near Brussels.

Holotype: *Karen 209.1067* — Photograph. 2341×2926. Angled ventral view. Subject standing at double-door entrance, partially open. Subject reflected twice in both glass panels. Daylight; lights in interior of house shut off. Subject's left arm placed dorsally. Hair positioned laterally; significant occlusion of right strap. *Heleonora vanhoofae* wb. Karen V.H., 2024. © Karen Van Hoof or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 02aaafd7e4b7b3828656eb09e6f27b06c4a3dc1bf0a096b2e994e8b847595cb8; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Karen_Van_Hoof3.jpg?v=1720291688; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100526/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Karen_Van_Hoof3.jpg?v=1720291688

Karen 209.1145 — Photograph. 2095×2619. Truncated ventral view. Subject sitting on unknown white mat. Glass bottle of perfume on floor alongside multiple *Rosa* spp. in wooden basket. *Heleonora vanhoofae* wb. Karen V.H., 2024. © Karen Van Hoof or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** dec9990bd1c603cce11ef2d3e92b642de6905fdd57dca9559952a5fb81f0f99f; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Karen_Van_Hoof6.jpg?v=1720291689; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100300/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Karen_Van_Hoof6.jpg?v=1720291689

[1/0562/9375/2969/files/Karen_Van_Hoof6.jpg?v=1720291689](https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Karen_Van_Hoof6.jpg?v=1720291689)

2.14.3 *Heleonora* subg. *Elastica*

Heleonora subgenus *Elastica* Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora* subg. *Elastica* is distinguished from subg. *Shira* by the lack of shirring and the presence of elastic channels.

Etymology: Pseudo-Latin form of English *elastic*.

2.14.4 *Heleonora* sect. *Unilastica*

Heleonora section *Unilastica* Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* subg. *Elastica*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora* sect. *Unilastica* is distinguished amongst subg. *Elastica* by the presence of only one waist channel at the bodice-skirt seam.

Etymology: Blend of Latin *uni-* (“one”) + *Elastica*.

2.14.4.1 *Heleonora antigonae*

Heleonora antigonae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora antigonae* is characterized by its fabric, a solid white cotton viscose with sparsely distributed orange flowers embroidered in yarn. Size EU 38, cup C-E. Bilateral pockets absent.

Remarks: See Tsami (2024) for Antigoni's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Antigoni* (itself the modern Greek form of *Antigone*) + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in an outdoors environment, in a wide horizontal frame, significantly zoomed out. We infer a high likelihood that a tripod was used based on the consistent positioning of vegetation and background features in both images. 27 has significantly more saturated colors than 70.

Holotype: *Antigoni 2024.133.27* — Photograph. 4000×2667. Ventral view. Subject facing right. Arms mostly adducted. *Heleonora antigonae* wb. Antigoni, 2024. © Antigoni Tsami or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 97c9150f13d1535158323509cc72ccca521cf70c6e90e68ea38b642e719ad3c6; **Original:**

https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Antigoni_Tsiami3.jpg?v=1720291725; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100815/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Antigoni_Tsiami3.jpg?v=1720291725

Antigoni 2024.133.70 — Photograph. 4000×2667. Angled dorsal view. Subject looking downwards. Left arm mostly occluded by body. Right arm mostly adducted. *Heleonora antigonae* wb. Antigoni, 2024. © Antigoni Tsami or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** b45779db34e8407fb23c9a08db922088520802160cba1f48c9e7d13138bad7c5; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Antigoni_Tsiami6.jpg?v=1720291724; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100825/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Antigoni_Tsiami6.jpg?v=1720291724

2.14.4.2 *Heleonora lauralia*

Heleonora lauralia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora lauralia* is characterized by its fabric, a solid light/earthy brown lightweight cotton.

Remarks: *Laural* is not a typo. The filenames use the spelling *Eleanora* for the dress. This misspelling also consistently occurs in Stapleton's source material. See Stapleton (2024) for Stapleton's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Laural* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Stapleton 2024.905.2118** — Photograph. 1072×1600. Ventral view. Subject facing camera directly. Left arm adducted. Right hand holding basket made of unknown woven material. *Heleonora lauralia* wb. Stapleton, 2024. © Laural Stapleton or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 5c6b41063ed0057bb098e92df14d2f25991c48eea499bc8ee9a8c0cb45dca85b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/sleeveless_Eleanora__tester_Laural_Stapleton-7.jpg?v=1720291715; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100929/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/sleeveless_Eleanora__tester_Laural_Stapleton-7.jpg?v=1720291715

Stapleton 2024.905.4098 — Photograph. 1067×1600. Ventral view. Subject facing camera directly. Left arm adducted, holding skirt. Right hand extended outward towards vegetation in background. *Heleonora lauralia* wb. Stapleton, 2024. © Laural Stapleton or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al.

(2024c); **SHA2-256:** 010adb019367ddaa6597db65c24ba1e6e7e8e7900a87b38c17af4ffef03f0717; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/sleeveless_Eleanora__tester_Laural_Stapleton-5.jpg?v=1720291715; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100502/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/sleeveless_Eleanora__tester_Laural_Stapleton-5.jpg?v=1720291715

2.14.4.3 *Heleonora shannonae*

Heleonora shannonae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora shannonae* is characterized by its fabric, a dark floral print referred to as “Art Gallery Rayon Challis” from Art Gallery Fabrics, or the “Art Gallery Fabrics Trinkets Fusion Rayon Challis Fabric Flower Glory”, the Minerva product name as cited by Shannon.

Remarks: See Shannon.P. (2024) for Shannon's original Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Shannon* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in a semi-outdoors environment, against a light yellow wall, with sliding doors to the subject's left. Light flows in from the subject's right.

Holotype: **Shannon 2024.115.2775** — Photograph. 2246×2246. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally; left strap occluded, slight occlusion on right strap. Left arms extended outward grabbing skirt, right arm mostly adducted. *Heleonora shannonae* wb. Shannon.P., 2024. © Shannon or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 22087290249a15ae0fd867f4ab971216a9cf8fddf52964885754a27815191d92; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shannon_P_353d5416-64af-467d-8432-e415fa8381ca.jpg?v=1720291713; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260506080133/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shannon_P4.jpg?v=1720291714

Shannon 2024.115.3905 — Photograph. 2704×2704. Truncated ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally, less occlusion of straps as hair is positioned more medially. Arms fully adducted. Shallow depth of field. *Heleonora shannonae* wb. Shannon.P., 2024. © Shannon or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 1e36e3e8a6f54262bdad42f8c7da84d54e01098a89fceb940912990c9875a56; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shannon_P4.jpg?v=1720291714; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260506080133/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Shannon_P4.jpg?v=1720291714

2.14.5 *Heleonora* sect. *Duolastica*

Heleonora* section *Duolastica Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* subg. *Elastica*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora* sect. *Duolastica* is characterized by the presence of two elastic channels on the waist.

Etymology: *Duo*- (“two”) + *elastica* (“elastic”).

Type species:

2.14.5.1 *Heleonora alinae*

Heleonora alinae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora alinae* is characterized by its fabric, a plain white fabric made of an unknown material.

Remarks: Wegner does not appear to have any posts about *H. alinae* on her Instagram timeline. Posts from around July 2024 only include unpublished Helargemmiidae and Argenclaridae spp.

Etymology: From *Alina* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Wegner 2024.29761.50** — Photograph. 2764×3925. Ventral view. Subject facing towards right. Skirt deliberately held out using arms to showcase details. *Heleonora alinae* wb. Alina.W., 2024. © Alina Wegner or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** dbdd37f9ad212f2dde64f7765da22c0d800472d538afd32da262182abff63020; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner2.jpg?v=1720291671; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100321/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner2.jpg?v=1720291671

Wegner 2024.29761.70 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view. Left lateral edge of dress, inferior portions of skirt, and face out of frame. Compared to .50, clearer view of ventral waist channels and ventral medial ties. *Heleonora alinae* wb. Alina.W., 2024. © Alina Wegner or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 745251dcc7e5e1d2365ecb2139c227530272b8546fbb8f1b401015e78224c972; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner7.jpg?v=1720291672; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100324/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner7.jpg?v=1720291672

2.14.5.2 *Heleonora alinaebis*

Heleonora alinaebis Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora alinaebis* is characterized by its fabric, a white fabric made of an unknown material, with a subtle floral pattern consisting of light blue flowers and green stems and leaves.

Etymology: From *Alina* + *-ae*, and Latin *-bis* (“twice”), as it is Alina’s second *Heleonora* make.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Wegner 2024.376.33009** — Photograph. 3039×4032. Ventral view. Subject facing downward. Subject’s hair draped ventrally on right, obscuring strap. Arms fully adducted. *Heleonora alinaebis* wb. Alina.W., 2024. © Alina Wegner or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 339337b43e4e521c8003b3d10700916e48fd722964196ee5cef96bef11fb2b2; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner.jpg?v=1720291668; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100105/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner.jpg?v=1720291668

Wegner 2024.376.33510 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally; no occlusion of straps. Head out of frame. Inferior portion of skirt out of frame. *Heleonora alinaebis* wb. Alina.W., 2024. © Alina Wegner or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 79e337393488456120b6b4821f0f1478691eb5f2f7db1625c64952ecb4d09eee; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner2_2.jpg?v=1720291726; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100110/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Alina_Wegner2_2.jpg?v=1720291726

2.14.5.3 *Heleonora angelae*

Heleonora angelae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora angelae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with a blue floral print on a green background.

Etymology: From *Angel* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Pickard 2024.17275.200** — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject’s arms mostly adducted. Hair positioned ventrally, medial to right strap. Subject in field of yellow flowers, daylight conditions. *Heleonora angelae* wb. Angela.P., 2024. © Angela Pickard or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 9cde027b41ce14c6ba59921e7535adc8fd980c854cbc0eeaf344386d80c1df41; **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562>

[/9375/2969/files/Angela_Pickard2.jpg?v=1720291672](https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Angela_Pickard2.jpg?v=1720291672); **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100716/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Angela_Pickard2.jpg?v=1720291672

Pickard 2024.17275.600 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject's arms mostly adducted. Hair positioned mostly dorsally, with slight bilateral ventral drape causing mild occlusion of straps. Skirt intentionally flared forward. *Heleonora angelae* wb. Angela.P., 2024. © Angela Pickard or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** eb9ad694ab24b20c3b1a3834d90a23bfe1be3fe5d420fd19b318a6925d019604; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Angela_Pickard6.jpg?v=1720291671; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100726/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Angela_Pickard6.jpg?v=1720291671

2.14.5.4 *Heleonora bethanae*

Heleonora bethanae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora bethanae* is characterized by its fabric, a double gauze from Lyrical Fabrics in a solid brown/clay/terracotta color. Care must be taken to avoid confusing *H. bethanae* with *H. lauralia*; *H. bethanae* has two elastic channels, consistent with its placement in section *Duolastica*, while *H. lauralia* only has one.

Etymology: From *Bethany* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Bethany 2024.59330.400** — Photograph. 2316×3088. Truncated ventral view. Subject's hair positioned dorsally; no occlusion of neckline. *Heleonora bethanae* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 53602ffa70aa6ad2ac3e2426a81547f4976bd8e042e635441c450d4f83c07124; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/BETHANY_ROUTAMAA_4.jpg?v=1720291675; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100217/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/BETHANY_ROUTAMAA_4.jpg?v=1720291675

Bethany 2024.59330.100 — Photograph. 2796×4032. Ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally on her right, with arm reaching for chin; right strap occluded as a result. Subject underneath wooden structure with significant sun cover provided by vegetation. *Heleonora bethanae* wb. Bethany.L., 2024. © Bethany Lynne or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 8a465c1a4c2007c383ab0db112c7da9c47e6123f

0ecdff0df819f9b602e8a5b6; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/BETHANY_ROUTAMAA_1.jpg?v=1720291674; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100217/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/BETHANY_ROUTAMAA_1.jpg?v=1720291674

2.14.5.5 *Heleonora bouteillerae*

Heleonora bouteillerae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora bouteillerae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown white material with a subtle floral pattern consisting of flowers with stems reaching out in all directions, alongside individual red leaves.

Etymology: From *Bouteiller* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: **Bouteiller 2024.35611.300** — Photograph. 3982×4978. Ventral view. Subject sitting in grass field. Saturation high; grass appears to have a darker color; though it may also be the result of shade as seen in .120. Hair positioned ventrally. Arms converge medially, with hands overlaid on top of each other; left arm position occludes portions of bodice. *Heleonora bouteillerae* wb. Sarah.Bou., 2024. © Sarah Bouteiller or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** b5f230279549aca2266870267fdb419bce52c64b9887e1e555c564620fd15a4a; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Sarah_Bouteiller3.jpg?v=1720291711; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100930/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Sarah_Bouteiller3.jpg?v=1720291711

Bouteiller 2024.35611.120 — Photograph. 3993×4991. Ventral view. Subject standing in grass field. Shadow cast by subject faces photographer. Arms extended outward; hair positioned dorsally; virtually no obscuration of ventral bodice. *Heleonora bouteillerae* wb. Sarah.Bou., 2024. © Sarah Bouteiller or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 9023db2824a93252207a44e2392a0afda8b7458f2f79867f52f5e5b70275e3d7; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Sarah_Bouteiller12.jpg?v=1720291713; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095919/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Sarah_Bouteiller12.jpg?v=1720291713

2.14.5.6 *Heleonora caydenae*

Heleonora caydenae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora caydenae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material consisting of flowers on a white

background. The flowers dominate some >85% of the surface area of the fabric, and invariably contain at least five petals.

Etymology: From *Cayden* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Cayden* 2024.25677.14 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Far ventral view. Subject facing away. Hair positioned laterally; very little occlusion of neckline. *Heleonora caydenae* wb. Cayden.Na., 2024. © Cayden Naughton or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** ac2a6a6aa97ecd37566dbff23f46fd607dbf47124540a0bd8c66014b4b73c95e; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cayden_Naughton14.jpg?v=1720291678; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100423/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cayden_Naughton14.jpg?v=1720291678

Cayden 2024.25677.12 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Closer ventral view. Subject facing camera. Hair positioned laterally; slightly occluding right strap. Left strap entirely visible. Entire dress in frame. *Heleonora caydenae* wb. Cayden.Na., 2024. © Cayden Naughton or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 24d69387c6527fff75fc00c39d64b69db125d70bc832149b7fa57dcdbb4e7edc; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cayden_Naughton12.jpg?v=1720291677; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100419/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cayden_Naughton12.jpg?v=1720291677

2.14.5.7 *Heleonora cynthiae*

Heleonora cynthiae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora cynthiae* is characterized by its fabric, a mostly white background with mostly-monochrome depictions of unknown *Plantae* spp.; and a slightly saturated yellow flower, and a grid-like pattern at the hem.

Etymology: From *Cynthia* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Cynthia* 2024.194735.75 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Angled ventral view. Dress significantly flared forward. Hair not long enough to obscure any portion of bodice. Romo is likely holding a camera remote trigger device on her right arm. *Heleonora cynthiae* wb. Cynthia.R., 2024. © Cynthia Romo or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** e1383211a2e1f31da7598b211b70dfdda9925b9e9e33b5e5d1cee7252bacb40c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cynthia_Romo4.jpg?v=1720291681; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100526/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cynthia_Romo4.jpg?v=1720291681

Cynthia 2024.194735.38 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Angled ventral view. Dress significantly flared forward. Hair not long enough to obscure any portion of bodice. *Heleonora cynthiae* wb. Cynthia.R., 2024. © Cynthia Romo or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** b45bdfb2671b4686307f2f7e4f2eea5fd1bf3e8dbdda4d11206c7060c338f8af; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cynthia_Romo4.jpg?v=1720291681; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100526/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Cynthia_Romo4.jpg?v=1720291681

Diagnosis: *Heleonora jenae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with flowers on a white background. The flowers are unidentifiable, though a major accent color amongst them is pink; with equally as much green, and to a rarer extent, pale yellow.

2.14.5.8 *Heleonora jenae*

Heleonora jenae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora jenae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with flowers on a white background. The flowers are unidentifiable, though a major accent color amongst them is pink; with equally as much green, and to a rarer extent, pale yellow.

Etymology: From *Jen* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Jen* 2024.3348.119 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Inferior portions of skirt out of frame. Subject has knit jacket partially covering lower arms. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring left strap significantly. *Heleonora jenae* wb. Jen Legg, 2024. © Jen Legg or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** ebfa152582c074d0afec902dddec378e2ec8788e2506f15d61f753140e2ea389; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jen_Legg2.jpg?v=1720291683; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100536/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Jen_Legg2.jpg?v=1720291683

2.14.5.9 *Heleonora lexiae*

Heleonora lexiae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora lexiae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with a white background and flows. The flowers are arranged in bouquets tied by red ribbons, positioned in areas separated by thin grey parallel lines, that themselves surround long vine-like plant structures.

Etymology: From *Lexi* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Lexi* 2024.5853.106 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Outdoors. Subject facing to her right. Dress intentionally held forward with right arm to show case skirt and fabric. Hair short enough to not occlude dress. *Heleonora lexiae* wb. Lexi.M., 2024. © Lexi Mccartt or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** bbda8f9cb8008cb6c66bbe3d1e1f5e84d8ec3befee921a8eb4ca448096c2f1de; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lexi_Mccartt4.heic?v=1720291693; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100306/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lexi_Mccartt4.heic?v=1720291693

Lexi 2024.5853.153 — Photograph. 1080×1616. Truncated ventral view. Indoors. Apparent light source from subject's right. Subject facing forward. Arms extend outward slightly. Head out of frame. Inferior portions of skirt out of frame. *Heleonora lexiae* wb. Lexi.M., 2024. © Lexi Mccartt or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** a69783651c9fcf07bdb1acba6281c0e967120d1ff7bbba7da6d959e0c4e73907; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lexi_Mccartt7.jpg; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260520213209/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Lexi_Mccartt7.jpg

2.14.5.10 *Heleonora lizzia*

Heleonora lizzia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora lizzia* is characterized by its fabric, a cotton lawn consisting of blue, yellow, and red flowers on a white background.

Remarks: See McNally (2024) for Liz's Instagram post.

Etymology: From *Liz* + *-ia*. She uses *Lizzy* in her handle and has her account name set to *Liz*.

Specimens examined

Photography conditions. The photographs were taken in daylight conditions with the sun behind the photographer.

Holotype: *McNally* 20.23014 — Photograph. 2316×3088. Truncated close ventral view. Area superior to lips out of frame; skirt out of frame. Hair likely tied dorsally; no occlusion of neckline. *Heleonora lizzia* wb. Elizabeth.M., 2024. © Elizabeth McNally or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 6f27893b736fbeb44fbfc24fec10afd2487c4cd a1d91daec6de441a9bfbf77b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_McNally2.jpg?v=1720291681; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095919/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_McNally2.jpg?v=1720291681

[1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_McNally2.jpg?v=1720291681](https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_McNally2.jpg?v=1720291681)

McNally 20.23710 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject standing on metal platform near large body of water. Shadow behind subject visible on left foot, indicating that photographer is positioned between subject and Sol. *Heleonora lizzia* wb. Elizabeth.M., 2024. © Elizabeth McNally or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** f46504965fb55a6e9a4ac4c7cab6f2e9835967042cf474b5e9162b4f9ec90bee; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_McNally3.jpg?v=1720291681; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095920/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Elizabeth_McNally3.jpg?v=1720291681

2.14.5.11 *Heleonora michellae*

Heleonora michellae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora michellae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with a white background and flowers, following a low-saturation maroon or pink color scheme; with the largest visible flowers characterized by six petals. Smaller flowers with five petals extend from a long vine-like structure also linked to the large flower.

Etymology: From *Michelle* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Michelle* 2024.58044.8750 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Lateral view. Outdoors in park; shallow depth of field. Hair not long enough to cause occlusion of bodice. *Heleonora michellae* wb. Michelle.Ts., 2024. © Michelle Tsang or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** d93fa52d657d1a445f2044dea048b39a11c1dfa38939c4b53cc7fd587c1237f3; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Michelle_Tsang.jpg?v=1720291698; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100805/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Michelle_Tsang.jpg?v=1720291698

Michelle 2024.58044.4339 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view; behind large fountain. Hair not long enough to cause occlusion of bodice. Arms fully adducted. *Heleonora michellae* wb. Michelle.Ts., 2024. © Michelle Tsang or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** d12a8673bef66d3ccb67d9d7e5dd3c51074e07d011fa85326310445c76d3f2d4; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Michelle_Tsang_f787cb0b-4224-4277-be94-13a1b2edc5d4.jpg?v=1720291699; **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260408>

100831/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Michelle_Tsang6_f787cb0b-4224-4277-be94-13a1b2edc5d4.jpg?v=1720291699

2.14.5.12 *Heleonora rachelae*

Heleonora rachelae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora rachelae* is characterized by its fabric, a black-and-white gingham check pattern. The black lines have sub-100% opacity, which result in higher opacity when interconnecting. Vertical black lines are of higher opacity than horizontal lines.

Remarks: *Rachel* is not a typo.

Etymology: From *Rachel* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *McClain 2024.50653.1149* — Photograph. 2810×4000. Truncated ventral view. Subject looking downward. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring right strap. Subject's arm on hair. *Heleonora rachelae* wb. Rachel.M., 2024. © Rachel McClain or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** fd7ff79162626fbed8f4a3d809a32d475631679e80990b5e94a5f1c994d6e61c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Rachel_McClain3.jpg?v=1720292013; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100609/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Rachel_McClain3.jpg?v=1720292013

McClain 2024.50653.3267 — Photograph. 2459×3279. Zoomed-out ventral view. Subject looking downward. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring right strap. Subject's arm on hair. *Heleonora rachelae* wb. Rachel.M., 2024. © Rachel McClain or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 0b35e47053803f4fa13acce3db1121224c2c2ef74487ce49f0817bf08a3f8e72; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Rachel_McClain4.jpg?v=1720291705; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100620/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Rachel_McClain4.jpg?v=1720291705

2.14.5.13 *Heleonora renskae*

Heleonora renskae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora renskae* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material with a white background with cyan and purple flowers in a paint-like pattern, alongside green leaves.

Etymology: From *Renske* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Renske 2024.50053.114* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Angled truncated ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally, obscuring right strap. *Heleonora renskae* wb. Renske.Tj., 2024. © Renske Tjoelker or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** c6d6e4ca15044233460dfbdc86872d7cde7e0577f3a6db25f63f800441b05c21; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Renske_Tjoelker2.jpg?v=1720291705; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100732/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Renske_Tjoelker2.jpg?v=1720291705

Renske 2024.24008.981 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Angled ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally, obscuring right strap. Subject facing camera. Arms fully adducted. *Heleonora renskae* wb. Renske.Tj., 2024. © Renske Tjoelker or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 60ca8f633f50161223d45cc6e168b13bd3f6fef319d41a31cbbf7165828f4624; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Renske_Tjoelker8.jpg?v=1720291706; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100900/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Renske_Tjoelker8.jpg?v=1720291706

2.14.5.14 *Heleonora willmesia*

Heleonora willmesia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora willmesia* is characterized by its fabric, a plain white, possibly off-white fabric, made of an unknown material.

Etymology: From *Willmes* + *-ia*.

Holotype: *Willmes 2024.505.39* — Photograph. 1080×1616. Angled ventral view of *Heleonora willmesia* hanging on plant. © or unknown photographer, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 81f473c1737ee32aae04f918b0d726b92ae3b34b0d51963d3deac2b125c07997; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes9.jpg?v=1720291703; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100936/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes9.jpg?v=1720291703

Willmes 2024.505.3315 — Photograph. 2667×4000. Truncated ventral view. Subject leaning slightly to right. Subject wearing flower crown; likely *Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam. or *Bellis perennis* L.; multiple unidentified berries in various life stages; some green and some purple; and some *Heleonora willmesia* wb. Willmes, 2024. © Pia Willmes or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 5ee16c144d7010850cfd448db02fc774067559ea

c07c248d32f4f6bc89c6619b; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes_211e9360-1aa6-42a1-a813-f5bb72c3315b.jpg?v=1720291702; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/2/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes_211e9360-1aa6-42a1-a813-f5bb72c3315b.jpg?v=1720291702

2.14.5.15 *Heleonora willmesiabis*

Heleonora willmesiabis Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora willmesiabis* is characterized by its fabric, an unknown material, with a white background and floral pattern. The floral pattern dominates most of the fabric, and consists of low-saturation red and yellow flowers, alongside leaves.

Etymology: From *Willmes* + *-ia*, and Latin *-bis* (“twice”) as it is Willmes’s second make.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Willmes 2024.11098.248* — Photograph. 4000×4687. Truncated ventral view. Superior portions of head out of frame. Most of skirt out of frame. Hair positioned ventrally; very minor occlusion of right strap. *Heleonora willmesiabis* wb. Willmes, 2024. © Pia Willmes or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 7053339fe890e875e1245f4cd489d02c013a53e74476c907630f5167367b5e0a; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes5_e76d31ac-b5a3-46fa-b7c1-c462a1383487.jpg?v=1720291705; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408101017/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes5_e76d31ac-b5a3-46fa-b7c1-c462a1383487.jpg?v=1720291705

Willmes 2024.11098.277 — Photograph. 2848×4000. Truncated ventral view. Superior portions of head out of frame. Inferiormost portions of skirt out of frame. Hair positioned ventrally; right strap occluded significantly; left strap fully visible. *Heleonora willmesiabis* wb. Willmes, 2024. © Pia Willmes or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** b05b36d7d0de41dedc43a65b5c9c224df2172a3d47bf07110b7adc3e64c949ec; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes6_3a17b4da-a010-46b7-800b-d56afb050b9b.jpg?v=1720291704; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100027/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Pia_Willmes6_3a17b4da-a010-46b7-800b-d56afb050b9b.jpg?v=1720291704

2.14.5.16 *Heleonora yoannae*

Heleonora yoannae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora yoannae* is characterized by its two distinct fabrics; a plain solid peach fabric on the bust pieces and interelastic fabric; with a subtle white-peach gingham check pattern fabric with lace on the skirt, ventral medial ties, straps, and another trim superior to the superior elastic channel. On the skirt, the lace is in the form of five small holes in a vaguely floral petal-shaped arrangement, running vertically, with gaps of around six gingham squares between each lace line.

Etymology: From *Yoanna* + *-ae*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *McClintock 2024.50987.14* — Photograph. 1638×2048. Ventral view, outdoors in park. Hair positioned mostly dorsally; minor occlusion of right strap. Arms extended outward holding skirt to showcase fabric. *Heleonora yoannae* wb. Yoanna.M., 2024. © Yoanna McClintock or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** 719f892b3ca9ffdb3a3cd8645405500c623c255d9648352cd899d7d91014d602; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock-14.jpg?v=1720291722; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095809/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock-14.jpg?v=1720291722

McClintock 2024.50987.15 — Photograph. 1638×2048. Truncated ventral view. Hair position same as in .14. Area of head above nose out of frame. Inferior portions of skirt out of frame. *Heleonora yoannae* wb. Yoanna.M., 2024. © Yoanna McClintock or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** Silversaga et al. (2024c); **SHA2-256:** ccd1ff5e4e852dfce93451f34f8f5007b16f7e5a7713626b4bbe51c76d94311d; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock-15.jpg?v=1720291722; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095821/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Yoanna_McClintock-15.jpg?v=1720291722

2.14.6 *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta*

Heleonora subsection *Pseudotruetta* Lemuria, 2026; subsectio nova

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* subsect. *Duo- lastica*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta* is distinguished from other *Heleonora* spp. phenetically by the presence of contrasting bias binding on the exterior of the dress, rather than the interior.

Heleonora subsect. *Pseudotruetta* is distinguished from *Truetta* (unpublished), the Truett dress from Christy

Dawn, by phylogenetic origin from the sleeveless Eleonora pattern. Phenetically, a larger corner radius on the neckline may help distinguish, however, numerous *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta* spp. have been sewn with a square shape intentionally closer to the Truett, making this method unreliable. Fabric may be a more reliable indicator; *Truetta* spp. encompass only red and pink fabric prints.

Remarks: *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta* was first developed by Silversaga in October 2025, as a way to replicate the look of the *Truetta* (Silversaga 2025). That year, the Truett dress from the RTW label Christy Dawn had trended throughout summer, which Silversaga attributed to the contrasting bias binding and ties enabling the showcase of the dress's morphology.

2.14.6.1 *Heleonora trudemelinae*

Heleonora trudemelinae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora trudemelinae* is characterized by its solid dark turquoise bias contrast fabric and a floral fabric, primarily consisting of mostly turquoise flowers, with some purple. Distance between superior and inferior elastic channels vertically narrower compared to *Heleonora* ser. *Annettae* spp.

Remarks: Laura Demelin's Instagram account is private. The only accessible holotype rests on Silversaga's website.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Demelin 1090.157* — Photograph. 1680×1280. Collage of two images; left image *Demelin 1090.157.10*, right image *Demelin 1090.157.13*. Left image larger than right. Both images taken outdoors during daytime. Subject in shadow of sun. *Heleonora trudemelinae* wb. Laura.Dem., 2025. Collage stitched together by Jessica Silversaga. Preferred over original Instagram images due to greater ease of reproducibility and excessively long Instagram CDN URLs, and the private status of Demelin's Instagram account. Original photos © Laura Demelin or unknown photographer, 2025, all rights reserved. **SHA2-256:** 742911d30c54a12de057e53d12a4ad58f0c505cfabc837d87c1045d3d886d7ce; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Silversaga_Patterns_Eleonora_Dress8_48020f5c-2b16-4a23-9430-703ec3e14cf4.jpg?v=1759270463; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318155812/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Silversaga_Patterns_Eleonora_Dress8_48020f5c-2b16-4a23-9430-703ec3e14cf4.jpg?v=1759270463

Demelin 1090.157.10 — Photograph. Collage fragment of *Demelin 1090.157*. Top left pixel coordinate (0, 0); bottom right pixel coordinate (959, 1279). Ventral view. Left arm on lateral side of elasticated channels. Right arm fully adducted. Subject leaning slightly to right. Hair positioned dorsally with bilateral single tied strands; left strap slightly obscured by hair. *Heleonora trudemelinae* wb. Laura.Dem., 2025. © Laura Demelin or unknown photographer, 2025, all rights reserved.

Demelin 1090.157.13 — Photograph. Collage fragment of *Demelin 1090.157*. Top left pixel coordinate (960, 0); bottom right pixel coordinate (1670, 1279). Angled ventral close-up view. Area of head superior to chin truncated, outside of frame. Left arm out of frame. Distal right arm out of frame. *Heleonora trudemelinae* wb. Laura.Dem., 2025. © Laura Demelin or unknown photographer, 2025, all rights reserved.

2.14.7 *Heleonora* ser. *Annettae*

Heleonora series *Annettae* Lemuria, 2026; series nova

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora* ser. *Annettae* is the subset of *Heleonora* subsect. *Pseudotruetta* that encompasses all dresses sewn by Annette, an American sewist. See Section 1.2.1 for biographical information.

2.14.7.1 *Heleonora truannettae*

Heleonora truannettae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* ser. *Annettae*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora truannettae* is characterized by its brown color with white dots and diamond-like shapes; from the usage of “topsy turvy” Jamdani cotton from Merchant & Mills as the main fabric, and vintage solid purple washed lawn from Oak Fabrics as the bias contrast fabric. Diamond shapes narrow with transparent diamond-shaped square inset. Two horizontal lines extruding from square diamond to form vague A-shapes.

Etymology: *Truett* + *Annette* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks: Annette's source materials consistently have the typo *Eleanora for the Eleonora dress.

Annette cut the neckline and shoulder ruffle on the grain, as opposed to the bias. Skirt panels were also cut 81.28 cm (32 in) wide due to lack of fabric.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Annette 6059.148* — Photograph. 2160×1440. Collage of two images; left image *Annette 6059.148.12*, right

image *Annette 6059.148.18*. Both fragments 1080×1440. Width consistent with Instagram maximum width of 1080px and 4:3 aspect ratio. Both images taken indoors, daytime; natural light flowing from subject's right, possible window. Window directly behind subject covered with mostly opaque white curtain. No glare, no overexposure. *Heleonora truannettae* wb. Annette.N., 2025. Collage stitched together by Jessica Silversaga. Preferred over original Instagram images due to greater ease of reproducibility and excessively long Instagram CDN URLs. Original photos © Annette or unknown photographer, 2025, all rights reserved. **SHA2-256:** d6887414c192cf6d6412efd59bf58d8903cfedbd52623a3b2da3597ef20120d3; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Silversaga_Patterns_Eleonora_Dress2_04f6d8c3-bdaf-41dc-b67d-8ab3e5b5cb6d.jpg?v=1759268517; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260412144351/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Silversaga_Patterns_Eleonora_Dress2_04f6d8c3-bdaf-41dc-b67d-8ab3e5b5cb6d.jpg?v=1759268517

Annette 6059.148.12 — Photograph. 1080×1440. Collage fragment of *Annette 6059.148*. Top left pixel coordinate (0,0); bottom right pixel coordinate (1079, 1440). Ventral view. Subject's left arm adducted. Right arm holding out skirt. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring wearer's right strap. *Heleonora truannettae* wb. Annette.N., 2025.

Annette 6059.148.18 — Photograph. 1080×1440. Collage fragment of *Annette 6059.148*. Top left pixel coordinate (1079, 0); bottom right pixel coordinate (2159, 1439). Ventral view. Subject facing slightly downward. Subject's left hand on left ear. Right arm holding out skirt. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring wearer's right strap. *Heleonora truannettae* wb. Annette.N., 2025.

2.14.7.2 *Heleonora monokhromos*

Heleonora monokhromos Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* ser. *Annettae*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora monokhromos* is characterized by its solid white main fabric with solid black bias contrast fabric, from Oak Fabrics.

Remarks: The tree in the background of the video is possibly a species within *Quercus* L.; though the possible candidates, *Quercus nigra* L.; and *Quercus imbricaria* Michx. 1801 not A.Gray ex A.DC as suggested by image search do not range within Boston, the subject's known location.

Etymology: From Ancient Greek μονόχρωμος (*monóchrōmos*; “one color”), from which the English word *monochrome* originated, due to the black and white color scheme of *Heleonora monokhromos*.

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Annette 6071.240* — Video. Instagram reel. 720×1280. 14.80s. 30 fps, 2672 kb/s. Four cuts. First cut: subject walks into frame, faces camera, holding skirt out, before making ~360° twirl. Second cut: subject walks toward camera. Third cut: Subject looks back at camera before turning around to face camera and beginning a twirl. Fourth cut: Subject repeatedly twirls through frame before leaving frame at camera's right side, before video ends. Video taken in forest, during the daytime. Tree in background; no conclusive identification. **SHA2-256:** c8a856780acfe94eff6e8c536210649c939a02287f49f4db9a245e46182dd16c (Video by annette.sews [DMtjYKeOzmE].fdash-4270518743180586v.mp4); 526458cb73b953f21cf9d7a2dc9717581cdc6dec69ddfd3dc89b83605cec7873 (Video by annette.sews [DMtjYKeOzmE].fdash-728851763264699a.m4a); 29aaceb3aec6a3b3ed18b825a685b844ba84f1d1146149825be45eb8b22fbb3d (Video by annette.sews [DMtjYKeOzmE].mp4) **Original:** <https://instagram.com/p/DMtjYKeOzmE/>; **Imginn:** <https://imginn.com/p/DMtjYKeOzmE/>

2.14.8 *Heleonora* sect. *Trilastica*

Heleonora section *Trilastica* Lemuria, 2026; sectio nova

Taxonomic placement: Placed in *Heleonora* subg. *Elastica*.

2.14.8.1 *Heleonora fraxina*

Heleonora fraxina Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Taxonomy: Placed in *Heleonora* sect. *Trilastica*.

Diagnosis: *Heleonora fraxina* is characterized by the usage of the fabric *Tanaflora betsia* (Section 3.1.1.1) and having been sewn by Ashley General.

Remarks: The fabric of *Heleonora fraxina* is identical to that of *Liberashira evae* Lemuria, 2026 (unpublished); wb. Eva, 2020; as of May 4, 2026, *Tanaflora betsia* is the first fabric to have been observed in two species. See Tea.S. (2024) for Ashley's original Instagram post.

We also note that Ashley 931.1763 allowed a clearer view of the garment's internal morphology, such as its three elastic channels.

Etymology: From Latin *fraxina*, feminine form of *fraxinus* (“of ash wood”), as a calque translation of *Ashley*, itself from Old English **Æsclēah, composed of *æsc* (“ash tree”) + *lēah* (“wood, clearing”).

Specimens examined

Holotype: *Ashley 931.1620* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Zoomed out. Outdoors. Vegetation in back-

ground. Arms mostly adducted, holding skirt slightly out. Subject facing camera directly. Hair draped bilaterally, very minor occlusion of neckline. *Heleonora fraxina* wb. Ashley.G., 2024. © Ashley General or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 3c9c348550c7b6df497d8d64f23d4b320d75f521eae6b518980f0995cff2cee3; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ashley_General.jpg?v=1720291730; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095925/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ashley_General.jpg?v=1720291730

Ashley 931.1744 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Truncated ventral view. Zoomed further in. Outdoors. Vegetation and garden infrastructure in background. Arms adducted, hands out of frame. Subject facing camera directly. Hair positioned dorsally, no occlusion of neckline ventrally. *Heleonora fraxina* wb. Ashley.G., 2024. © Ashley General or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** fe06a0b9b231c960af85b806a2620b21d0e040b42ee4f538f75deec67210773; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ashley_General2.jpg?v=1720291729; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408095919/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ashley_General2.jpg?v=1720291729

Ashley 931.1763 — Photograph. 2992×2000. Ventral view. Dress on wooden hanger in front of window with curtain. Dress fabric penetrated by light. *Heleonora fraxina*. © Ashley General or unknown photographer, 2024, all rights reserved. **Page:** ; **SHA2-256:** 9e8cb857a04dfb6b41e9bc7ea8b395eeee8b1bd6b40399cfb958a71b2acf9d0c; **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ashley_General6.jpg?v=1720291726; **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260408100029/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0562/9375/2969/files/Ashley_General6.jpg?v=1720291726

3 *Incertae sedis*

3.1 Tana

Tana Lemuria, 2026; unranked

Remarks: Though Liberty fabrics are technically out of the scope of this monograph, which is about Silver-saga, we include descriptions of some fabrics that have recurred for the first time in the LCT-01. The below taxa are considered *incertae sedis* within the root of the LCT-01; that is, not in domain Vestimentia. Liberty also reuses names for multiple distinct designs; either the barcode (the term used on the Liberty website for an SKU) or LCT-01 binomial name can be used for disambiguation.

On floral prints in general. Biological accuracy is often not a consideration when designers design floral prints. Thus, the jargon used in botanical treatments is unsuitable as-is, and just like many other components of biological taxonomy, will require significant modification to accurately describe the morphology of fabric flowers. Flowers by themselves are not plants; they are the reproductive structures of flowering plants (the clade Angiospermae). Anecdotally, the lead author observes that fabric designers often prioritize the flower over the other parts of a plant; especially in top-down views where the non-flower body is not seen. As such, botanical treatments pertaining to any of the leaves, stems, and roots of an angiosperm are likely to go unused.

Reproducibility. Images from Liberty's website have serious unresolved reproducibility concerns. See Section 1.5.

Diagrams. We have created diagrams of the features on some of the fabric holotypes. They are intended to be downloaded as is without images. The user can then align the diagram with the images directly obtained from Liberty's website. We do not embed the files themselves due to copyright concerns.

3.1.1 Genus *Tanaflora*

3.1.1.1 *Tanaflora betsia*

Tanaflora betsia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Description: Physical fabric. 100% cotton (most likely *Gossypium hirsutum* L.). 76 g/m². 1.33 m usable width; max bolt len. 25 m. Liberty recommends line drying and washing at 40° C. **Design.** Stylized flowers on white background. Hexagonal pattern, multiple floral designs (FD). **FD1:** top view, six petals, with small outward radial black lines. **FD2:** top view, six petals. Two-layered core; orange circle surrounding inner white core. Smiley face at core. **FD3:** top view, ~6-8 petals. No clear distinction between petals. Core **FD4:** side view. Two flowers. On left, pink flower; on right, yellow flower. Orange core on both flowers with partial black arch line. Green pedicel. **FD5.1:** Two flowers seemingly laid atop each other. Bottom layer red, top layer orange. **FD5.2:** Two flowers seemingly laid atop each other. Bottom layer red, top layer orange on top, yellow on bottom. **FD6:** Yellow flower. Orange and white core. Line of three dots, two parallel lines, four parallel lines, and single line emanate from core. **FD7:** (number intentionally skipped). **FD8:** Yellow flower. Orange and white core. Significant areas of white color on petals, no line border to rest of yellow flower. Numerous other designs undescribed due to time constraints. Most FDs known to repeat ~10 cm vertically according to hexagonal pattern.

Seller information: Liberty London. URL: <https://www.libertylondon.com/us/betsy-tana-lawn%E2%84%A2-cotton-000544799.html#>. Barcode 5057409022787.

Used for: *Liberashira evae* Lemuria, 2026, unpublished; *Heleonora fraxina* Lemuria, 2026, see Section 2.14.8.1

Specimens examined

Holotype: 000544799-R124365006-1 — Photograph. 2500×3000. Exposure: 1/160s. F-stop: 18.0. Focal: 60.00 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: Canon EOS 5D Mark III. Flat-lay of fabric on white background, zoomed in. © Liberty London, 2017, all rights reserved. **Page:** (*Liberty Fabrics - Betsy Tana Lawn™ Cotton 2026*); **SHA2-256:** 9c53c2b760f637ab47f656741fd7b63b88d840eaa72de6f96888fa55cef201c3; **Original:** <https://i8.amplience.net/i/liberty/000544799-R124365006-1>. **IA:** (unavailable).

000544799-R124365006-3 — Photograph. 2500×3000. Exposure: 1/160s. F-stop: 18.0. Focal: 28.00 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: Canon EOS 5D Mark III. Flat-lay of fabric on white background, zoomed out. One-meter ruler to left of fabric. © Liberty London, 2017, all rights reserved. **Page:** (*Liberty Fabrics - Betsy Tana Lawn™ Cotton 2026*); **SHA2-256:** 83a62d4dd2c2acf4c3a24fb0d4633f3d749182e9aef2e19e33b9a5183161b74; **Original:** <https://i8.amplience.net/i/liberty/000544799-R124365006-3>. **IA:** (unavailable).

4 General remarks

4.1 Filenames

Jessica’s naming conventions for pattern tester filenames are consistent at the pattern-level, but inconsistent as a whole.

Many filenames included the names of the pattern testers, which allowed identification of the wearers. However, some patterns used a purely numeric naming convention, which required us to compare and cross-reference both with Silversaga’s Instagram and other holotypes with known filenames to obtain the names of the sewists.

4.2 Person coordinate system

In this document, we use an *ad hoc* coordinate system modeled on right ascension and declination for describing the direction a specific feature is in from the perspective of the wearer.

We define zero degrees as the direction at which the subject and the camera lens are able to face directly each other.

For photoshoots where the photographer switches position, zero degrees may change. If possible, we may also define the zero degree point as a more consistent landmark that appears in all photographs.

5 Appendix

5.1 Acknowledgements

We thank Jessica Silversaga for her amazing patterns that help bolster a culture of home sewing and advance the slow fashion movement. We thank all the sewists, pattern testers, and the sources we have cited for documenting their projects in intricate detail.

We thank Zoe Edwards for helping start the concept of Me Made May, which has further bolstered a culture of home sewing across the world. Me Made May is described by Edwards as a “wardrobe challenge” (Edwards 2026), though in general, it can be thought of as a time of heightened interest in home sewing and a celebration of homemade; a time of great speciation; and the best time for the *Journal* to publish monographs and taxonomic treatments of sewing pattern taxa as opposed to RTW taxa.

We thank the people of the Archive Team (https://wiki.archiveteam.org/wiki/Main_Page) for assistance in archiving the Silversaga website and making it available through the Wayback Machine.

We thank the people of the Coffee Shop on 4d2.org, where our lead author has posted fragments of the paper time and time again, for being absolutely wonderful people, and being an extra set of eyes to keep errors shallow under Linus’s law; and we thank Sarah, the operator of 4d2, for fostering such a wonderful space.

We thank one of the Coffee Shop’s members, elypony, who helped double-check the identification of *Acer saccharum* in the background of the holotype of *Argenclara morgania* (Section 2.4.1.14). In his freshman year, he took a botany course.

And, we also point out the incredible coincidence that Silversaga is from the same country that gave birth to one of taxonomy’s greatest figures; Carl Linnaeus himself. And now, a Swedish woman and her patterns are the subject of a monograph.

We used R; specifically, *ggtree*, to render tree figures. For information on *ggtree*, see Yu, Smith, Zhu, Guan, and Lam (2017).

5.2 Data availability

Supplementary data is available on Zenodo.

5.3 Information

Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy is the gray literature journal of the First Lemurian Clothing Taxonomy, a system by Lemuria to assign Latin names to dresses using biological methods. The author, known mononymically as just Lemuria, is an Filipino programmer and independent gray literature researcher from Manila.

Disclaimer: *Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy* is a non-peer-reviewed, single-author, citizen science/gray literature publication with no institutional backing.

Publisher article ID: 2026.0010

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20450648](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20450648)

At publication, the journal did not have a DOI prefix.

Work began on the paper on 2026-04-08. Proofreading began by 2026-05-28 in preparation for publication. Final publication took place on 2026-05-31.

Argenclara was put into a species freeze on 2026-04-18 and thus began proofreading. The entire monograph was placed in a species freeze on 2026-05-01 in preparation for publication during Me Made May.

This monograph is part of the Silversaga special issue, a collection of research papers focused on the Swedish sewist and designer Jessica Silversaga and her patterns.

- Visit us at: <https://lct01.lemuria.ph>
- Version control: <https://github.com/a-random-lemurian/lct01.lemuria.ph>
- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/lct01>
- Matrix: <https://matrix.to/#/#lct01:matrix.org>
- Our lead researcher's Instagram: <https://instagram.com/lemuriaph>

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